

Budapest University of Technology and Economics
Doctoral School of Informatics

ADVANCING ROBUSTNESS, INTERPRETABILITY AND
EXPLAINABILITY FOR CLASSICAL AND LARGE ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE MODELS

KLASSZIKUS ÉS NAGYMÉRETŰ MESTERSÉGES INTELLIGENCIA
MODELLEK ROBUSZTUSSÁGÁNAK, ÉRTELMEZÉSÉNEK ÉS
MAGYARÁZHATÓSÁGÁNAK FEJLESZTÉSE

Ph.D. Thesis

Modafar Mohammad Mahmood Al-Shouha
MSc in Electrical Engineering

Advisor: Dr. Gábor Szűcs (PhD, Associate Professor)

Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Informatics
Department of Telecommunications and Artificial Intelligence

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Preface

Declaration of own work and references

I, undersigned Modafar Al-Shouha hereby declare that this Ph.D. dissertation was made by myself, and I only used the sources given at the end. Every part that was quoted word-for-word, or was taken over with the same content, I noted explicitly by giving the reference to the source.

Budapest, 2025.

(Modafar Al-Shouha)

*„I should have thought of this before I
made him. Now it's too late!”*

Geppetto
Pinocchio's creator

Abstract

With the increasing integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into applications, the need for designing systems that are robust, interpretable, and explainable grows. Robustness, in particular, concerns the ability of a system to function consistently under changing or imperfect conditions [173]. Interpretability and explainability, on the other hand, refer to the degree to which a system (and its outcome) is understood by users, allowing more trust and usability [112].

While modern deep learning (DL) has shifted towards large models (LMs), many practical applications still depend on classical neural networks: models typically trained on relatively small, task-specific datasets for use in applications where resources are limited [170]. While they are simpler and relatively transparent, they struggle with shifts in input distributions and require careful design to boost their robustness [43]. I proposed model-agnostic, post-hoc algorithms to extend image classifiers, allowing them to detect out-of-distribution (OOD) instances. Also, I presented S-GCD, a model-agnostic generalized category discovery (GCD) algorithm that is effective on complex domain-specific data (e.g., hyper-spectral imaging).

Large models (LMs) are becoming more popular in solving complex tasks. However, their black-box nature and wide exposure to data render the traditional definition of OOD insufficient. I extended the OOD definition by introducing novel non-semantic types that correspond to the input difficulty (i.e., image, text, and their relatedness). Also, I proposed an approach to create benchmarks along with two datasets for intent classification and visual question answering. Furthermore, I introduced two algorithms (i.e., ReaL and ReDiT) to increase the trust of LMs' prediction confidence score after re-evaluation. Moreover, I explored the usage of LMs in GCD and showed that a stand-alone model can achieve sufficient results in a zero-shot setting. To further improve the performance, I proposed two continual learning methods (i.e., similarity- and prompt-driven).

Beyond robustness, interpretability and explainability play a key role as AI models grow in scale and complexity. Interpretability allows access to the model's inner workings, making it easier to analyze, adjust, and improve. I used it as a tool to identify strengths of existing story visualization solutions, and fused them in a novel design (i.e., Mod-StoryGAN). Also, I discussed the definition of interpretability for KANs and criticized their claims. Lastly, I proposed three XAI algorithms (i.e., PIC-XAI, iPIC-XAI, and PEX-VQA) that operate with multi-modal systems and designed three automatic metrics to assess their performance.

Kivonat

A mesterséges intelligencia (MI) széles körű alkalmazásával egyre nő az igény a robusztus, értelmezhető (interpretable) és magyarázható (explainable) rendszerek tervezése iránt. A robusztusság különösen a rendszer azon képességét jelenti, hogy változó vagy tökéletlen körülmények között is következetesen működik [173]. Az interpretálhatóság és a magyarázhatóság ezzel szemben azt mutatja, mennyire értik meg a felhasználók a rendszert (és annak kimenetét), ami nagyobb bizalmat és használhatóságot eredményez [112].

A klasszikus neurális hálókat általában viszonylag kis, feladatspecifikus adathalmazokon tanítják, és tipikusan kis erőforrásigényűek [170]. Ezek viszonylag egyszerű rendszerek, de nehezen kezelik a változatos bemeneteket [43]. Ezen disszertáció első része képosztályozással és általánosított klaszterazonosítással (generalized category discovery, GCD) foglalkozik. Modell-agnosztikus, post-hoc algoritmusokkal lehetővé tettem a tanuló minták eloszlásától távoli esetek (out-of-distribution, OOD) észlelését. Továbbá bemutattam egy modell-agnosztikus GCD algoritmust (S-GCD), amely hatékonyan működik hiperspektrális bemenettel.

A nagy modellek (LM-ek) egyre népszerűbbé válnak komplex feladatok megoldásában. Azonban fekete doboz jellegük és tanító adathalmazuk mérete miatt az OOD hagyományos definíciója elégtelenné válik. Ezért az OOD definícióját új típusokkal terjesztettem ki, melyek tükrözik a bemeneti minták összetettségét. Új megközelítést javasoltam benchmarkok létrehozására, amely lehetővé teszi nagy modellek OOD-ra való érzékenységének tesztelését feladatspecifikus (szándékosztályozás, képalapú kérdésmegválaszolás) adatokkal. Ezenkívül bemutattam két konfidenciaérték újraértékelő algoritmust (ReaL és ReDiT) az LM-ek predikcióiba vetett bizalom növelése érdekében. Emellett megmutattam, hogy az LM-ek képesek GCD feladatok megoldására, külön tanítás nélkül. Teljesítményük további javítása érdekében két folytonos tanuláson alapuló módszert is javasoltam.

Az MI rendszerek méretnövekedésével a robusztusságon túl az értelmezhetőség és a magyarázhatóság szerepe is egyre jelentősebb. Egy modell belső működésének értelmezése lehetővé teszi annak fejlesztését és javítását. Ezt kihasználva azonosítottam már meglévő történetvizualizációs (story visualization, SV) modellek erősségeit, amelyeket ötvözve létrehoztam egy újszerű SV megoldást (Mod-StoryGAN). Továbbá vizsgáltam a KAN-ok magyarázhatóságának definícióját, és az ezzel kapcsolatos állításokat. Végezetül javasoltam multimodális rendszerekhez is alkalmas magyarázható MI (explainable AI) algoritmusokat (PIC-XAI, iPIC-XAI, PEX-VQA), valamint ezek értékeléséhez használható metrikákat.

Dedication

I dedicate this work to my father
who will be always with me and ...

أهدي هذا العمل إلى والدي
الذي لن يفارقني أبداً و ...

To those I saw ascending to the sky,
not just the souls, but the bodies too.
I admit, whatever I wrote here feels meaningless
compared to the lines you write—
lines of resilience, bravery, and sacrifice.
To him, to her, to them,
to all the unnamed,
to all the ones who became mere numbers,
the ones I do not know.

إلى أولئك الذين رأيتهم يرتقون إلى السماء
ليس بالأرواح فقط، لكن بالأجساد
أعترف أن أيّاً ما كتبت هنا يبدو بلا معنىٍ
مقارنةً بما تكتبون
من سطور الصمود و الشجاعة و التضحية.
له، لها، لهم
إلى كل المجهولين
إلى الذين أصبحوا مجرد أرقام
إلى الذين لا أعرفهم.

I wish to meet you,
to apologize on my behalf
and ask for your forgiveness
for my unforgivable crime—

أتمنى لقاءكم
حتى أعتذر لكم بالنيابة عن نفسي
و أطلب منكم الغفران
على خطيئتي التي لا تغتفر.

silence.

الصمت .

You knocked on the walls of the tank;
I heard that, yet I did nothing.

لقد طرقتم جدران الخزان
سمعتكم، لكنني لم أفعل شيئاً.

I am sorry...

أنا آسف...

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Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the development of AI systems (Section 1.1). Later, it summarizes my contributions (Section 1.2), describes the research methodology (Section 1.3), and outlines the structure of this report (Section 1.4).

1.1 Context

Humans have long imagined machines capable of independent learning and decision-making. This thought dates back to ancient myths like Talos [174] and Golem [59], and continued with the philosophical concepts from Aristotle [21] and Avicenna [177]. The mathematical groundwork laid by scholars like Al-Khwarizmi [97] was the next step towards realizing these ideas. In the mid-20th century, Turing wondered if machines could ‘think’ and ‘learn’ from experience [179, 178]. Around the same period, the term *artificial intelligence* (AI) was coined [126] and the first neural networks (NNs) appeared solving symbolic logic [127], pattern recognition [152], and classification [130] causing waves of hype and optimism.

While these systems were relatively simple and inherently interpretable, their limitations in terms of robustness and scalability were criticized [81, 130, 109]. This led to reduced funding and interest, starting decades of the so-called ‘AI winter’ [133]. The development pace in machine learning (ML) was relatively slow, however, progress continued in clustering, classification and natural language processing (NLP) and several task-specific algorithms (such as: K-means [121], hierarchical clustering [196], decision trees [144], DBScan [47], Gaussian mixture [200], support vector machines [37], random forests [74], spectral clustering [169], etc.) were proposed. A milestone was the introduction of the backpropagation algorithm [154], which allowed the training of larger multi-layer NNs for complex problems, especially in image

and speech recognition. By the end of the century, a large expert system (i.e., Deep Blue) was designed. It could execute a search with a complex evaluation function characterized by at least 8150 parameters [28]. Deep Blue was the first AI to defeat a world chess champion [44].

The progress in the beginning of the century was heavily influenced by the explosion of data and the increased computational resources, starting the era of deep learning (DL). Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [90, 93] revolutionized the field of computer vision (CV). Through successive layers, they transform raw pixels into increasingly abstract features beyond human perception. Long short term memory (LSTM) [75] and gated recurrent units (GRUs) [33] pushed for significant changes in time series data processing and NLP. With their intricate gating mechanisms, they capture complex, non-linear dependencies in sequential data that can be extensive for direct human comprehension. These architectures, along with the generative AI (GenAI) approaches, such as auto-encoders (AE) [86] and generative adversarial networks (GANs) [63], enabled solving more complex tasks, such as image captioning (IC) and story visualization (SV). Additionally, multi-modal tasks like visual question answering (VQA) were addressed, allowing for more human-machine interaction. AlphaGo using reinforcement learning (RL) and policy networks achieved what was considered out of reach for AI, by defeating a legendary player in the board game Go [128].

More recently, transformers became efficient substitutes to previous machine translation approaches [16, 120]. However, modern versions with multi-head attention [183] have found many applications since. Besides their efficiency, the exponential growth of resources led to their wide usage in NLP, CV, and multi-modal learning. They are the foundational architecture of generative pretrained transformer (GPT) [146] and other large language models (LLMs). Starting as next word predictors, LLMs' abilities were further extended to cover more general tasks, becoming large models (LMs). These models are trained on massive and diverse datasets, often outperforming humans in certain tasks [106]. LMs were given access to tools (i.e., Agentic AI), allowing them to make decisions and act autonomously, potentially driving a new industrial revolution [53] and realizing the initial dream of intelligent machines.

While classical AI solutions were enhanced in terms of performance and robustness, some challenges still remain. Creating complex systems increases their opaqueness, raising ethical, legal, and technical questions. Unlike humans, machines can neither explain their decisions nor be held responsible for their actions. And even if AI reached human-like capabilities, it would still be prone to unusual scenarios due to the uncertainty of the real-world.

Regulatory efforts (e.g., the EU AI Act [2]) consider these aspects and aim to establish frameworks for safe AI systems. However, they face criticism due to ambiguity and practical applicability [189]. This dissertation aims to clarify related terms and focuses on obscure black-box models to enhance real-world applicability for such systems.

1.2 Contribution

In this dissertation, I present my findings on the robustness, explainability, and interpretability of both classical neural networks and large models (LMs). The first thesis group introduces model-agnostic, post-hoc algorithms to recognize instances correctly even if they were not represented during training (i.e., out-of-distribution, OOD). Also, it presents a model-agnostic generalized category discovery (GCD) algorithm (i.e., S-GCD) that is effective on complex data (such as hyper-spectral imaging).

The second thesis group extends the out-of-distribution (OOD) definition to accommodate the large models (LMs) and their wide exposure to data. Also, it details a method to create benchmarks and proposes two datasets (i.e., NS-OOD and 3U-VQA). Furthermore, it introduces two post-hoc algorithms (i.e., ReaL and ReDiT) that improve the robustness of these models by re-evaluating their prediction score. Additionally, it presents algorithms that significantly enhance the performance of LMs for GCD task, without any additional training, following continual learning (CL) approach.

The third thesis group shows how interpretability can be used to identify and fuse the strengths of existing story visualization (SV) models to create an enhanced design (i.e., Mod-StoryGAN). Exploring other aspects of interpretability, the claims of the recently introduced KAN were examined and argued. To address explainability, post-hoc black-box XAI algorithms (i.e., PIC-XAI, iPIC-XAI, and PEX-VQA) were designed for image captioning (IC) and visual question answering (VQA). Lastly, this thesis group proposes quantitative metrics to assess XAI methods for multi-modal tasks.

Figure 1.1: Summary of the theses groups and results.

The scope of this work can be defined through the following research questions:

- How is out-of-distribution (OOD) defined for classical neural networks, and how to enhance their robustness across several tasks?
- How to define out-of-distribution (OOD) for large models and how to enhance their robustness across several tasks?
- What is interpretability, and what are its practical implications for AI systems?
- How to enhance the explainability for multi-modal AI systems?

1.3 Methodological summary

Addressing the development of more reliable and transparent AI systems, this work focuses on advancing the technical dimensions of robustness, explainability, and interpretability across a range of model types, including both classical neural networks and large models. I employed a methodology that integrates experimental computer science practices with quantitative and

qualitative evaluation frameworks, following a structured workflow of problem formulation, model development, validation, and analysis.

Research design followed a problem-driven experimental approach with four interconnected phases. Initially, I selected a specific single or a multi-modal task based on a thorough literature review. Then, after identifying the gaps (in terms of robustness, explainability, and interpretability), I developed novel solutions to tackle the task. Also, where required, I studied available terminology and extended the definition(s) to suit recent technologies. Lastly, the proposed methods were evaluated quantitatively and qualitatively using existing or novel datasets and domain-specific metrics.

Data included publicly available benchmarks for the experiments. When needed, I proposed an approach to prepare novel datasets.

Models covered a wide variety of state-of-the-art designs: large models (LMs) and classical neural networks. In most cases, I used pre-trained and publicly available models. When required, I selected and trained an architecture from scratch, and/or designed a novel one.

Evaluation was performed by relevant widely-used metrics. When needed, novel metrics were designed.

Results included quantitative and qualitative analysis to draw conclusions and suggest future work directions.

Ethical considerations were in focus as well. I either used available datasets with the appropriate license or made the novel data public. When relevant, I discussed the details regarding class representation in these datasets and potential biases. Additionally, I made the full code, trained models, and evaluation scripts publicly available on GitHub.

1.4 Outline

The thesis contains five chapters:

- **Chapter 1: Introduction** briefly presents the context of the development of AI systems. In this chapter, I highlight their robustness, explainability, and interpretability aspects. Furthermore, I list my contributions and outline the structure of this report. Also, I detail the research methodology applied to answer this work’s objectives. The literature review is detailed at the beginning of each chapter.

-
- **Chapter 2: Enhancing robustness of classical neural networks** summarizes the new scientific results of Thesis group 1. In this chapter, I present several algorithms that enhance the robustness of traditional classification and GCD.
 - **Chapter 3: Enhancing robustness of large models** summarizes the new scientific results of Thesis group 2. In this chapter, I detail the extended OOD definition and the proposed datasets. Also, I present various algorithms that enhance the robustness for classification, VQA, and GCD.
 - **Chapter 4: Interpretability and explainability in AI systems** summarizes the new scientific results of Thesis group 3. In this chapter, I present Mod-StoryGAN and argue KAN's interpretability claims. Also, I detail several XAI algorithms (i.e., PIC-XAI, iPIC-XAI, and PEX-VQA) and metrics to assess them.
 - **Chapter 5: Conclusion** provides a final interpretation of the results. In this chapter, I conclude the findings and discuss possible future research.

Thesis I: Enhancing robustness of classical neural networks

This chapter addresses the robustness of classical neural networks (NNs), which are still used in systems requiring real-time performance, such as automated industrial inspection. Classification is widely applied in this domain; however, its closed-set nature limits the ability to recognize instances from unseen categories. To address this, out-of-distribution (OOD) detection has been introduced. Existing methods often require modifications to the training process, which is impractical in many real-world scenarios. I proposed post-hoc, model-agnostic algorithms that extend the detection capabilities of classical models, and formalized the task mathematically. Furthermore, addressing a more advanced setting, generalized category discovery (GCD) aims to not only detect but also distinguish novel categories. Most existing GCD methods either depend on training-time interventions or are not well-suited for high-dimensional data such as hyper-spectral imaging (HSI). To overcome these limitations, I introduced a model-agnostic algorithm that improves both clustering and classification performance and is effective for HSI data.

2.1 Introduction

Despite the increasing use of large models (LMs), classical artificial intelligence (AI) systems, such as classical neural networks (NNs), remain relevant in specialized domains such as medical diagnostics [35] and certain industrial processes [147]. Their low computational requirements make them suitable for deployment in resource-constrained environments. They also perform

well with limited data and offer greater interpretability, improving trust and transparency in decision-making [170].

In computer vision, classification is among the earliest and most common tasks addressed by deep neural networks [186]. The availability of large, curated datasets and the development of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [90, 93] have led to significant improvements in classification performance. However, these models are constrained by the training distribution (i.e., in-distribution, or ID) features and attributes [18].

Most classifiers apply a softmax function [62] in the final layer, producing a probability distribution over the K training classes. The model selects the class with the highest probability. A key limitation of this approach is the inability to handle instances from unseen classes (i.e., out-of-distribution). This challenge is addressed by out-of-distribution (OOD) detection, or $K + 1$ classification. To extend the model’s knowledge, one solution is to train it on an additional class representing unknown data, but this is constrained by defining (and sampling) what constitutes an unknown. An alternative approach is to modify the model architecture or retrain the classifier [210, 226], which is often impractical due to resource limitations. Instead, Section 2.3 presents post-hoc, model-agnostic methods that extend the detection capabilities of existing classifiers without retraining or requiring explicit OOD data. These methods extend a K -classifier while maintaining its classification performance. Moreover, Section 2.4 shows the mathematical formulation for the $K + 1$ classification task, its accuracy, and the defined inequality that bounds its performance. Both the formulation and inequality were validated empirically.

Section 2.5 extends beyond OOD detection to address a more specialized task. In practice, it is often necessary not only to detect OOD instances but also to group them. Novel category discovery (NCD) [70] addresses this by identifying new classes within the unlabeled set. However, it assumes that all unlabeled instances belong to unknown categories, which is unrealistic in many real-world settings. To relax this assumption, generalized category discovery (GCD) [184] was proposed, allowing the unlabeled data to include both known (ID) and unknown (OOD) instances. The task becomes more challenging in domain-specific contexts such as hyper-spectral imaging (HSI) [12], where existing methods either perform poorly or compromise semantic information. To tackle this, a novel, model-agnostic algorithm (i.e., S-GCD) that is suitable for complex data was introduced. S-GCD outperformed the sole clustering approach when categorizing known and unknown data.

My contributions can be summarized as follows:

- I introduced post-hoc, model-agnostic algorithms to boost classical classifiers’ robustness, by extending them to be able to detect unknown (OOD) instances (Section 2.3).
- I provided a mathematical formulation and introduced an estimator for $K + 1$ classification accuracy (Section 2.4).
- I developed a model-agnostic algorithm that enhances both clustering and classification performance, and is suitable for complex data such as HSI (Section 2.5).

2.2 Related work

Traditional OOD definition relies on the assumption that supervised learning methods expect excessive similarity between training and test data (e.g., from the same distribution). In real-world settings, model performance can degrade significantly when exposed to data from a different distribution (i.e., OOD), sometimes performing worse than random guessing [43]. Many solutions addressed this by improving various components of the supervised learning pipeline [163].

In computer vision (CV), learning the feature representation is the first component of the pipeline, where the aim is to achieve a proper generalization on unseen target domain instances (i.e., images under different circumstances). Some works tried to learn the disentangled and causal feature representation of the data [19, 115] to improve generalization during training [72, 83, 202]. Others, such as domain alignment approaches, adjusted intra- and inter-domain distances [98, 180, 193]. While the authors of DANN [57, 58] and CIAN [102] used domain adversarial learning to extract domain-invariant features.

Alternative approaches focused on training strategies. Meta-learning methods aimed at domain generalization [51, 79]. Ensemble-based methods combined models trained on different domains [159, 194, 224], while others explored semi-supervised and unsupervised learning [108, 216]. The authors of OpenHybrid [210] combined a base classifier with a discriminative model trained in the latent space. Their flow-based model avoids assigning high likelihoods to OOD data.

Furthermore, the authors of ODIN [107] introduced a post-hoc OOD detector that used temperature scaling and input perturbation, building on prior works [64, 73]. Another approach used a GAN-based model [226], where the discriminator acted as a $K + 1$ classifier for hyper-spectral imaging (HSI) data.

Double probability model (Dpm) [138] was used in constructing some of the combined algorithms. Dpm uses the classifier’s output to compute the cumulative distribution function (CDF) and its inverse. Based on the CDF-transformed outputs, probabilities for class k (P_k) and the OOD class (P_{K+1}) are estimated. If $P_{K+1} > \max_{k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}} P_k$, the instance is assigned to the $K + 1$ class; otherwise, it retains the classifier’s original prediction. This effectively extends the K -classifier to include an OOD class.

Novel category discovery (NCD) [70] was introduced to further categorize unknown instances in open-world applications. It aims to group unlabeled data from unseen categories using knowledge from known classes. This prior information helps reduce clustering ambiguity and improves the quality of the discovered categories. Unlike transfer learning, NCD targets clustering rather than classification. The authors of RankStat [69] showed that self-supervised pre-training benefits NCD. The authors of NCL [222] used contrastive learning to enhance representations, while the authors of UNO [50] proposed a unified objective for learning from both labeled and unlabeled data. Other methods [219] were extended through: (1) modeling inter- and intra-class constraints [101], (2) mutual information-guided knowledge transfer [209], and (3) reusing known class knowledge [223]. One limitation of NCD is the assumption that all unlabeled instances belong exclusively to unknown classes, which is unrealistic in practical scenarios.

Generalized category discovery (GCD) [184] addresses the automatic clustering of unlabeled data with partial knowledge. The key challenge is that the unlabeled data may include both known and novel categories. GCD has been explored in meta-learning settings, as in MetaGCD [197], which aimed to incrementally discover new categories while minimizing forgetting. It leveraged labeled data offline to simulate the incremental learning process during testing. The authors of DCCL [143] improved clustering by alternately estimating visual concepts and learning their representations. While effective for complex natural images, it is less applicable to hyper-spectral imagery (HSI), which lacks the higher-level structures DCCL relies on. Most existing methods treat known and unknown categories jointly during training, which can hinder both generalization and discrimination. This coupled training limits the transferability of category-specific knowledge from labeled to unlabeled data, potentially leading to semantic information loss and reduced performance. To address this, the authors of DPN [13] formulated GCD as a bipartite matching problem between category prototypes. They separated known and unknown categories to enable distinct training strategies, while aligning known categories across labeled and unlabeled data to transfer knowledge and retain semantic structure. However, their use of prototypes to represent entire groups could lead to information loss.

Hyper-spectral imaging (HSI) [12], also known as imaging spectroscopy, evolved from a niche research topic into a widely accessible technology [142]. It is increasingly used in remote sensing due to its ability to capture detailed spectral and spatial information [5], enabling improved analysis of the Earth’s surface. However, HSI presents challenges for supervised classification methods because of its high dimensionality and the limited availability of labeled samples [100, 136]. Several studies addressed different aspects of HSI. One approach targeted denoising, inpainting, and super-resolution [135], while another combined random patch networks with recursive filtering to extract deep features [181]. The authors of HybridSN [153] and JigsawHSI [132] applied convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for classification, and proposed a probabilistic pseudo-label generation framework for semi-supervised learning [161]. These methods assume that all classes are known during training, and they are not designed to discover and distinguish previously unseen categories in open-world scenarios.

2.3 OOD detection for classical neural networks

I proposed single [C2] and combined [J1] algorithms with various combinations to tackle $K + 1$ classification. Unlike previous methods, these algorithms are model-agnostic, and they operate with the original K -classifier without requiring retraining or architectural changes. The goal was to address the task and maintain robustness against various uncertainties, including the nature and extent of out-of-distribution (OOD) data.

The $K + 1$ classification was divided into two steps: (1) binary classification, and (2) K classification (Figure 2.1). The proposed methods were applied to the binary classification step, while the original K -classifier handled the second step. I found that different versions of the combined methods are effective in avoiding either Type I (FP) or Type II (FN) errors.

2.3.1 Problem statement

Out-of-distribution (OOD) refers to data points or instances that differ significantly from the training dataset. Formally, let \mathbb{P} be the set of all probability distributions. \mathbb{D}_{ID} represents the training (i.e., in-distribution, ID) dataset drawn from \mathbb{P}_{ID} (where $\mathbb{P}_{\text{ID}} \subseteq \mathbb{P}$). For classical AI systems, \mathbb{D}_{ID} is well-defined. For an image classifier, \mathbb{D}_{ID} contains a set of images/objects and their class(es). A K -classifier M learns the features of \mathbb{D}_{ID} and associates them with a set of K classes. In this case, \mathbb{P}_{ID} is characterized by the K classes and constrained by the features of \mathbb{D}_{ID} . At inference, M expects an instance x from \mathbb{P}_{ID} (i.e., $x \sim \mathbb{P}_{\text{ID}}$), and computes the softmax (Equation 2.1) over the final-layer logits V (i.e., $V = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_K]$) to assign the

class with the highest score as the predicted label (Equation 2.2). The softmax output is interpreted as the model’s class likelihood.

$$P_i = \frac{e^{\frac{v_i}{T}}}{\sum_{k=1}^K e^{\frac{v_k}{T}}} \quad (2.1)$$

$$P = \max_{i \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}} P_i \quad (2.2)$$

In real-world scenarios, M may encounter a semantically shifted instance x that violates the standard assumption of belonging to one of the K classes. Such x is drawn from \mathbb{P}_{OOD} (i.e., $x \sim \mathbb{P}_{\text{OOD}}$ and $\mathbb{P}_{\text{OOD}} \subseteq \mathbb{P}$) and considered out-of-distribution (OOD). For classical AI systems, instances sampled from \mathbb{P}_{OOD} have characteristics different than the ID data and do not belong to any of the K classes (Equations 2.3 and 2.4).

$$\mathbb{P}_{\text{OOD}} \cap \mathbb{P}_{\text{ID}} = \phi \quad (2.3)$$

$$\mathbb{P}_{\text{OOD}} \cup \mathbb{P}_{\text{ID}} = \mathbb{P} \quad (2.4)$$

A robust model M should be able to identify instances from \mathbb{P}_{OOD} and respond accordingly. The goal is to extend M to detect OOD instances while preserving high classification accuracy on the K known classes, effectively addressing the $K + 1$ classification task.

2.3.2 Single and combined algorithms

To solve the OOD detection post-hoc, I relied on two assumptions: (1) models generally assign lower likelihoods to OOD instances than to ID ones [23], and (2) ID and OOD data are from different distributions [3]. I interpreted the $K + 1$ classification task as two consecutive steps (Figure 2.1): a binary classification to distinguish between ID and OOD, followed by a K -class classification for ID instances. If the input is classified as OOD, it is assigned the $K + 1$ label; otherwise, it is passed to the existing K -classifier. Therefore, my approach was to design the binary classifier while keeping the K -classifier unchanged.

Figure 2.1: $K + 1$ classification stages: (1) binary classification, and (2) K classification.

Single algorithms:

I proposed two single algorithms [6], one of them is the threshold algorithm (i.e., Thr), which operates on the output of the existing K -classifier (Algorithm A.1 in Appendix A). Initially, the classifier produces a probability vector over the K classes, where higher values indicate greater confidence. Thr assigns the $K + 1$ label (OOD) if the highest confidence score is below a predefined threshold $\beta \in [0, 1]$, otherwise, it retains the K -classifier’s predicted class. The threshold value β ($\beta \in [0, 1]$) represents the aggressiveness of the algorithm; higher threshold means that the algorithm is more strict in considering the ID decision from the classifier. Despite that a similar idea was presented earlier by the authors of [210] and [138], they require either end-to-end re-training or access to the training data to obtain a proper threshold value. In contrast, the Thr algorithm does not assume that \mathbb{D}_{ID} is accessible and does not require any data pre-processing or additional model training.

The other proposed algorithm is the discriminator algorithm (i.e., Disc). The discriminator algorithm (Disc), unlike Thr, requires access to \mathbb{D}_{ID} . Disc uses a discriminator from a simple GAN as a binary classifier, followed by a pre-trained K -classifier (Algorithm A.2 in Appendix A). The GAN would be trained solely on \mathbb{D}_{ID} , in which the discriminator is supposed to learn to differentiate between real and fake instances. Later, the discriminator is utilized to detect OOD instances before applying the K -classifier. If the discriminator classifies an instance as fake, it is assigned the $K + 1$ label; otherwise, the K -classifier prediction is considered. While this algorithm involves an additional training step using \mathbb{D}_{ID} , unlike existing methods [57, 58, 72, 83, 98, 159, 180, 193, 210], it does not require any changes to the K -classifier. Also, in contrast to other works [51, 79, 102, 134, 107, 194, 224], Disc is

generic (no specific design choices for the GAN or its components) and does not assume any knowledge of \mathbb{P}_{OOD} .

Combined algorithms: While the simplicity of individual algorithms is an advantage, their performance could be unstable. For instance: (1) the β parameter strongly influences the Thr algorithm, (2) relying solely on the softmax confidence of the K -classifier can be problematic [139], (3) and the discriminator in the Disc algorithm inherits the limitations from GAN training [156]. To address these limitations, I combined the algorithms in various configurations [7]. The overall framework remains the same, with separate binary and K -class classification stages, but the combination occurs at the binary classification step. Unlike single methods, decisions are made jointly by two separate algorithms.

The combination has two main aspects: (1) selecting the individual methods and (2) defining the logical relation between their decisions. I combined the Disc method with a threshold-based method (either Thr algorithm or Dpm [138]). In contrast to Thr, Dpm requires access to training data while setting the threshold dynamically. For the decision logic, I used logical OR and AND operators (Table A.1 in Appendix A). This resulted in four combined variants: ThrAndDisc, ThrOrDisc, DpmAndDisc, and DpmOrDisc.

2.3.3 Experimental setup

I studied the three single algorithms (Thr, Disc, and Dpm) individually to identify their limitations and establish baselines. I also examined and evaluated the four combined variants (ThrAndDisc, ThrOrDisc, DpmAndDisc, and DpmOrDisc). For a comprehensive evaluation, I defined several groups using multiple datasets, classifiers, and performance metrics.

Data

For \mathbb{D}_{ID} , I used E-Mnist (i.e., Extended-Mnist - by merge [36]), and Arab-L (i.e., Arabic handwritten characters set [45]) separately. The training sets were used to train two different K -classifiers, and the experiments were conducted with the test sets (Table 2.1).

Table 2.1: E-Mnist and Arab-L datasets details. K is the number of classes in each dataset.

Dataset	train	test	K
E-Mnist	410,000	10,000	37
Arab-L	40,000	10,000	28

Figure 2.2: OOD with (a) E-Mnist and (b) Arab-L datasets after dimension reduction using t-SNE [114]. The number of components for t-SNE is 2, and it uses PCA initialization with 50 components.

To ensure better generalization and represent varying levels of similarity to \mathbb{D}_{ID} , I used six types of OOD data (Figure 2.2). Four were taken from classical datasets: the test sets of Mnist [40], F-Mnist (Fashion-Mnist [199]), Ku-Mnist (Kuzushiji-Mnist [34]) and B-Mnist (i.e., a binarized version of Mnist). Additionally, I generated two synthetic datasets with Gaussian distributions: R-gauss $\sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 128, \sigma = 12.8)$ and I-gauss $\sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = \mu_{ID}, \sigma = \sigma_{ID})$, where μ_{ID} and σ_{ID} are the mean and standard deviation of the ID (training) data. I generated separate I-gauss sets for each of the ID datasets.

I conducted experiments on mixed test sets, each containing 10,000 instances of ID and OOD data. For each experiment, one ID set was combined with one of the six OOD sets. The proportion of OOD instances was controlled by setting the OOD ratio (i.e., R_{OOD}) from 0% to 100% with 5% increments.

Models

I trained two K -classifiers using the training sets of the two ID datasets. The first, denoted as Classifier-37, was built using the VGG16 architecture with dropout layers, and trained on the E-Mnist dataset (excluding digits), which has 37 classes ($K = 37$). The second, denoted as Classifier-28, was built using AlexNet architecture, and trained on the Arab-L dataset with 28 classes ($K = 28$). Noting that the ID accuracy (A_K) is 0.94 for Classifier-37 and 0.82 for Classifier-28. Additionally, I trained a simple GAN (comprising two convolutional layers in the discriminator and two deconvolutional layers in the generator) on each ID training set. As mentioned earlier, the algorithms do not require a specific design for GAN, and they are model-agnostic.

Parameters

A key variable is the threshold value (β) in the Thr algorithm. I evaluated multiple values in the range $[0, 1]$ using a step of 0.01. Based on the results, I selected the range $[0.90, 0.99]$, which yielded the highest $K + 1$ accuracy with minimal variance (Figure 2.3). This approach helped to reduce potential bias by relying solely on the softmax confidence of the K -classifier [139].

Figure 2.3: The average $K + 1$ accuracy (in dark blue) and standard deviation range (in light blue) from all experiments that include Thr for $\beta \in [0, 1]$. (a) and (b) plots are the results for Classifier-37 and Classifier-28, respectively. Red lines define the range of β value where the accuracy is the highest and the standard deviation is the lowest.

Along with the β value, the OOD percentage in the test set would directly impact overall algorithm performance. Thus, I defined three evaluation groups. In the first, β was fixed at 0.99 while varying the OOD ratio from 5% to 95%. In the other two, the OOD ratio was fixed at 5% and 95%, while varying β (Table 2.2).

Table 2.2: Groups parameters. The first and the second rows are for the β and OOD ration value (or range) per group, receptively.

Parameter	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
β	0.99	$\in [0.90, 0.99]$	$\in [0.90, 0.99]$
OOD ratio	$\in [0.05, 0.95]$	0.05	0.95

Metrics

The first component of the approach is binary classification, where OOD instances are filtered out. If the instance is from the ID data, it is either correctly classified (TP) or results in a Type II error (FN). If the instance is OOD, it is either a true negative (TN) or a Type I error (FP). To evaluate this step, I used sensitivity (TP rate) and specificity (TN rate).

Additionally, I measured the overall classification performance using accuracy and balanced accuracy (Equations A.25 and A.26 in Appendix A) to account for potential issues with unbalanced data that could skew the results [167, 137].

2.3.4 Results

Enhanced robustness through effective OOD detection

I assessed the proposed algorithms’ ability to perform binary classification. As shown in Table 2.3, the AND methods (i.e., ThrAndDisc and DpmAndDisc) achieved the highest sensitivity, along with the single Disc algorithm. These methods were effective at directing ID instances to the next stage, leading to the highest TP rates, and are suitable for scenarios where minimizing Type II error (FN) is crucial. In contrast, Table 2.4 indicates that the OR methods (i.e., ThrOrDisc and DpmOrDisc) performed better in cases where avoiding Type I error (FP) is more critical. The sensitivity and specificity results (Tables 2.3 and 2.4) reveal that: (1) the single Disc algorithm, despite its simplicity, handled binary classification effectively, (2) the ability to detect OOD instances remained within an acceptable range across all algorithms, and (3) the methods showed more stability in terms of sensitivity (TP rate) than specificity (TN rate).

Table 2.3: Mean μ (\uparrow) and standard deviation σ (\downarrow) of binary task sensitivity for all OOD datasets using Classifier-37 and Classifier-28. The three highest scores are in bold.

Algorithm	Classifier-37		Classifier-28	
	μ	σ	μ	σ
Disc	0.858	0.003	0.767	0.024
Dpm	0.651	0.005	0.375	0.023
DpmAndDisc	0.956	0.002	0.850	0.023
DpmOrDisc	0.554	0.005	0.292	0.024
Thr	0.664	0.004	0.700	0.024
ThrAndDisc	0.955	0.001	0.919	0.012
ThrOrDisc	0.567	0.006	0.548	0.003

Table 2.4: Mean μ (\uparrow) and standard deviation σ (\downarrow) of binary task specificity for all OOD datasets using Classifier-37 and Classifier-28. The three highest scores are in bold.

Algorithm	Classifier-37		Classifier-28	
	μ	σ	μ	σ
Disc	0.938	0.137	1.000	0.000
Dpm	0.806	0.121	0.932	0.133
DpmAndDisc	0.754	0.160	0.932	0.133
DpmOrDisc	0.990	0.021	1.000	0.000
Thr	0.916	0.099	0.825	0.275
ThrAndDisc	0.855	0.135	0.825	0.275
ThrOrDisc	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.000

Preserved $K + 1$ classification performance

I used the three groups (detailed in Table 2.2) to evaluate the algorithms’ accuracy in the binary and $K + 1$ classification tasks. The results were consistent across different classifiers and ID data types. The findings in Tables 2.5 and 2.6 further confirm the ones observed in sensitivity and specificity. For example, when the OOD ratio was low (Group 2), the AND methods performed best, while the OR methods excelled at high OOD ratios (Group 3). Group 1 demonstrated the overall superiority of the DpmAndDisc method in terms of accuracy and stability. Additionally, the tables reveal the instability of the single Thr algorithm, which was highly sensitive to the β value, as evident from the standard deviation results for Groups 2 and 3. Although Thr showed a high mean in Group 2, this does not necessarily indicate superior performance, and Disc might be a better choice.

Maintained robustness regardless of the OOD ratio

I further evaluated the algorithms in a more general scenario. Figure 2.4 presents their average $K + 1$ balanced accuracy for $\beta \in [0.90, 0.99]$. Balanced accuracy removes the effect of the OOD ratio, offering a clearer view of the algorithms’ overall performance. The figure highlights the general effectiveness of the AND methods, with ThrAndDisc outperforming the others, followed closely by DpmAndDisc. Since both of these algorithms include the Disc component, they require access to the training data, diminishing the main advantage of the Thr algorithm (i.e., independence from training data).

Table 2.5: Average binary accuracy mean ($\mu \uparrow$) and standard deviation ($\sigma \downarrow$) using Classifier-37 and Classifier-28. The highest three scores in every group are in bold.

		Group 1		Group 2		Group 3	
Algorithm		μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Classifier-37	Disc	0.899	0.081	0.862	0.008	0.934	0.143
	Dpm	0.728	0.081	0.660	0.007	0.787	0.137
	DpmAndDisc	0.854	0.110	0.948	0.009	0.753	0.173
	DpmOrDisc	0.773	0.120	0.574	0.001	0.968	0.025
	Thr	0.790	0.089	0.899	0.108	0.486	0.337
	ThrAndDisc	0.904	0.084	0.963	0.016	0.463	0.324
	ThrOrDisc	0.785	0.119	0.798	0.102	0.957	0.092
Classifier-28	Disc	0.879	0.075	0.748	0.000	0.991	0.000
	Dpm	0.649	0.180	0.364	0.006	0.904	0.139
	DpmAndDisc	0.886	0.083	0.823	0.006	0.928	0.139
	DpmOrDisc	0.642	0.206	0.289	0.000	0.967	0.000
	Thr	0.759	0.164	0.876	0.116	0.292	0.313
	ThrAndDisc	0.869	0.159	0.938	0.025	0.295	0.317
	ThrOrDisc	0.768	0.140	0.687	0.093	0.988	0.005

Table 2.6: Average $K + 1$ accuracy mean ($\mu \uparrow$) and standard deviation ($\sigma \downarrow$) using Classifier-37 and Classifier-28. The highest three scores in every group are in bold.

		Group 1		Group 2		Group 3	
Algorithm		μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Classifier-37	Disc	0.874	0.089	0.816	0.008	0.932	0.143
	Dpm	0.725	0.086	0.657	0.007	0.787	0.137
	DpmAndDisc	0.830	0.108	0.901	0.009	0.751	0.173
	DpmOrDisc	0.769	0.135	0.571	0.001	0.968	0.025
	Thr	0.787	0.097	0.865	0.095	0.484	0.338
	ThrAndDisc	0.879	0.083	0.913	0.016	0.461	0.324
	ThrOrDisc	0.782	0.133	0.768	0.089	0.955	0.092
Classifier-28	Disc	0.821	0.122	0.629	0.000	0.985	0.00
	Dpm	0.644	0.199	0.361	0.006	0.904	0.139
	DpmAndDisc	0.828	0.008	0.703	0.006	0.923	0.139
	DpmOrDisc	0.637	0.231	0.287	0.000	0.966	0.000
	Thr	0.738	0.173	0.743	0.080	0.287	0.315
	ThrAndDisc	0.807	0.163	0.775	0.017	0.288	0.317
	ThrOrDisc	0.752	0.165	0.596	0.066	0.984	0.004

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.4: The average $K + 1$ balanced accuracy (% \uparrow) for all OOD sets, at OOD ratio value in range $[0.05, 0.95]$ for the experiments using (a) Classifier-37 and (b) Classifier-28.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.5: The average $K + 1$ accuracy (% \uparrow) for all algorithms with respect to the selected OOD set for the experiments using (a) Classifier-37 and (b) Classifier-28.

Moreover, Figure 2.5 shows the average $K + 1$ accuracy of the algorithms relative to the OOD set. Across all classifiers, the best performance was achieved with random OOD data (R-gauss). For other OOD sets, the Disc algorithm’s performance was unaffected by the type of OOD data, a pattern also observed in the OR methods.

2.4 $K + 1$ classification mathematical formulation

I presented a mathematical formula [J1] to estimate the $K + 1$ classification accuracy (Equation 2.5), where the first and second terms correspond to binary (OOD detection) and K -class classification, respectively. I also proposed and mathematically proved two inequalities that bound the estimated accuracy \hat{A}_{K+1} (Equation 2.7). Finally, I introduced an exact formula for computing $K + 1$ accuracy (Equation 2.12) and empirically verified that the differences between the exact and estimated values are very small.

2.4.1 Problem statement

My approach to solve the $K + 1$ classification task (detailed in Section 2.3) involves two stages: (1) binary classification to filter out the OOD instances, and (2) K classification for the instances identified as ID (Figure 2.1). Accordingly, the overall accuracy could be estimated by combining high-level information from both stages.

2.4.2 Estimated and exact $K + 1$ classification accuracy

By interpreting the $K + 1$ classification task as two consecutive steps: (1) binary classification (i.e. ID or OOD), followed by (2) K classification, I derived equations to compute both the estimated (\hat{A}_{K+1}) and exact (A_{K+1}) $K + 1$ accuracy of the algorithm. These formulations were then used to define an inequality for \hat{A}_{K+1} . Noting that A_{K+1} requires knowledge of the binary true positive ratio ($TPR = \frac{TP_{ID}}{TP_{ID} + FN_{ID}}$) and the K -classification accuracy (A_K), whereas \hat{A}_{K+1} can be computed using the original model’s accuracy (A_K) only [7].

Estimated $K + 1$ classification accuracy:

To estimate the $K + 1$ accuracy, I incorporated (1) the ratio of OOD data in the test set R_{OOD} , (2) the original model K classification accuracy A_K , and (3) the algorithm binary classification accuracy A_{bin} . This formulation does not require access to detailed task-specific information such as the confusion matrix or the true positive and negative ratios. In Equation 2.5, the first term corresponds to binary classification and the second to K -classification, while R_{ID} denotes the ratio of ID data. An alternative form is given in Equation 2.6. The derivation of the estimated $K + 1$ accuracy equation is detailed in Appendix A (Proof.1 in Section A.1.2).

$$\hat{A}_{K+1} = A_{\text{bin}} \cdot R_{\text{OOD}} + A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\hat{A}_{K+1} = A_{\text{bin}} + A_{\text{bin}} \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \cdot (A_K - 1) \quad (2.6)$$

Additionally, I proved that the estimated $K+1$ accuracy is bounded between $(A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K)$ and the binary classification accuracy A_{bin} (Equation 2.7), assuming the conditions in Equations 2.8, 2.9, and 2.10 hold. This was derived by rewriting Equation 2.5 as Equation 2.11, using the relation $R_{\text{OOD}} = 1 - R_{\text{ID}}$. The derivation is detailed in Appendix A (Proof.2 in Section A.1.2).

$$A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K \leq \hat{A}_{K+1} \leq A_{\text{bin}} \quad (2.7)$$

Where

$$0 < A_{\text{bin}} \leq 1 \quad (2.8)$$

$$0 \leq A_K < 1 \quad (2.9)$$

$$0 \leq R_{\text{OOD}} \leq 1 \quad (2.10)$$

$$R_{\text{OOD}} = \frac{\hat{A}_{K+1} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K)}{A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K)} \quad (2.11)$$

Exact $K + 1$ classification accuracy:

The exact accuracy of the algorithm A_{K+1} is given by Equation 2.12. Noting that Equation 2.12 is undefined when the test set contains only OOD data ($R_{\text{ID}} = 0$), as $TPR = \frac{0}{0}$. The derivation of the exact $K + 1$ accuracy equation is detailed in Appendix A (Proof.3 in Section A.1.2).

$$A_{K+1} = A_{\text{bin}} + TPR \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \cdot (A_K - 1) \quad (2.12)$$

2.4.3 Experimental setup

To validate the proposed equations, I used the same data, models, and parameters settings as in Section 2.3.3. I executed an extensive amount of experiments (~ 76000 experiments¹) and calculated the mean squared error (MSE) between the actual and estimated $K + 1$ accuracy.

¹Total number of experiments = 2 ID sets (classifiers) \times 6 OOD sets \times 20 OOD ratios \times [4 algorithms without Thr + 3 algorithms with Thr \times 100 β values].

Figure 2.6: The inequality empirical results sorted by the calculated accuracy value. The dark blue data is \hat{A}_{K+1} , that lies between $(A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K)$ and A_{bin} in light blue for all the experiments using (a) Classifier-37 and (b) Classifier-28.

2.4.4 Results

The mean squared error (MSE) between the actual and estimated $K + 1$ accuracy across all algorithms was 1.02×10^{-4} and 6.31×10^{-4} , confirming the validity of Equation 2.5. Additionally, the proposed inequality (Equation 2.7) held in all cases (Figure 2.6). \hat{A}_{K+1} was higher than or equal to the lower bound $(A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K)$, but it could not exceed A_{bin} . This confirms the critical role of the binary classifier in the architecture (Figure 2.1), poor separation between ID and OOD reduces the overall performance.

2.5 GCD with classical neural networks

In the generalized category discovery (GCD) framework, the goal is to identify both known and novel classes based on known categories. I proposed S-GCD [C5], a new method that suits complex domain-specific data (such as hyper-spectral imaging, HSI). S-GCD improves the accuracy and enhances the robustness compared to a stand-alone clustering approach.

2.5.1 Problem statement

Formally, given a labeled dataset $\mathbb{D}_k = \{(x_n, y_n) \mid \forall x_n \in X_k, \forall y_n \in Y_k\}_{n=1}^{N_k}$ and an unlabeled dataset $\mathbb{D}_u = \{x_n \mid \forall x_n \in X_u\}_{n=1}^{N_u}$, the GCD model M has three objectives: (1) assigning labels from Y_k to the instances X_k , (2) identifying and classifying the instances X_u that belong

to known classes Y_k , and (3) clustering the remaining instances X_u . To achieve this, M relies on the knowledge obtained from \mathbb{D}_k .

$$\mathbb{D} = \mathbb{D}_k \cup \mathbb{D}_u \quad (2.13)$$

$$X = X_k \cup X_u \quad (2.14)$$

2.5.2 Spectral generalized category discovery

I proposed S-GCD [124] shown in Figure 2.7. Initially, S-GCD pre-processes X by reducing its dimensionality to \tilde{X} using some method (i.e., $X \rightarrow \tilde{X}$). Next, it applies a clustering step to assign cluster labels Y_c to the entire set X . Using Y_k and the assigned Y_c , dummy labels Y_d are generated for the data points. This step ensures that labels are assigned to the entire dataset. Finally, leveraging the obtained labels, a classifier is trained in a supervised manner. A new set labels Y' is created for training, which includes Y_k (for X_k) combined with Y'_d (for X_u). Y'_d is not more than Y_d after excluding the known categories from it, to avoid confusion during the classification step. Assuming K known categories and U novel categories, the trained classifier will be able to classify new instances into one of $K + U$ classes.

Figure 2.7: S-GCD algorithm architecture. It consists of three main components: (1) data dimension reduction, (2) cluster assignment, and (3) classification on combined labels.

2.5.3 Experimental setup

Data

To examine my proposal’s suitability for domain-specific data, I used two hyper-spectral imaging datasets: Indian Pines (Ind-Pines) and Salinas-A [160]. The Ind-Pines dataset

represents a site in northwestern Indiana, containing 145×145 px and 224 spectral reflectance bands in the wavelength range of 0.4 to 2.5×10^{-6} meters. Salinas-A is a high-resolution, 224-band hyper-spectral image of Salinas Valley, California.

Models

For dimension reduction, I applied principal component analysis (PCA) on all the instances (i.e., X). For the clustering step, I used three clustering algorithms: k-means, semi-supervised k-means (semi-k-means), and spectral clustering. The categorization (assignment among classes and clusters) was performed by applying the Hungarian method². For classification, I used two classifiers³: multi-layer perceptron (MLP) and support vector machine (SVM).

Parameters

When applying the dimension reduction (using PCA), I experimented with several principle component counts (i.e., $C = \{5, 15, 30, 60\}$). On the other hand, for clustering, the number of clusters was defined to be the sum of the known and unknown classes for each dataset. Each experiment was repeated with a randomly selected set of known classes.

Metrics

To benchmark the results, I compared the S-GCD outcomes directly with the clustering step results. For known instances, I used accuracy as the performance metric. For novel categories, I employed the Rand index, as commonly practiced in unsupervised clustering.

2.5.4 Results

I evaluated S-GCD by comparing it with the stand-alone clustering method. The results in Tables 2.7 and 2.8 are for experiments with principal components set to 30 (i.e., $C = 30$)⁴. Each table includes the baseline clustering performance and two S-GCD variations using MLP and SVM classifiers.

The results show that exploiting the obtained information about the inner relationships in the data to train a classifier enhanced the final outcome. S-GCD, regardless of the embedding dimension, used classifier type or clustering algorithm, outperformed the sole clustering approach. For example, S-GCD increased accuracy by up to four times on Salinas-A and two

²Using SciPy [187] implementation.

³Using scikit-learn [26] implementation.

⁴Further analysis for $C = \{5, 15, 60\}$ is detailed in Appendix A (Tables A.2 - A.7).

times on Ind-Pines. Furthermore, using MLP generally led to slightly better performance than SVM, though the improvement was not always substantial. Overall, the Ind-Pines dataset appeared more challenging, likely due to its relatively higher complexity.

Table 2.7: Accuracy (\uparrow) results for Salinas-A and Ind-Pines datasets ($C = 30$). The columns contain the three clustering methods in addition to the average accuracy per row (last column). The best results are in bold.

	Algorithm	k-means	spectral	semi-k-means	average
Salinas-A	clustering	0.759	0.313	0.289	0.454
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.966	0.965	0.966	0.966
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.993	0.993	0.995	0.994
Ind-Pines	clustering	0.423	0.466	0.423	0.437
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.853	0.846	0.843	0.847
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.860	0.879	0.860	0.866

Table 2.8: Rand index (\uparrow) results for Salinas-A and Ind-Pines datasets ($C = 30$). The columns contain the three clustering methods in addition to the average accuracy per row (last column). The best results are in bold.

	Algorithms	k-means	spectral	semi-k-means	average
Salinas-A	clustering	0.968	0.944	0.964	0.959
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.979	0.757	0.979	0.905
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.997	0.950	0.996	0.981
Ind-Pines	clustering	0.772	0.745	0.739	0.752
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.858	0.914	0.875	0.882
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.886	0.902	0.909	0.899

2.6 Conclusion

This chapter focused on improving the robustness of classical neural networks (NNs) in real-world scenarios where inputs may come from unknown categories. Two tasks were addressed: OOD detection using image datasets and generalized category discovery (GCD) using hyper-spectral imaging data. I first defined the relevant concepts, such as out-of-distribution (OOD) and novel categories, and then proposed model-agnostic solutions to improve a classifier’s robustness.

For OOD detection, I proposed two set of algorithms. The first group includes two single algorithms, while the second group combines the single algorithms into four variations. Evaluation showed that DpmAndDisc and ThrAndDisc algorithms provided robust overall performance; they were better at reducing false negatives (Type II errors), while OR variants were more effective in high-OOD scenarios by reducing false positives (Type I errors).

Additionally, I derived mathematical expressions for both the exact (A_{K+1}) and estimated (\hat{A}_{K+1}) $K + 1$ accuracy. I also proved, both theoretically and empirically, that the inequality ($A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K \leq \hat{A}_{K+1} \leq A_{\text{bin}}$) always holds.

Lastly, I addressed a more practical scenario within the generalized category discovery (GCD) framework. I presented S-GCD targeting domain-specific data such as hyperspectral images. Across datasets and settings, S-GCD consistently outperformed clustering-only baselines.

Thesis II: Enhancing robustness of large models

Large models (LMs) have achieved remarkable results in computer vision (CV) and natural language processing (NLP). Such models are fine-tuned for downstream tasks like intent classification and visual question answering (VQA). Their wide exposure to data demands formalizing a novel definition of what constitutes out-of-distribution (OOD). I expanded the conventional definition of OOD and introduced a method to create benchmark datasets. Also, I proposed two approaches (i.e., ReaL and ReDiT) to enhance the robustness of LM-based intent classifiers and VQA models. By re-evaluating the prediction score, they achieve a more reliable confidence for the answers. Additionally, I showed that a stand-alone LM-based VQA model (LVQA) could perform generalized category discovery (GCD) efficiently. I further enhanced its performance by two lightweight methods (i.e., similarity- and prompt-driven). All the proposals in this chapter are post-hoc, model-agnostic, and well-suited with LM-based artificial intelligence (AI) systems.

3.1 Introduction

Large models (LMs) have gained attention due to their capabilities. They are utilized in a wide range of applications from writing software [129] to generating functional protein sequences [122]. However, training an LM is an expensive process; it consists of billions of trainable weights, and needs to undergo a long training on enormous datasets [106]. Hence, fine-tuning them is a common practice [155]. However, due to this inherited knowledge,

investigating such models in the context of out-of-distribution (OOD) detection requires expanding the basic definitions and assumptions.

Two tasks were mainly addressed: intent classification and visual question answering (VQA). In intent classification (also known as intent recognition or detection), the objective is to understand the purpose of a user’s request expressed in a natural language (text or speech) [30]. LM-based models have been used and could achieve high accuracy in this task [211]. However, in real-life applications, facing OOD instances can still influence performance. This also applies to VQA, but the challenge becomes more complex due to its multi-modal nature. Few previous works investigated abnormal test conditions and attempted to define various anomalies for VQA [94, 61] without considering LMs’ capabilities.

Section 3.3 shows my approach to extending the conventional definition of OOD to better align with LM-based systems. I detailed the potential sources of difficulty for intent classifiers and VQA models, and categorized the OOD types accordingly. Moreover, I created a categorical scale that can be applied to assess the input scenario difficulty based on a set of criteria. To simulate challenging/OOD scenarios for LM-based models, I proposed a method to create benchmark datasets. I published two open-source and customizable datasets for intent classification (i.e., NS-OOD) and VQA (3U-VQA).

Sections 3.4 and 3.5 introduce post-hoc, model-agnostic methods (i.e., ReaL and ReDiT) that enhance the robustness of LM-based systems. ReaL was designed to increase the trust in intent classifiers. It recalibrates the original confidence score using a temperature-adjusted softmax formulation. On the other hand, ReDiT operates similarly for large visual question answering (LVQA) based on the input scenario difficulty. The experiments showed that both methods enhanced the robustness of LM-based solutions.

Lastly, Section 3.6 focuses on LMs used for generalized category discovery (GCD). It shows that a stand-alone LVQA model could perform the task using zero-shot prompting, without access to labeled data for feature extraction. Moreover, two lightweight yet effective methods were introduced: similarity-driven and prompt-driven. They improved GCD performance through a continual learning (CL) paradigm with minimal to no computational training overhead. Both methods are (1) post-hoc, (2) model-agnostic, and (3) suitable for common and domain-specific data.

My contributions can be summarized as follows:

- I extended the OOD definition, taking into account the abilities of LM-based intent classifiers and VQA models, and introduced a method to create benchmark datasets.

- I proposed ReaL, a post-hoc, model-agnostic method to increase the trust in LM-based intent classifiers.
- I proposed ReDiT, a post-hoc, model-agnostic method to enhance LVQA models' robustness with respect to the input conditions.
- I demonstrated that a stand-alone LVQA model can perform GCD in a zero-shot setting, and enhanced its performance by two post-hoc, model-agnostic, lightweight continual learning (CL) approaches.

3.2 Related work

Large models (LMs) are trained on vast datasets to learn patterns, grammar, and meaning [41]. For example, BERT (as a large language model, LLM) understands context from both directions (left and right) within a sentence, capturing deep contextual meaning, making it highly effective for tasks like text embedding.

Several LMs were designed to perform intent classification. MiniLM [195] uses transformers similar to BERT, while XLM [10] is a developed version of RoBERTa. Both models use the XLM-R tokenizer and have a fixed maximum input length. In contrast, XLNet [203] has a dynamic input length, since it follows a permutation language modeling approach instead of the traditional one. It employs Transformer-XL [39] as the backbone model and uses its own tokenizer.

Similarly, LM-based visual question answering (LVQA) models are available with various architectures. Such models are vision-language models that were pre-trained on datasets containing an enormous amount of image-text pairs [145]. A simple encoder-decoder model, GIT [192], generates the answer in an auto-regressive way after treating the question as a text prefix. The model has two different variants: Large and Base. On the other hand, BLIP [99] was pre-trained using a multi-modal mixture of an encoder-decoder model. Later, it was fine-tuned for VQA by encoding the image-question pair, then passing this embedding to the decoder. Moreover, the authors of [85] presented a minimal architecture that is free of convolution and region supervision (i.e., ViLT). It tackles VQA as a classification task, where every token in the vocabulary is a separate class. Compared to GIT and BLIP, ViLT has a smaller vocabulary size, and the answer is limited to one word. Another widely used model is Google's Gemini [4] that was built on BERT. It incorporates advanced reasoning capabilities, enabling more complex understanding and content generation.

OOD for LMs is an emerging research direction. Although the traditional definition is well formulated (Section 2.2), it is only applicable to the cases where the training data is bounded. The authors of [201] discussed this limitation in the framework of classical image classifiers, and provided a more detailed categorization (e.g., semantic and non-semantic shifts), whereas [211] addressed LM-based text intent classifiers, and introduced two new types of data (i.e., OOD-OOS and ID-OOS). Nevertheless, their approach requires knowledge of the training data, which is challenging when using LMs. Similarly, the authors of [225] explored OOD for intent classification in inference and training phases. However, their method demands either access for the model’s inner layers or full re-training.

Only a few works addressed multi-modal settings, such as VQA [165]. The authors of [94] systematically defined various anomalies, most of which originate from the classical definition of OOD. Thus, they are not applicable when dealing with pre-trained LMs. The authors of MUTANT [61] followed a type exposure approach. They used input mutations to train VQA models with the goal of out-of-distribution generalization. This method requires model re-training, hence, being impractical.

More recently, the authors of [165] focused on evaluating several detection techniques, and extended their work by evaluating a single large model (i.e., X-VLM [207]). They suggested equipping LMs with an OOD detection mechanism to prevent them from answering. For benchmarking, they used popular VQA datasets to compose a validation set.

The authors of NExT-OOD [213] constructed an OOD video question answering benchmark. They identified two types of false correlations (i.e., vision-answer and question-answer biases). The proposed dataset is useful for quantifying the generalizability of the model and measuring its reasoning ability. However, it only contains ordinary scenes while lacking unusual and unknown objects.

Lastly, the authors of [215] evaluated the performance of several multi-modal LMs under OOD scenarios. They showed that in-context learning (ICL) could enhance these models’ generalization capabilities. All these works investigated the basic setting of OOD without considering LMs’ exposure to data.

Generalized continual category discovery (GCCD) [217] follows a continual learning (CL) [105] paradigm to solve generalized category discovery (GCD). It assumes that the model continuously handles and learns from new sequential data to discover novel categories. This task has been explored in the literature under various terms, such as continuous generalized category discovery [82], continuous category discovery [217], and incremental generalized category discovery [220]. None of these methods leveraged the strengths of LMs.

3.3 Extending OOD definition for LMs

The conventional definition of OOD emphasizes semantic novelty or class unawareness. In other words, instances are considered OOD only if they do not belong to classes included in the training (ID) data. This definition is insufficient when considering the extensive data exposure of LMs. Thus, I extended the OOD definition, introducing novel non-semantic types with input scenario difficulty categorization. Furthermore, obtaining publicly available datasets that correspond to the extended OOD definition is infeasible. Therefore, I introduced a method to create benchmark datasets, and demonstrated its applicability by forming two datasets for intent classification [C6] (i.e., NS-OOD) and visual question answering [J2] (i.e., 3U-VQA). I showed that the extended definition poses serious challenges for LM-based systems, and the proposed input scenario difficulty estimation is valid.

3.3.1 Problem statement

For classical AI systems (as detailed in Section 2.3.1), \mathbb{P}_{ID} is typically represented by a well-defined dataset \mathbb{D}_{ID} , which encompasses a set of instances X and their corresponding labels/targets Y . However, with LMs' wide exposure to data, characterizing \mathbb{P}_{ID} (based on \mathbb{D}_{ID}) and consequently \mathbb{P}_{OOD} (Equations 2.3 and 2.4) is impractical. As a result, extending the concept of out-of-distribution (OOD) was required to suit LM-based AI systems' capabilities. Moreover, it is reasonable to assume that \mathbb{D}_{ID} encloses all known published datasets, and obtaining publicly available \mathbb{D}_{OOD} becomes challenging. This is even more amplified in the case of a multi-modal task (such as VQA). Thus, designing and building customizable datasets is deemed necessary.

3.3.2 Extended OOD definition

To address the limitations of the traditional OOD definition, I introduced novel OOD types [8, 172] for both visual (image) and textual (question) modalities. Moreover, in contrast to the earlier works, I considered the combined difficulty (i.e., between image and text) when dealing with VQA.

The extended definition fits both single- and multi-modal systems. For instance, image-related criteria suit image classification or image captioning, text-related is useful for intent classification or text-to-image generation, while the three aspects (i.e, image-related, text-related, and their relatedness) can be applied to VQA.

Image-related criteria:

To understand the image difficulty, a question arises: “what makes an image more challenging?”. The matter of subjectivity might interfere with the answer. However, it is clear that certain objective features contribute to the image’s interpretation difficulty. These features can be classified along two dimensions: (1) macro and micro, and (2) semantic and non-semantic (Table 3.1). I defined several potential challenging examples: (1) *full noise*, (2) *unusual setup*, (3) *unknown object*, (4) *far distribution*, (5) *fully altered*, and (6) *partially altered*.

Full noise image lacks any comprehensible pattern, making it difficult for the model to extract useful information. A good example is a Gaussian noise image; in addition to its inherent randomness, the characteristic of the Gaussian distribution can be tricky and may cause model hallucination [212].

Unusual setup occurs even when the object(s) or/and features(s) are known to the model, but the object exhibits inconsistent feature or situation. Several examples fall under this category, such as: a blue dog in front of a yellow house, a pharaoh riding a bike, etc.

Unknown object category aligns with the classical definition for OOD, and would comprise more examples if M is a classical (not LM-based) model. Nevertheless, due to possible knowledge gaps in LMs [221], I still considered this category. For instance, even in rare cases, if the image contains an unknown object (not included in \mathbb{D}_{ID}), the model will not be able to recognize it.

Far distribution instances are sampled from a distant distribution to the training data ($\sim \mathbb{P}_{\text{OOD}}$). This type corresponds with the conventional OOD definition and is mostly irrelevant for large models. For instance, a model that is trained on the Mscoco dataset [110] would have difficulties in dealing with an instance from the Mnist dataset [40].

Fully altered images category can contain many examples, since processing is a broad term. This includes, but is not limited to, resizing, gray-scaling, style changing, and blurring. Similar to the previously discussed categories, this one assumes that an image will be more difficult if it lacks enough information. Noting that in this category, the image is entirely manipulated (not just part of it).

Partially altered images category is very similar to the previous one; however, as the name suggests, only part of the scene is manipulated (e.g., on object-level). The model, in this case, can comprehend the scene partially, but it is likely to provide an incorrect answer if asked about the manipulated part.

Table 3.1: Image-related criteria are divided into two dimensions: (1) macro (full image level) vs. micro (object/partial level) and (2) semantic vs. non-semantic.

	semantic	non-semantic
macro	Full noise	Fully altered
	Far distribution	
micro	Unknown object	Unusual setup
		Partially altered

Text/Question-related criteria:

To understand the question difficulty, I studied both semantic and non-semantic aspects. I defined four attributes and combined: (1) *used language* (d_{Qu}), (2) *specificity* (d_{Qs}), (3) *length* (d_{Ql}), and (4) *structural complexity* (d_{Qc}). These attributes are not mutually exclusive, and they overlap with each other on different levels.

Used language (d_{Qu}) is a crucial aspect. Although LMs exhibit excellent linguistic skills, and they are proficient in various styles (e.g., formal, scientific, etc.) [129] and across several languages, it remains well-documented that performance is still best in English [55, 32]. This limitation arises from the excessive availability of English training data and content compared to other languages [176].

Specificity (d_{Qs}) is a semantic aspect of the question. A specific question has a detailed objective (e.g., contains relevant adjectives and/or nouns) and a smaller (more exact) set of expected answers. For instance, “*what is the blue object in the image?*” is a specific question, while “*what is in the image?*” is not.

Length (d_{Ql}) is a more objective aspect than the others. It can be defined by the number of words/tokens in the question. By processing a longer question, the model may lose the main point of it.

Structural complexity (d_{Qc}) is a syntax-related aspect that can be challenging to define. More ambiguous references (e.g., his, whose) and extensive usage of linking words (e.g., thus, albeit) make a question more complex. For example, asking directly: “*what is the right object’s color?*” is simpler than “*considering the two objects in the image, what is the right one’s color?*”, where the model needs to consider the connections within the sentence.

Similar to the image-related criteria set, the question-related set can be measured on the semantic and non-semantic scale. All of the criteria are non-semantic except for the *specificity*. Unlike the other aspects, this semantic attribute may require manual evaluation as well.

Combined criteria (relatedness):

Lastly, when dealing with VQA models, beyond the challenges arising independently from the image I and the question Q , I defined an additional non-semantic type originating from the relation between them (i.e., *relatedness*). For instance, a specific question “*what is the brown dog doing?*”, can be: (1) highly related (if there is a brown dog in the image), (2) partially related (in case of a blue dog), or (3) not related (otherwise). Noting that, the image and question can be unrelated even if neither of them contains semantic OOD elements (unknown objects and/or segments).

3.3.3 Novel OOD datasets

NS-OOD (i.e., Non-Semantic OOD) is a single-modality dataset for LM-based intent classification. It was created by manipulating two question-related criteria (from Section 3.3.2): *used language* and *length*.

The first version of NS-OOD (i.e., $d_{Q_u} = 1$ and $d_{Q_l} = 0$) was created by translating the English subset of the Massive dataset [52] into two languages¹ that are not part of it: Esperanto (i.e., *eo-short*) and Punjabi (i.e., *pa-short*). I picked these two languages to reflect higher levels of difficulty; while Esperanto is an artificial language and it is relatively close to the Latin language family, Punjabi is a distant language with a different writing system. For the other version of NS-OOD (i.e., $d_{Q_l} = 1$), I constructed longer versions of the (three languages) subsets: *en-long*, *eo-long*, and *pa-long*. To do so, each query was repeated until it reached the maximum input length of the used models.

In overall, NS-OOD contains 5940 English instances (i.e., $d_{Q_u} = 0$), and 11880 non-English instances (i.e., $d_{Q_u} = 1$) split equally between Esperanto and Punjabi languages. Regarding the length, NS-OOD has an equal number (i.e., 8910 instances) of *long* (i.e., $d_{Q_l} = 1$) and *short* (i.e., $d_{Q_l} = 0$) types.

3U-VQA (i.e., Usual, Unusual, and Unknown object scenarios for LVQA models with difficulty scoring dataset) is a novel, open source, customizable, multi-modal dataset. Each instance is an image-question pair associated with a set of features representing the criteria (detailed in Section 3.3.2).

To construct 3U-VQA, 272 questions were formed using placeholders for the objects and their features, 5 of them suitable for extremely difficult images. For the images, 4 *usual*

¹Using Google Translate python package: github.com/ssut/py-googletrans

Figure 3.1: Two examples from 3U-VQA dataset: (a) *unusual* setup and (b) noisy image.

and 5 *unusual* objects were generated². Additionally, 4 characters for the *unknown* set (Figure 3.2) were designed to ensure that they are not present in any existing dataset and were not encountered by any model during training or fine-tuning stages. Each image (e.g., Figure 3.1a) represents a simple scene with a single character placed in front of a neutral background (i.e., white building). Additionally, to simulate the extreme image difficulty scenario, I sampled 4 noisy images from Gaussian distributions (Figure 3.1b): $I \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 0.5, \sigma \in \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5\})$. Overall, 3491 question-image pairs were obtained.

Figure 3.2: The characters in 3U-VQA dataset: (a) *usual*, (b) *unusual* and (c) *unknown*.

3.3.4 Input scenario difficulty estimation

Following the extended OOD definition (detailed in Section 3.3.2), the input scenario difficulty for a model is either sourced from a single- (e.g., the input text in intent classification) or multi-modality (e.g., the text, image and their relatedness for VQA). I suggested scoring the difficulty of each criterion either manually or automatically. The scores range from low (0) to high (1), and they are aggregated to estimate the input scenario difficulty D_{score} .

²Using StableDiffusion [150].

Image-related difficulty (D_I):

To score the image-related difficulty D_I manually, I assigned 1 for *full noise*, 0.5 for partially difficult (i.e., *unusual* and *unknown*) and 0 otherwise (i.e., *usual*). On the other hand, automatic image difficulty can be estimated by using Entropy or compression complexity (Figure 3.3). The image was considered a major factor, since in extreme cases (i.e., when $D_I = 1$) it could mislead the model entirely.

Figure 3.3: The (a) relative entropy and (b) relative compression (PNG) complexity for five examples (bottom to up): (1) Red (one-color image), (2) Mnist [40], (3) F-Mnist [199], (4) Cifar-10 [89], (5) 3U (3U-VQA), and (6) Rand (random noise).

Text/Question-related difficulty (D_Q):

To estimate the text-related difficulty D_Q manually or automatically (e.g., using relative length or dependency tree depth), each criterion in the text-related criteria (i.e., d_{Qu} , d_{Qs} , d_{Ql} and d_{Qc}) was scored separately. Not all criteria influence the model equally; thus, I considered *used language* only to be major. D_Q is calculated using Equation 3.1, where $D_{Q_{avg}}$ was the overall average of text-related criteria.

$$D_Q = \max(d_{Qu}, D_{Q_{avg}}) \quad (3.1)$$

Combined difficulty, relatedness (D_R):

Relatedness would be manually scored by 0 (for fully), 0.5 (for partially), or 1 (for not related) questions. Automatic estimation can be achieved by using available similarity measures like CLIP similarity [145].

Overall input scenario difficulty score (D_{score}):

The overall scenario difficulty score is denoted by D_{score} (Equation 3.2). The formula combines D_I and D_Q . If the text or the image is not part of the input (e.g., intent classification), then D_R is neglected. Otherwise, if both text and image are present (as in case of VQA), the average is calculated considering all three difficulty scores.

$$D_{\text{score}} = \frac{\alpha \cdot D_Q + \beta \cdot D_I + \gamma \cdot D_R}{\alpha + \beta + \gamma} \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

$D_Q \in [0, 1]$; text/question-related difficulty score

$D_I \in [0, 1]$; image-related difficulty score

$D_R \in [0, 1]$; combined (relatedness) difficulty score

$\alpha \in \{0, 1\}$; 1 if the model takes text/question as input, otherwise 0

$\beta \in \{0, 1\}$; 1 if the model takes image as input, otherwise 0

$\gamma = \alpha \cdot \beta$; $\gamma \in \{0, 1\}$

3.3.5 Experimental setup

To show the validity of the novel OOD types, I checked the relationship between the input scenario difficulty D_{score} and the model’s performance, using various sets of features (Table 3.2). I also investigated the significance of each criterion. Lastly, I studied the advantages and limitations of the manual and automatic difficulty estimation approaches.

Data

For intent classification, I used the English test set of Massive dataset [52] (i.e., *en-short*) with 2970 instances as ID, while the rest (i.e., non-English and long) as non-semantic OOD. In terms of D_{score} , I treated the *used language* as a major criteria, thus, D_{score} is assigned 0 for *en-short* (i.e., $d_{Q_u} = 0$ and $d_{Q_l} = 0$), 0.5 for *en-long* (i.e., $d_{Q_u} = 0$ and $d_{Q_l} = 1$), and 1 otherwise (i.e., $d_{Q_u} = 1$).

Furthermore, for 3U-VQA, I manually assigned scores from low (0) to high (1) for each criterion and calculated D_{score} using Equation 3.2. To achieve a more objective estimation and a continuous scoring system, I measured the difficulty automatically. For images, D_I was

Table 3.2: Feature sets details. The first three sets comprises the original probability (P), the overall difficulty score (D_{score}), and the set of difficulty scores ($Diff$). Two more sets were created by combining P with D_{score} and $Diff$ separately.

	Name	Items
1	P	original probability (P)
2	D_{score}	overall difficulty score (D_{score})
3	$Diff$	Image difficulty (D_I)
		<i>Relatedness</i> (D_R)
		<i>Used language</i> (d_{Qu})
		<i>Specificity</i> (d_{Qs})
		<i>Length</i> (d_{Ql})
		<i>Structural complexity</i> (d_{Qc})
4	P and D	feature sets P and D_{score}
5	P and $Diff$	feature sets P and $Diff$

estimated by the relative compression complexity. To do so, I performed the following steps on each image: (1) resizing into a common size (e.g. 28×28), (2) compressing it using PNG compressor and obtaining a string of bits, (3) measuring the length of the resulted string and normalizing it by the highest complexity (i.e., *full noise* image). For text, I employed a different method for each criterion. For *used language*, similar to the manual approach, I used binary scoring (i.e., the text is either in English 0 or not 1). For *specificity*, I counted the number of nouns and adjectives in each text and mapped it to a scale from 0 (the most specific) to 1 (the least specific). Similarly, for *length*, I measured the relative length of each text in the dataset to the longest question. For *structural complexity*, I built the dependency tree for each text and obtained the depth. Then, I normalized the depth by the maximum depth in the dataset. Lastly, the *relatedness* was measured using CLIP similarity. For each instance, both the image and the question were embedded, and the cosine similarity between them was calculated. The detailed statistics of the dataset are shown in Appendix A (Figures A.1 - A.4 in Section A.2.4).

Models

In order to cover different backbone architectures and language modeling approaches, I utilized three LMs³ (i.e., MiniLM, XLM, and XLNet) and fine-tuned them for intent classification using the English training and validation datasets from Massive (Table 3.3). MiniLM and XLM have a maximum input token length, 512 and 514, respectively. In contrast, XLNet has

³Using HuggingFace implementation: huggingface.co

Table 3.3: Size is the approximate number of parameters (in millions) and K is the number of classes (for intent classifiers) or the vocabulary size (for LVQA models).

	intent classification			VQA			
	MiniLM	XLM	XLNet	GIT-Base	GIT-Large	BLIP	ViLT
size	118	278	117	177	395	385	118
K	60	60	60	30,522	30,522	30,524	3,129

no fixed maximum input length. For VQA, I utilized four LVQA models⁴ (Table 3.3): BLIP, ViLT, and two variations of GIT (Base and Large).

To validate the difficulty categorization, I trained two classifiers: logistic regression (LR) and multi-layer perceptron (MLP)⁵, to predict whether the model’s answer is correct or not based on various set of features (Table 3.2). I used a balanced subset of the 3U-VQA dataset (75% train and 25% test split).

Moreover, I trained another LR classifier to analyze the significance of each criterion. I trained it to predict whether the LVQA model’s answer is correct or not using *Diff* feature set after excluding *used language* d_{Ql} (i.e., D_I , D_R , d_{Qs} , d_{Ql} and d_{Qc}). *Used language* as a feature was dropped due to significantly unbalanced classes in the data. Although image-related difficulty D_I classes are relatively unbalanced too, I kept it in the features set since this is true only in extreme scenarios ($D_I = 1$).

Metrics

I measured the intent classifiers’ performance using binary accuracy, and used the ground-truth labels from the Massive dataset. For VQA models, their correctness was scored by human evaluation (correct 1 or not 0). To measure the performance of LR and MLP, I employed accuracy (Acc) and the $F_{0.5}$ scores to favor precision over recall.

3.3.6 Results

Novel OOD types are challenging for large models

Table 3.4 shows that all the intent classifiers’ performance dropped when facing NS-OOD (i.e., non-English and/or long) compared to ID (i.e., *en-short*), regardless of architecture. Specifically, non-English instances resulted in a significant degradation; thus, it was reasonable to consider *used language* as a major factor. Additionally, the results demonstrate that the

⁴See the previous footnote ³.

⁵Using sklearn [140] implementation.

Table 3.4: Intent classifiers accuracy (\uparrow) on both test splits (*short* and *long*) for the three languages.

Model	<i>en</i> (English)		<i>eo</i> (Esperanto)		<i>pa</i> (Punjabi)	
	<i>short</i>	<i>long</i>	<i>short</i>	<i>long</i>	<i>short</i>	<i>long</i>
MiniLM	0.846	0.787	0.448	0.319	0.374	0.314
XLM	0.875	0.854	0.506	0.457	0.498	0.459
XLNet	0.837	0.819	0.160	0.159	0.056	0.048

length also influenced the performance (e.g., in the case of *en-long*). However, the effect was not as dominant as with the non-English instances, which aligns with the assumption that *length* can be considered as a minor factor.

For complex multi-modal scenes, I used the input scenario difficulty to reflect the OOD extent. I examined LVQA models performance relationship to D_{score} . Results showed that a higher D_{score} led to more mistakes. Detailed results are presented in Appendix A (Table A.8).

Criteria definition is valid

Table 3.5 shows that although P alone indicates the model’s answer correctness, manual D_{score} seemed to have more information. What’s more, when using *Diff* (with and without P) the model’s performance was improved. This suggested that although D_{score} carried useful information, the overall scoring method (Equation 3.2) did not reflect the instance’s difficulty well. It seemed that the weighting in the formula and/or the importance categorization (major and minor factors) was not sufficient.

Similar conclusions could be drawn for the automatically estimated difficulty score (in Table 3.5). However, it can be observed that D_{score} failed to represent the difficulty (even compared to P). Table 3.7 supports the significance of the proposed criteria in the form of LR’s coefficients. Detailed results are presented in Appendix A (Tables A.9 - A.12).

Estimating the input scenario difficulty automatically has several practical advantages: (1) requiring less human resources, (2) offering more objectivity, and (3) providing a continuous scoring scale (in most cases). However, I found that the automatic approach sometimes failed to articulate apparent features of the input.

Moreover, selecting a method for automatic evaluation is critical. For example, in Table 3.6 it could be seen that while using the relative image compression complexity (detailed in Section 3.3.5) to represent the image-related difficulty D_I was simple and could differentiate between a *full noise* image and *usual* scenes, it failed to capture more subtle nuances.

Table 3.5: Accuracy (Acc) \uparrow and $F_{0.5}$ (\uparrow) scores for both classifiers: LR and MLP, using different sets of features, across LVQA models. The best results are in bold.

Method	Features	classifier			
		LR		MLP	
		Acc	$F_{0.5}$	Acc	$F_{0.5}$
manual	P	0.625	0.625	0.625	0.626
	D_{score}	0.683	0.683	0.682	0.682
	$Diff$	0.701	0.700	0.737	0.741
	P and D_{score}	0.692	0.693	0.707	0.717
	P and $Diff$	0.720	0.721	0.767	0.773
automatic	P	0.627	0.627	0.627	0.627
	D_{score}	0.555	0.558	0.544	0.551
	$Diff$	0.635	0.635	0.668	0.664
	P and D_{score}	0.625	0.625	0.625	0.626
	P and $Diff$	0.655	0.657	0.669	0.670

Table 3.6: Relative compression complexity and CLIP similarity for (a) *full noise*, (2) *usual*, and (3) *unknown* examples. The similarity was evaluated with: “*what is the brown object?*”.

Compression complexity	1.000	0.573	0.585
CLIP	0.247	0.214	0.197

Similar limitations were present when using CLIP to reflect the relatedness. Further analysis (Table A.10 in Appendix A) supported the conclusions about D_I and D_R automatic estimation.

The results highlighted: (1) the importance of selecting the appropriate automatic methods, (2) the influence of the aggregation approach, and (3) the benefit of the (individual or overall) difficulty criteria in cases where resources/human expertise are unavailable.

Table 3.7: The LR coefficients’ weights representing each criterion importance, using the manual and automatic difficulty score estimation, across all LVQA models.

	d_{Q_s}	d_{Q_I}	d_{Q_e}	D_R	D_I	intercept
manual	0.324	-1.795	-0.776	-2.079	-0.290	1.897
automatic	0.639	-3.162	1.579	-1.668	-1.113	2.246

3.4 Re-assessing classifier’s confidence score

Relying on the classifier’s output layer (softmax) to reflect the prediction’s confidence is problematic. Hence, I developed ReaL [C6], a method designed to enhance the credibility for black-box LM-based intent classifiers. ReaL recalculates the original confidence score using a temperature-adjusted softmax formulation. The experiments demonstrated that ReaL more effectively distinguishes the confidence scores of correctly and incorrectly classified instances, improving the trust in model predictions.

3.4.1 Problem statement

Similar to an image classifier (as detailed in Section 2.3.1), when an intent classifier M encounters a text instance x at inference, it computes the softmax (Equation 2.1) over K logits in the final-layer and assigns the class/intent with the highest score as the predicted label (Equation 2.2). Usually, this value is considered as the answer’s confidence. Many approaches debated this assumption and looked for alternatives. However, I considered softmax score (Equation 2.1) as confidence indicator but after re-assessment [172].

3.4.2 ReaL

To increase the trust in the softmax score, I proposed ReaL. Although I agree that the logits in their raw form do not reflect the model’s correctness [166], I assumed that they still hold useful information. ReaL distills the logits by increasing the temperature T in softmax (Equation 2.1). I argued that given a pre-trained intent classifier M and a sufficiently large dataset \mathbb{D}_{ID} (of size N), a proper temperature parameter \hat{T} can be estimated by Equation 3.3. Where $\hat{T}^{(n)}$ (defined in Equation 3.4) is the n^{th} instance estimated temperature, $v_{\text{max}}^{(n)}$ and $v_{\text{min}}^{(n)}$ are the maximum and minimum values in the logit vector, and ε is a user-specified parameter. The complete derivation is detailed in Appendix A (Proof.1 in Section A.2.2).

$$\hat{T} = \min_{\forall n \in N} \left(\hat{T}^{(n)} \right) \quad (3.3)$$

$$\hat{T}^{(n)} = \frac{v_{\text{max}}^{(n)} - v_{\text{min}}^{(n)}}{\ln 1 + \varepsilon} \quad (3.4)$$

3.4.3 Experimental setup

To confirm that the logits in their raw form do not reflect the correctness, I compared the range of the logits for correct and incorrect predictions. Moreover, to validate ReaL, I showed the effect of the \hat{T} across several models.

Data:

I used the NS-OOD dataset that was introduced in Section 3.3.3. Additionally, I constructed *full* test sets which combine both *short* and *long* sets to examine the raw logits usability.

Models:

I used MiniLM, XLM and XLNet intent classifiers detailed in Section 3.3.5 and Table 3.3.

Parameters:

The hyperparameter ε (in Equation 3.4) was fixed to 10. Noting that, this parameter is user-defined and influenced by the scenario characteristic (e.g., the choice of the dataset).

Metrics:

When testing the raw logits for the correct and incorrect predictions, I used the ground-truth labels from Massive [52]. For the maximum and minimum logits values, I calculated the average μ and the standard deviation σ over all the test instances. I used box-plots to illustrate the difference between $T = 1$ and $T = \hat{T}$, highlighting the mean, median, quartiles, and outliers.

3.4.4 Results

Raw logits do not reflect the model’s correctness

The results in Table 3.8 support that the logits’ raw form does not reflect the model’s correctness. Regardless of the model, correctly and incorrectly classified answers’ logits overlapped; hence, the correctness of an answer cannot be directly inferred. Further results for the Esperanto and Punjabi test sets are detailed in Appendix A (Table A.13 in Section A.2.3).

Table 3.8: The correct and incorrect predictions’ maximum and minimum logits values. The values are in the form $(\mu_{\max} \pm \sigma_{\max}, \mu_{\min} \pm \sigma_{\min})$.

en-full (English)

	correct (1)	incorrect (0)
MiniLM	$(9.51 \pm 1.08, -5.58 \pm 0.88)$	$(7.88 \pm 1.45, -5.58 \pm 0.86)$
XLM	$(12.55 \pm 1.08, -3.19 \pm 0.51)$	$(10.13 \pm 2.22, -3.42 \pm 0.58)$
XLNet	$(10.65 \pm 0.90, -2.72 \pm 0.37)$	$(9.10 \pm 1.67, -2.83 \pm 0.38)$

Re-assessment leads to clearer predictions

Figure 3.4 shows that re-assessment helped in making a clearer separation between the correct and incorrect answers’ scores. With such distinguishing, a simple approach to increase the model’s accuracy, like thresholding, becomes more feasible. Similar observations can be seen in the case of the Esperanto and Punjabi datasets (Figures A.5 and A.6).

Figure 3.4: The used models’ predictions confidence score average with $T = 1$ and $T = \hat{T}$.

3.5 Re-evaluating LVQA model’s confidence score

Based on the assumption in Section 3.4, I argued that the same is applicable for large visual question answering (LVQA) models. The raw predicted probability does not reflect the confidence, and it should be recalculated with respect to the overall input scenario difficulty D_{score} (detailed in Section 3.3.4). Aiming to enhance the robustness of LVQA models and increase the trust in their confidence score, I proposed ReDiT [J2]. I showed that ReDiT reduces the scatter around the median and achieves better distinction between correct and incorrect confidence scores.

3.5.1 Problem statement

When a VQA model M receives an instance x (text-image pair), it generates an answer $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ (i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = [\hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \dots, \hat{y}_W]$). To predict the w^{th} token, M applies the softmax (Equation 2.1) on the w^{th} logits vector V_w and selects the one with the highest score (Equation 2.2); where $V_w = [v_{w1}, v_{w2}, \dots, v_{wk}, \dots, v_{wK}]$, and K is the model’s vocabulary size. This score ($P^{(w)}$) is usually considered as the confidence of the model to generate the w^{th} token. Accordingly, the answer’s prediction confidence is obtained by applying Equation 3.5.

$$P(\hat{\mathbf{y}}|x) = \prod_{w=1}^W P^{(w)} \quad (3.5)$$

3.5.2 ReDiT

Building on the findings from Section 3.3, I assumed that a challenging scenario would decrease the trust in the model’s confidence P . To capture this uncertainty, I used T in Equation 2.1. ReDiT re-evaluates P after mapping D_{score} (detailed in Section 3.3.4) to \hat{T} (Equation 3.6); where $\hat{T} \in [T_{\min}, T_{\max}]$. The re-evaluated confidence is denoted by P_T .

$$\hat{T} = T_{\min} + D_{\text{score}} \cdot (T_{\max} - T_{\min}) \quad (3.6)$$

In Equation 2.1, it can be seen that $T \in (0, \infty)$ influences the softmax result exponentially; as $T \rightarrow 0$, P_i collapses to a point mass; while as $T \rightarrow \infty$, P_i reaches a maximum uncertainty ($1/K$) [66, 107]. However, a suitable \hat{T} should maintain the linearity of Equation 3.6. Thus, I defined the lower bound of \hat{T} (i.e., T_{\min}) to 1; retaining the original confidence when the

scenario is easy. On the other hand, the upper bound T_{\max} is defined by Equation 3.7. The complete derivation is detailed in Appendix A (Proof.2 in Section A.2.2).

$$T_{\max} \approx \frac{v_{\max} - v_{\min}}{\ln K} \quad (3.7)$$

Noting that the vocabulary size K is fixed per model, while the difference between the maximum v_{\max} and minimum v_{\min} values of V_w varies per the predicted token. Thus, T_{\max} and \hat{T} are calculated for each token independently.

3.5.3 Experimental setup

I designed two groups of experiments. In Group 1, I examined the difference between P and P_T for both correct and incorrect answers. In Group 2, I tested the applicability of thresholding using the prediction score (P and P_T) to detect erroneous answers.

Data

I used the 3U-VQA dataset that was introduced in Section 3.3.3.

Models:

I used the same LVQA models detailed in Section 3.3.5 and Table 3.3 (i.e., GIT-Base, GIT-Large, BLIP, and ViLT).

Parameters

All the experiments were performed using both the manually and automatically estimated difficulty score. Also, I defined an additional setting (i.e, semi-automatic), in which the automatic difficulty is used for all the criteria except the *relatedness* D_R .

For Group 1, I defined a *normal* scenario to imitate the expected real-world setup; where the *used language* is known by the model (i.e., $d_{Qu} = 0$), and the image is not *full noise* ($D_I \neq 1$). In Group 2, I analyzed the proposed re-evaluation method in *all* scenario. It relaxes the restrictions of *normal* and represents all the possible conditions, including $d_{Qu} = 1$ and $D_I = 1$. To ensure a fair evaluation, I defined an optimal threshold value for each case separately⁶.

⁶Using Youden’s index [204].

Table 3.9: IQR (\downarrow) and QIR (\downarrow) between P and P_T scores. The best score is in bold, while the second best is underlined.

	P	P_T manual	P_T auto	P_T semi
IQR_0	0.225	0.071	0.040	<u>0.054</u>
IQR_1	0.474	0.302	0.106	<u>0.222</u>
QIR	0.286	0.124	0.247	<u>0.130</u>

Metrics

In Group 1, I calculated the inter-quartile range IQR (Equation A.50) to measure the spread of the data for correct and incorrect predictions separately. Moreover, to examine the distance between them, I calculated the quartile intersection ratio QIR (Equation A.51). To measure the binary classification performance in Group 2, I used accuracy Acc and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve AUC_{ROC} scores w.r.t the corresponding optimal threshold.

3.5.4 Results

Re-evaluation better separates correct and incorrect predictions

In Group 1, P_T was expected to be lower than P after the re-evaluation. The advantage of the re-evaluation (regardless of the used difficulty estimation approach) was twofold: (1) reducing the scatter around the median for correct and incorrect scores separately (indicated by IQR), and (2) achieving better distinction between them (indicated by QIR).

Re-evaluated confidence scores boost robustness

In Group 2, after setting the optimal thresholds, Acc and AUC_{ROC} were measured (Table A.16 in Appendix A, Section A.2.3). The results in Table 3.10 illustrate the applicability of thresholding with the re-evaluated scores to detect incorrect responses. Moreover, it could be seen that the lowest performance was with the fully automatic approach P_T (auto). This supported the findings from Section 3.3.6 regarding the importance of selecting the automatic estimation approach.

Table 3.10: Acc (\uparrow) and AUC_{ROC} (\uparrow) between P and P_T scores. The best score is in bold, while the second best is underlined.

	P	P_T manual	P_T auto	P_T semi
Acc	0.694	<u>0.706</u>	0.678	0.736
AUC_{ROC}	0.671	0.721	0.659	<u>0.710</u>

3.6 Zero-shot generalized category discovery

Unlike classical AI systems, LM-based models can directly perform GCD without further training. The experiments showed that a stand-alone LVQA model can execute the task adequately. To further enhance its performance, two lightweight approaches (i.e., similarity-driven and prompt-driven) were developed [C8]. These methods are suitable for both general and domain-specific data in a zero-shot setting.

3.6.1 Problem statement

In contrast to traditional GCD (detailed in Section 2.5.1), a zero-shot GCD approach does not require model training and assumes no access to a labeled dataset (i.e., $\mathbb{D}_k = \phi$). It only requires knowledge of the set of known classes Y_k (i.e., $Y_k \neq \phi$). In case of images, an LVQA model M can perform GCD operating as a post-hoc classifier. The objective of M is to assign categories to the instances in the unlabeled dataset \mathbb{D}_u (i.e., $\mathbb{D}_u = X_u$). The complete set of labels \check{Y} consists of the known Y_k and the discovered \check{Y}_u labels sets (i.e., $\check{Y} = Y_k \cup \check{Y}_u$). Assuming K known categories and U novel categories, ideally, \check{Y} should contain $K + U$ classes. In practice, M might find more classes. In such cases, it should at least discover all the unknown categories (i.e., $Y_u \in \check{Y}_u$) [9].

3.6.2 Zero-GCCD

Stand-alone GCD

The trivial way to perform the GCD task using an LVQA model is by prompting it with a fixed question and image x_n (Figure 3.5a). As a result, the model’s prediction \hat{y}_n is the class that is assigned to x_n (Algorithm A.3 in Appendix A). However, this approach struggles when dealing with domain-specific labels and is prone to assigning synonyms for the same class.

Figure 3.5: The pipeline of (a) the stand-alone, (b) the similarity-driven, and (c) the prompt-driven approaches.

Similarity-driven GCCD

The similarity-driven method (Figure 3.5b and Algorithm A.4 in Appendix A) overcomes the stand-alone limitations by including the previous knowledge in its decision, thus, it belongs to generalized continual category discovery (GCCD). Formally, \check{Y}_{n-1} is defined as the union of the set of known classes Y_k and the set of discovered classes \check{Y}_u obtained from the previous instances $X_{1:n-1}$ (i.e., $X_{1:n-1} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n-1}\}$). For an instance x_n from \mathbb{D}_u , M is queried using a fixed prompt to assign a category. To determine whether it is a new category or part of \check{Y}_{n-1} , the relevance to the classes in \check{Y}_{n-1} is checked. To do so, the similarity is measured between the embeddings of the given category and each class in \check{Y}_{n-1} . If the score is above a certain threshold β , that class is assigned to x_n , otherwise, it is considered as a novel category and added to \check{Y}_u . This approach has a main limitation: the similarity measure reliability.

Prompt-driven GCCD

Like the similarity-driven method, prompt-driven (Algorithm A.5 in Appendix A) belongs to GCCD by using a dynamic prompt that includes the previous knowledge (Figure 3.5c). This approach relies entirely on M without any additional components, such as embedding and the similarity evaluation present in the similarity-driven approach. Formally, given an instance x_n , the prompt-driven approach uses a question that contains all the available classes \check{Y}_{n-1} . Then, M is queried to either select one of them or assign a new category, hence, it is appended to \check{Y}_u and considered for the next instance.

Human refinement

It is common to encounter instances that can be assigned multiple classes (e.g., a car instance could be classified as “car”, “SUV”, or more generally as “vehicle”). In such cases, M might

generate predictions that include hyponym, hypernym, or synonym classes. These labels can be refined by a human, which can significantly improve performance.

3.6.3 Experimental setup

I examined the ability of a stand-alone LVQA to perform GCD and used it as a benchmark. Moreover, I assessed the methods’ performance with and without prediction refinement.

Data

For variety, I used low-resolution general purpose (i.e., Cifar-10 [89]) and high-resolution domain-specific (i.e., iNat [182]) datasets. For both datasets, I treated (approximately) half of the available classes as known classes (Y_k) and the other half as unknown classes (Y_u). The dataset details are in Table 3.11.

Table 3.11: Datasets details: image resolution, number of instances (N), number of known classes (K), number of unknown categories (U), and total number of classes (i.e., $K + U$).

	resolution	N	K	U	no. of classes
Cifar-10	32×32	3,000	5	5	10
iNat	299×299	2,992	8	9	17

Models

I used Google’s Gemini [4] API⁷ as an LVQA model, and embedding was performed by the pre-trained BERT [41] model.

Parameters

I fixed the threshold (β) to 0.8 for the similarity-driven approach. The used prompts vary slightly depending on the dataset. For example, additional hints were included for the iNat experiments, such as: “*biological class*” and “*the Latin term*”. The used prompts are detailed in Table A.18 (Appendix A, Section A.2.3).

⁷Gemini-1.5-flash.

Metrics

To assess the performance, I used the balanced overall accuracy Acc , known class accuracy Acc_k , and unknown class accuracy Acc_u . I also calculated the accuracy scores after human refinement.

3.6.4 Results

The results in Table 3.12 show that the stand-alone LVQA model performance was sufficient. Moreover, the results highlight the advantage of the continual learning (CL) approach over the stand-alone approach. This enhancement came with minimal cost. Additionally, the Table 3.12 shows that the prompt-driven solution outperformed the other approaches across both datasets. Furthermore, in the case of iNat, the prompt-driven method outperformed the stand-alone benchmark even without human refinement.

Moreover, both CL methods (i.e., similarity- and prompt-driven) showed superior performance in the case of iNat data; however, in the case of Cifar-10, the stand-alone solution generally outperformed the similarity-driven method. This was attributed to two factors: (1) including hints in the prompt for domain-specific data was more straightforward, and (2) higher-resolution instances held more information.

Table 3.12: The overall (Acc), known (Acc_k) and unknown (Acc_u) accuracy (\uparrow). The first group of columns is for the automatic scores, and the second is for the refined scores.

Method		automatic			refined		
		Acc	Acc_k	Acc_u	Acc	Acc_k	Acc_u
Cifar-10	stand-alone	0.524	0.473	0.576	0.806	0.797	0.810
	similarity-driven	0.593	0.639	0.548	0.760	0.775	0.745
	prompt-driven	0.709	0.778	0.640	0.832	0.854	0.810
iNat	stand-alone	0.675	0.730	0.626	0.837	0.919	0.764
	similarity-driven	0.730	0.823	0.647	0.860	0.957	0.776
	prompt-driven	0.876	0.965	0.797	0.891	0.965	0.826

3.7 Conclusion

This chapter focused on improving the robustness of LM-based systems when dealing with unusual and unknown scenarios. Three tasks were addressed: intent classification, visual question answering, and generalized category discovery.

Initially, I challenged the conventional definition of OOD and expanded it to accommodate the capabilities of large models. Considering their wide exposure to data, characterizing OOD based on the training (ID) data is impractical. Instead, I defined three types of difficulty that suit even multi-modal tasks: image-related, text-related, and their relatedness. For instance, for intent classification, the difficulty is only sourced from text. However, for VQA, two modalities (i.e., image and text) separately and their relatedness contribute to the scenario complexity. I elaborated these types further into sets of criteria, representing non-semantic OOD scenarios for LMs. Based on the criteria, I created D_{score} to assess the input scenario difficulty. I developed a method for generating benchmark datasets to simulate challenging, out-of-distribution (OOD) scenarios for LM-based models. I’ve also released two open-source, customizable datasets: NS-OOD for intent classification and 3U-VQA for VQA.

Furthermore, I proposed two methods (i.e., ReaL and ReDiT) to increase the trust in the prediction confidence scores by re-scaling them. Both approaches use the temperature parameter T in the softmax function. ReaL estimates T across a large dataset globally with a user-provided hyper-parameter ϵ . In contrast, ReDiT obtains the value locally (for every instance), relying on the prediction logits without additional parameter tuning. The experiments showed that both approaches achieved better separation between correct and incorrect predictions. This distinction enhanced the model’s (i.e., intent classifier and LVQA) robustness when encountering challenging or OOD instances.

Lastly, I demonstrated that a stand-alone LM-based visual question answering (LVQA) model could perform GCD in a zero-shot setting. Additionally, I introduced two lightweight yet effective methods (i.e., similarity- and prompt-driven) to enhance its performance through continual learning (CL). The results showed that the prompt-driven method (even without human refinement) consistently outperformed both the similarity-driven approach and the benchmark, particularly with domain-specific data.

Thesis III: Interpretability and explainability in AI systems

The more critical the applications that use AI, the more the need for interpretability and explainability. The black-box nature of many AI models hinders their deployment in real-world use cases. These aspects are also essential for model design, failure identification, and trust. This chapters explore the inner inner-workings of existing story visualization (SV) models, which led to the development of Mod-StoryGAN. It also presents a thorough analysis on the interpretability of the recently introduced Kolmogorov–Arnold networks (KANs) [113], questioning their applicability to higher-dimensional data like images and text. Finally, the chapter introduces post-hoc, black-box explainability methods for image captioning (IC) and visual question answering (VQA), along with quantitative metrics.

4.1 Introduction

Both classical neural networks (NNs) and large models (LMs), produce seemingly intelligent output without real understanding of the underlying concepts. This phenomenon is also known as the Clever Hans effect, and it highlights the importance of interpretability and explainability [131]. Explainable AI (XAI) offers several benefits: (1) improves model design, (2) eases development, and (3) justifies predictions. This chapter addresses these topics across several single- and multi-modal tasks: story visualization (SV), image and text classification, image captioning (IC), and visual question answering (VQA).

Section 4.3 details Mod-StoryGAN, a modular SV model designed based on previous state-of-the-art methods [103, 168, 123] using interpretability. It also introduces two evaluation

concepts: theme and background awareness. Experiments showed that Mod-StoryGAN outperformed prior models both qualitatively (theme and background consistency, and overall visualization quality) and quantitatively (F_1 , BLEU1/2, and FID scores).

Section 4.4 investigates the interpretability claims of Kolmogorov-Arnold networks (KANs) [113]. It presents the theoretical foundation of KAN - namely, KAT (Kolmogorov Arnold representation theorem [87, 25] - and shows KAN’s violations of a key constraint of the theorem: number of layers and nodes. Experiments demonstrated that a classical neural network (i.e., MLP) outperformed KAN with even fewer parameters when using high-dimensional data, challenging KAN’s enhanced interpretability claim.

Section 4.5 introduces two evaluation metrics (i.e., XIC and $iXIC$) to assess the performance of XAI methods, aiming for objective evaluation. Experiments showed alignment with human evaluation. Section 4.6 addresses post-hoc, black-box explainability for image captioning (IC) models. Two local and model-agnostic XAI methods (i.e., PIC-XAI and iPIC-XAI) were presented. Both manual and automatic evaluations showed that PIC-XAI produced reasonable explanations, with iPIC-XAI offering further improvements.

Section 4.7 extends XAI to multi-modal LMs (i.e., LVQA), by introducing PEX-VQA, a post-hoc, local method. It produces three types of explanations: visual, textual, and combined. Additionally, SHAP [119], a widely used algorithm, was adapted to suit VQA (i.e., SHAP-VQA). Overall, PEX-VQA generated better explanations compared to the benchmark (i.e., SHAP-VQA). Lastly, to evaluate XAI output validity more effectively, the hallucination score [95] was revised (i.e., H) and used. After modification, H showed stronger alignment with human judgment.

My contributions can be summarized as follows:

- I proposed a modular story visualization model (Mod-StoryGAN) by analyzing and combining components from existing approaches.
- I evaluated and challenged the interpretability claims of KANs for high-dimensional data, both theoretically and empirically.
- I developed automatic evaluation metrics (XIC and $iXIC$) for assessing XAI methods in image captioning.
- I introduced two post-hoc, model-agnostic, local XAI methods for image captioning (PIC-XAI and iPIC-XAI) applicable to black-box models.

- I proposed an improved hallucination score for automatic XAI evaluation and introduced a post-hoc, model-agnostic, local XAI method (PEX-VQA) for black-box LVQA models.

4.2 Related work

Interpretability and explainability are considered vital for ensuring compliance with emerging AI regulations such as the EU AI Act [2]. However, these terms are often used interchangeably, and there is a lack of consensus on their precise definitions [218]. Interpretability generally refers to the ability of a human to understand the model’s internal workings [49, 151], showing *how* a model makes decisions. In practice, the complexity of a neural network (e.g., measured by the number of layers, neurons, or trainable parameters) can serve as a proxy for interpretability, since it directly influences the ability to trace relationships between inputs, intermediate representations, and outputs. In contrast, explainability typically concerns the *why* behind a specific model decision, without necessarily requiring insight into the internal mechanics.

Explainable AI (XAI) solutions that were proposed to address these challenges [11] can be mapped to the taxonomy shown in Figure 4.1. Interpretable-by-design methods are models that are inherently interpretable (either entirely or partially), such as decision trees [188], linear and logistic regression [175, 54]. However, recent AI systems rely predominantly on complex and obscure architectures like deep neural networks. For such models, post-hoc methods are designed to capture relevant correlations or causal patterns. Some analyze the features learned by a specific model [20], while others are model-agnostic. The latter can be further categorized into global and local methods. As their names suggest, global methods aim to characterize the behavior of a model over an entire data set [14, 96], whereas local methods focus on establishing a direct link between the input and output for an individual prediction [119, 149].

Story visualization (SV) is a task that intersects computer vision (CV) and natural language processing (NLP). It involves generating a sequence of images from a series of sentences that compose a story. Unlike text-to-image (T2I) [148], and text-to-video, (T2V) [80, 104, 125, 206], SV maintains the local consistency of each scene while considering the global consistency across the story. The SV task was first formally introduced by the authors of StoryGAN [103]. Later works (i.e., CP-CSV [168] and DuCo [123]) enhanced their design to preserve character integrity and reinforce semantic alignment between the story and the generated images.

Figure 4.1: Taxonomy of interpretability and/or explainability approaches [131].

Universal approximation theorems (UATs) [77, 141] and **Kolmogorov–Arnold representation theorem (KAT)** [87, 25] aim to demonstrate that complex multivariate functions can be represented or approximated by simpler compositions of functions [15]. UAT has dominated the machine learning (ML) field over KAT due to its theoretical approximation guarantee and implementation simplicity. Given sufficient neurons in the hidden layer (arbitrary width and/or depth) [78], a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) can estimate any continuous function to any desired degree of accuracy [38] (Formula 4.1).

$$MLP(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{b=1}^{\infty} \omega_b^{(2)} \sigma \left(\sum_{a=1}^r \omega_{b,a}^{(1)} x_a \right) \quad (4.1)$$

KAT states that any multivariate continuous function on a bounded domain can be expressed as a finite composition of continuous univariate functions and addition (Equation 4.2), where: (1) the input \mathbf{x} is of size r (i.e., $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, \dots, x_r]$), (2) $\{\phi_{b,a} : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}$ are the inner univariate functions, and (3) $\{\Phi_b : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}$ are the outer univariate functions. The relevance of KAT has been discussed very early [60, 91, 71], and several recent works still argued its applicability [116, 158, 164, 92].

$$KAT(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{b=1}^{2r+1} \Phi_b \left(\sum_{a=1}^r \phi_{b,a}(x_a) \right) \quad (4.2)$$

In contrast to UAT (Equation 4.1), KAT (Equations 4.2) requires $2r+1$ nodes/units at most in the hidden layer to approximate any function. Relying on this theoretical constraint, the authors of [113] recently proposed Kolmogorov-Arnold networks (KANs) as an interpretable alternative to MLPs.

Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) [119] is a model-agnostic XAI method that provides local explanations for ML systems. It quantifies the contribution of each input feature

to a model’s prediction by computing Shapley values, a concept derived from cooperative game theory. SHAP is effective in tasks such as question answering (QA) [117] and image captioning (IC) [118], however, it lacks a built-in mechanism for handling multi-modal tasks like VQA, where reasoning over both textual and visual inputs is required. Additionally, SHAP is computationally expensive¹ and has limitations when applied for IC [118], such as image segmentation over a fixed-axis, and reliance on auxiliary language models.

4.3 Improving story visualization by interpretability

Story visualization involves generating visual representations while preserving *local* consistency within each frame and *global* consistency across the entire story. To enhance these aspects, I conducted an interpretability-driven analysis of existing architectures (i.e., StoryGAN [103], CP-CSV [168], and DuCo [123]), and integrated the most effective components into Mod-StoryGAN [C1]. Both qualitative and quantitative evaluations demonstrated that Mod-StoryGAN achieved superior *background* and *theme* awareness, along with improved visual quality, in comparison to CP-CSV and DuCo.

4.3.1 Problem statement

During training, a SV model M learns to map textual features of each instance/story \mathbf{x} (i.e., $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_S]$) in dataset \mathbb{D} to the corresponding ground-truth visual representations \mathbf{y} (i.e., $\mathbf{y} = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_S]$), where S is the length of the story. The objective of M is twofold: (1) to generate an image \hat{y}_s that is similar to y_s and accurately reflects the content of x_s (i.e., local consistency), and (2) to maintain semantic and visual coherence across the entire sequence \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} (i.e., global consistency).

4.3.2 Mod-StoryGAN

Design

To design an architecture that preserves both local and global consistency, I conducted a detailed analysis of the original StoryGAN architecture and the enhancement components introduced in CP-CSV and DuCo.

¹By default, SHAP sets the number of evaluations to 300-500 to get explanations with meaningful granularity of super pixels. Higher number results in more detailed maps; however, it causes longer run-time.

Figure 4.2: Components from storygan are in blue, the adopted parts from CP-CSV and DuCu are highlighted in red and green, respectively.

From StoryGAN, I adopted the recurrent neural network (RNN) backbone that incorporates previously generated images when visualizing the current sentence, ensuring temporal coherence. From CP-CSV, I integrated figure-ground segmentation \tilde{y}_s , which enriches the generator’s input with scene-structure information, allowing better distinction between foreground elements and background context across frames. From DuCo, I incorporated the dual learning framework to strengthen the alignment between the input story and its visualization, as well as the copy-transform module, which enhances attention over previous frames and reinforces background continuity. Finally, I adopted the MART module to model complex temporal interactions by maintaining a memory of previous visual states, enabling more coherent transitions and context retention across the entire story sequence. By combining these key components, I developed a new architecture, Mod-StoryGAN, which integrates the strengths of all three prior models [C1].

Training

The objective function of the proposed design (Equation 4.3) consists of the losses of the fused components, and involves parameters for the generator (θ_G), image discriminator ($\theta_{\hat{y}}$), figure-ground discriminator ($\theta_{\tilde{y}}$), and story discriminator (θ_x). The dual learning component was pre-trained and kept frozen during training. The formulation of all the terms in the objective function is detailed in Appendix A (Section A.3.2).

$$\min_{\theta_G} \max_{\theta_Y, \theta_X} (\mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{img}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{fg}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{story}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{dual}}) \quad (4.3)$$

Background and theme awareness

Background awareness represents the ability of M to reflect the dynamicity of the surroundings through the frames. For instance, the movement between indoor and outdoor scenes or the change from dark to bright environments. On the other hand, for short stories (e.g., five sentences/frames), the theme throughout the story is not changing frequently, and the events happen in a relatively static surrounding. For example, the whole story takes place in a ‘spooky’, ‘dreamy’, or ‘bright’ environment. This concept is denoted as *theme awareness*. These two aspects that can contradict to some extent, making their joint optimization a key challenge in story visualization.

4.3.3 Experimental setup

Data

I used the PororoSV dataset introduced in StoryGAN [103], a tailored version of the Pororo dataset [84] for SV. It includes 15336 story-description pairs (13000 for training and 2336 for testing), where each story consists of five consecutive frames. For segmentation ground-truth, I used the segmented version provided in [123].

PororoSV includes nine main characters, but their appearance frequencies are imbalanced, introducing potential training bias. For example, features of the frequently appearing character ‘Pororo’ are more likely to be learned than those of less frequent ones like ‘Harry’. A similar bias exists in themes: while ‘outdoor snowy’ and ‘indoor’ are common themes, others are underrepresented. Figures A.7 and A.8 (in Appendix A) show the relative frequencies of characters and themes.

Models

To assess my proposal (i.e., Mod-StoryGAN), I used CP-CSV and DuCo models as benchmarks on the test split.

Parameters

All models were trained from scratch using the training split, with default settings for CP-CSV and DuCo. The dual learning component was pre-trained and kept frozen during training.

Metrics

Evaluation included both human and objective metrics. Human evaluators rated *background* and *theme* awareness, as well as overall visual quality, on a scale of 1 to 5. I also used weighted F_1 , BLEU1/2, and FID for quantitative assessment.

4.3.4 Results

The qualitative assessment showed that Mod-StoryGAN was more aware of the *background* than the benchmarks (CP-CSV and DuCo). With CP-CSV, transitions between frames appeared noisy. For example, in the story shown in Figure 4.3a, CP-CSV generated scenes that were partially aligned with the text and ground-truth, but the second frame contained a confusing scene without clear characters or objects. DuCo, in contrast, maintained the background from the first frame but failed to reflect the dynamic change in the story. Mod-StoryGAN handled this better by detecting the scene change with less confusion, generating visuals that were more consistent with the story content and ground-truth.

Figure 4.3b illustrates Mod-StoryGAN’s advantage in preserving *theme* throughout the story. It correctly identified the scene as an outdoor ‘forest’ setting and was not misled by cues such as ‘run’ in the second sentence, usually associated with the ‘snowy’ theme in PororoSV, or ‘shadow’ in the third sentence, which typically suggests a ‘dark’ theme. In contrast, CP-CSV and DuCo struggled to maintain theme consistency. CP-CSV showed noisy and inconsistent outputs, and DuCo failed to detect the correct theme. Mod-StoryGAN demonstrated better *theme awareness*, producing more coherent and visually aligned stories in such cases.

Table 4.1 presents the manual ranking results. Mod-StoryGAN was preferred over both benchmarks across all aspects: *background* awareness, *theme* awareness, and overall visualization quality. Table 4.2 supports this finding through objective metrics. The weighted F_1 score reflected better character representation and clearer feature distinctions. Mod-StoryGAN also outperformed CP-CSV and DuCo in FID score by 17% and 5%, respectively. Although DuCo achieved the highest BLEU score, Mod-StoryGAN still surpassed CP-CSV.

(a) Pororo has confidence with the truth of his words. Pororo starts telling his story about skiing to his friends. Pororo is scared in the sky without any safety equipment. Only Pororo has one ski board. Pororo is struggling to rise up by spinning ski board in his hand.

(b) Yellow butterfly and Crog is hiding behind the rock, Pororo approaches. Pororo runs toward grass to find someone. Pororo is still looking for other, Pororo notices shadow behind mushroom. Pororo attacks someone behind mushroom. Pororo got something but Pororo is surprised.

Figure 4.3: Examples highlighting Mod-StoryGAN’s ability to maintain (a) *background* and (b) *theme* awareness. The rows (from top to bottom) represent the ground-truth and the outputs of CP-CSV, DuCo, and Mod-StoryGAN.

Table 4.1: Qualitative comparison (\uparrow) in terms of visualization quality and the *background* (BG) & *theme* awareness. The best results are in bold.

Model	Visualization	BG awareness	Theme awareness
CP-CSV	1.2	1.6	2.8
DuCo	2.1	2.5	3.1
Mod-StoryGAN	2.9	3.7	4.2

Table 4.2: Quantitative comparison using weighted F_1 \uparrow , BLEU1/2 \uparrow , and FID \downarrow score. The best results are in bold.

Model	F_1	BLEU1/2	FID
CP-CSV	0.173	0.127/0.037	119.4
DuCo	0.191	0.137/0.042	104.7
Mod-StoryGAN	0.212	0.131/0.040	99.0

4.4 Challenging KAN’s interpretability

Kolmogorov-Arnold Network (KAN) [113], inspired by KAT [87, 25], was proposed as a more interpretable and efficient alternative to MLPs, which are justified by UAT [77, 141]. This claim was supported by both theoretical and practical evidence. To examine this, I initially defined interpretability in the context of KANs. Then, I analyzed the fundamental differences between KAT and UAT, showing that KAN violates a key constraint of the KAT representation theorem. Finally, I reviewed the proposed interpretability tools and evaluated their effectiveness in high-dimensional domains such as image and text data [C7].

4.4.1 Problem statement

Formally, a KAN consists of L layers, where each layer is characterized by: (1) input size r_a , (2) output size r_b , and (3) a set of trainable univariate functions $\phi_{b,a}$. The layer shape is denoted as $[r_a, r_b, \text{degree of } \phi_{b,a}]$. Based on Equation 4.2, the KAT structure can be viewed as a two-layer KAN ($L = 2$), with layers of shape $[r, 2r + 1, 1]$ and $[2r + 1, 1, 1]$, respectively.

The authors of KAN argued that a two-layer architecture is insufficient to approximate complex functions effectively. Therefore, they extended the structure to allow arbitrary depths and widths, leading to a general KAN defined by the composition in Equation 4.4.

$$KAN(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i_{L-1}=1}^{r_{L-1}} \phi_{L-1, i_L, i_{L-1}} \left(\sum_{i_{L-2}=1}^{r_{L-2}} \cdots \left(\sum_{i_0=1}^{r_0} \phi_{0, i_1, i_0}(x_{i_0}) \right) \cdots \right) \quad (4.4)$$

While interpretability was presented as a main advantage of KAN, there are three debatable aspects of this claim: (1) the lack of explicit definition for interpretability, (2) the effect of relaxing KAT’s size constraint, and (3) the applicability of KAN to high-dimensional data.

4.4.2 Discussing KAN’s interpretability claim

Interpretability definition

The authors of KAN used visualization to compare the networks in terms of interpretability. Also, they suggested that pruned (smaller) networks are more convenient and they enhance the interpretability since the information is compressed into a smaller space. Thus, I concluded that considering the size of the network as an objective reference when investigating KAN’s interpretability claim is appropriate.

The effect of relaxing KAT’s size constraint

Relying on KAT, the authors of KAN promised to enhance the interpretability over MLP by ensuring a fewer number of parameters (a smaller network). However, they admitted that a network of two layers represented by Equation 4.2 is incapable of capturing the complexity of any function with smooth splines. Thus, they characterized KAN with a generalized form of KAT (Equation 4.4). While having a wider and deeper network seems reasonable, it caused KAT to lose its size advantage [42]. Hence, I concluded that KAN failed to hold the promise of bounded network size, thus, not being more interpretable than MLP, since it failed to hold the promise of bounded network size.

Applicability to high-dimensional data

The widest network example that was shown in KAN’s paper has an input size of $r = 17$. However, when dealing with higher-dimensional data (e.g., text or image), a *wider* KAN (at least in the input layer) should be used. Additionally, to achieve a smoother representation for complex data, it is natural to use a *deeper* KAN. However, this increases the number of nodes, resulting in decreased interpretability.

To maintain the claimed interpretability for large KANs, the authors provided sparsification and pruning techniques to reduce the network size. However, the original KAN implementation suffers from a performance issue when used in solving tasks with high-dimensional data (e.g., image and text). To overcome this, two main approaches were proposed: (1) LANs² (learnable activation networks [113]) and (2) EfficientKAN (a reformulated version of KAN [24]). LANs are not more than MLPs, but with learnable activation functions parameterized as splines. EfficientKAN³ uses the original L1 regularization instead

²Presented in KAN’s paper (Appendix B).

³Mentioned in KAN’s repo: github.com/KindXiaoming/pykan

of KAN’s proposed one, thus, giving up KAN’s sparsification and pruning techniques, which were claimed to be critical to KAN’s interpretability.

4.4.3 Experimental setup

I conducted experiments using high-dimensional data with different variants of KAN and compared their size and performance against classical MLPs.

Data

Two datasets were used: (1) Mnist [40], an image dataset with $K = 10$ classes, and (2) AG_news [214], a text dataset with $K = 4$ classes. For Mnist, the 28×28 images were flattened to vectors of size $r = 784$ without further pre-processing. For AG_news, features were extracted into vectors of size $r = 3072$.

Models

I tested two KAN implementations: (1) ChebyKAN [171], a LAN variant with learnable activation functions that are parametrized as Chebyshev polynomials [29], and (2) EfficientKAN [24]. These were compared to a fully connected (FC) network. Text features were extracted using BERT [41].

Parameters

Three experiment groups were created: (1) wide, (2) deep, and (3) simple. The wide group used one hidden layer of size $2r$ ($[r, 2r, K]$). The deep group used two hidden layers, each of size $r/2$ ($[r, r/2, r/2, K]$). The simple group excluded hidden layers, using $[r, K]$. The wide and deep FC models correspond to MLPs, while the simple FC is a linear classifier. For fair comparison, the polynomial degree in KAN models was fixed to one to match the linearity of FC layers.

Metrics

Model performance was evaluated by accuracy. Model size (measured by the number of trainable parameters) was used as a proxy for interpretability; with smaller models considered more interpretable.

4.4.4 Results

KAN is less interpretable

The results in Table 4.3 show that KANs (i.e., ChebyKAN and EfficientKAN) were significantly larger than the MLPs across all datasets and experiment groups (i.e., wide, deep, or simple). This was expected since KAN has trainable activation functions which contain an additional number of parameters compared to an MLP. However, this overhead was not as minor as described in KAN’s paper. For instance, EfficientKAN was approximately 8 times larger than the MLP model (FC) in all the scenarios. Consequently, considering that the size is an indication of its interpretability, the results suggest that KAN models were much less interpretable than MLP when dealing with high-dimensional data.

Table 4.3: Size (number of trainable parameters ↓). The best results are in bold.

Model	Mnist			AG_news		
	wide	deep	simple	wide	deep	simple
EfficientKAN	9,959,936	3,719,296	62,720	151,191,552	56,672,256	98,304
ChebyKAN	2,489,984	929,824	15,680	37,797,888	14,168,064	24,576
FC	1,246,570	465,706	7,850	18,905,092	7,087,108	12,292

KAN is more expensive

Furthermore, the results in Table 4.4 show that the size overhead for KAN models did not benefit the performance; KANs required more computational resources to achieve comparable performance to MLPs, while offering less interpretability.

Table 4.4: Test accuracy (↑). The best results are in bold.

Model	Mnist			AG_news		
	wide	deep	simple	wide	deep	simple
EfficientKAN	0.985	0.982	0.931	0.906	0.909	0.906
ChebyKAN	0.965	0.967	0.922	-	-	0.868
FC	0.985	0.984	0.924	0.892	0.895	0.890

KAN is less stable

The missing values in Table 4.4 indicate that ChebyKAN was unable to converge when dealing with higher-dimensional data (the missing values in Table 4.4). For instance, it failed to learn entirely when using AG_NEWS dataset, unlike the other models. In fact, a ChebyKAN model trained on AG_NEWS dataset was unable to converge in other scenarios even with smaller layers size (e.g., $[r, 128, K]$ and $[r, 256, K]$). However, it converged in other cases with reasonable accuracy, for example: 0.863 and 0.873 with network sizes $[r, 64, K]$ and $[r, 64, 32, K]$, respectively. This implied ChebyKAN’s sensitivity to the selection of the layer size, which is an additional practical difficulty. As a result, I could conclude that KAN was not suitable in some scenarios when stability is crucial (with limited resources).

4.5 Evaluating image captioning XAI algorithms

Despite the development of various explainable AI (XAI) methods to improve deep learning (DL) model explainability, little attention has been given to image captioning (IC) [46]. What’s more, evaluating these methods and their explanations remains challenging due to limited resources (e.g., human evaluators) and the inherent subjectivity of IC. To address this, I proposed two automatic metrics, XIC and $iXIC$, to assess the performance of XAI algorithms in image captioning.

4.5.1 Problem statement

Given a black-box IC model M , its goal is to process an input image x and generate a caption $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ consisting of W words or tokens (i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \{\hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \dots, \hat{y}_W\}$). A post-hoc XAI algorithm \mathcal{F}_{IC} aims to explain a query/part of the caption \hat{y}_w , given $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, \mathbf{x} and M (Equation 4.5). The expected explanation \tilde{x} is a patch of pixels from the image \mathbf{x} (i.e., $\tilde{x} \subseteq \mathbf{x}$). The objective of an evaluation method is to decide if \tilde{x} possesses enough information for M to generate the query \hat{y}_w .

$$\mathcal{F}_{IC}(\hat{y}_w | \hat{\mathbf{y}}, \mathbf{x}, M) = \tilde{x} \quad (4.5)$$

4.5.2 Metrics for image captioning XAI algorithms

Human evaluation is a cornerstone in assessing XAI performance [17]. A good explanation is generally one that sufficiently clarifies the model’s output to the user [157]. However, to ensure objective evaluation, XAI methods must also be assessed quantitatively. I proposed two metrics: XIC and its improved version $iXIC$.

XIC :

To test the explanation \tilde{x} , XIC evaluates it by generating a set of E test images $\tilde{I}_{\text{test}} = \{\tilde{i}_1, \tilde{i}_2, \dots, \tilde{i}_E\}$, each containing \tilde{x} over different backgrounds⁴. Each test image \tilde{i}_e is then passed to the captioning model M to produce a caption $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_e$. If \hat{y}_w appears in any caption (i.e., $g_e = 1$ if $\hat{y}_w \subseteq \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_e$), XIC considers the explanation \tilde{x} adequate (Equation 4.6). Thus, XIC provides a binary local evaluation of the explanation generated by the XAI method.

$$XIC(\tilde{x}|\hat{y}_w, M) = 1 - \prod_{e=1}^E (1 - g_e) \quad (4.6)$$

$iXIC$:

XIC requires selecting E backgrounds to create the test images. However, this may limit reliability in case a background shares features with the query (e.g., white background with “snow”, black background with “dark”). The improved method $iXIC$ was designed to simplify evaluation and reduce ambiguous scenarios. It uses a single test image \tilde{I}_{test} , generated by blurring the input image x around the explanation \tilde{x} . Also, it does not require running M , instead, it computes CLIP [145] cosine similarity between the query \hat{y}_w and \tilde{I}_{test} (sim_{test}). Then, it compares sim_{test} to the baseline similarity between \hat{y}_w and the original image (i.e., sim_x). If $sim_{\text{test}} > sim_x$, the explanation is classified as ‘good’, otherwise, it is ‘bad’ (Equation 4.7).

$$iXIC(\tilde{x}|\hat{y}_w) = \begin{cases} 1 & sim_{\text{test}} > sim_x \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.7)$$

⁴Selected based on user preference.

4.5.3 Experimental setup

To examine the validity of XIC and $iXIC$ I compared them to manual evaluation across various experiments⁵.

Data

For training, I used Mscoco [111] and Lvis [67], while the testing was performed on Flickr8K [205].

Models

The image captioning model was built with an encoder-decoder architecture. The encoder used a pre-trained MobileNetV3Small [1] to extract image features. The decoder was a transformer with multiple layers of causal self-attention, cross-attention (combining image and text features), and feed-forward networks that generate captions token by token.

Parameters

For XIC , three backgrounds were used: black, white, and random noise drawn from $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$. For $iXIC$, an appropriate blurring kernel size was applied to generate the test image.

Metrics

The metrics were evaluated by measuring their agreement with the human evaluator. I calculated Pearson’s correlation coefficient (ρ) [56] between human ratings and each metric across different experiments. The human evaluator scored explanations as bad (0), sufficient (0.5), or clear (1). An agreement was counted when both human and metric gave full agreement (both 1 or both 0) or when the human gave a sufficient score (0.5).

4.5.4 Results

Figure 4.4 offers a detailed view of the agreement between human and metrics across individual experiment variations. Unlike XIC , the agreement between the human evaluator and $iXIC$ was more consistent. This is supported by the Pearson correlation coefficients (ρ), where $iXIC$ scored higher (0.70) than XIC (0.31). Thus, using human evaluation as the reference, $iXIC$ served as a more reliable and stricter metric.

⁵Detailed description of these variations is in Section 4.6.3.

Figure 4.4: The consensus between human evaluation (in blue) and metrics score (red i.e., XIC in red and $iXIC$ in green) for the two IC models trained on (a) Mscoco and (b) Lvis, across several experiments (detailed in Section 4.6.3).

4.6 XAI for image captioning

Image captioning requires recognizing objects and features and understanding how they interact in a scene. Despite advances in explainable AI (XAI), image captioning is underexplored due to its complexity. Highlighting objects alone is insufficient; explanations must consider the interactions among elements to provide a holistic understanding of the caption relative to the input image. To address this, I proposed novel post-hoc XAI methods, PIC-XAI and its improved version iPIC-XAI. These model-agnostic algorithms improve explainability by linking caption predictions to relevant super-pixels in the input image.

4.6.1 Problem statement

As detailed in Section 4.5.1, a post-hoc XAI algorithm \mathcal{F}_{IC} objective is to explain the query \hat{y}_w from the caption $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ (generated by an IC model M for the input image \mathbf{x}) by the relevant part \tilde{x} , where $\tilde{x} \subseteq \mathbf{x}$ (Equation 4.5).

4.6.2 Post-hoc image captioning explanation

Both PIC-XAI and iPIC-XAI aim to explain black-box IC model predictions (i.e., captions). To understand why a specific query word \hat{y}_w appears in the caption $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, these methods rely on segmentation components to nominate candidate explanations, then evaluate their relevance

Figure 4.5: PIC-XAI pipeline (in blue) and its improvement iPIC-XAI (the blocks in red).

to select the most appropriate explanation. For example, if M outputs the caption “a man is swimming in the water”, these methods explain why the word “man” appeared by highlighting the corresponding image region.

PIC-XAI

PIC-XAI operates in two stages (blue components in Figure 4.5), each involving three steps: proposal generation, evaluation, and decision-making. In the first stage \mathcal{S}_1 , an instance segmentation model generates object-level proposals. The proposals include I objects plus the combined background (all objects jointly inverted), resulting in $I + 1$ single proposals. Then, PIC-XAI forms all possible combinations of these proposals (excluding the full image) without repetition, producing a set \mathcal{P}_1 with $2^{I+1} - 2$ proposals.

For each proposal \tilde{p}_{1i} in \mathcal{P}_1 , a processed image is created by blurring the input image outside the proposed region (Figure 4.6). This processed image is then passed to M to generate a caption \tilde{y}_{1i} . The similarity score \hat{z}_{1i} is computed as the cosine similarity between \tilde{y}_{1i} and \hat{y}_w (i.e., sim_{1i}) scaled by the proposal size ratio $\Gamma_{1i} = \frac{\text{size}(\tilde{p}_{1i})}{\text{size}(x)}$ (Equation 4.8); favoring smaller (more specific) proposals but bounded to avoid bias toward very small segments. The proposal with the highest similarity $\max_i \hat{z}_{1i}$ is selected as \tilde{p}_1 for the next stage. If multiple proposals tie, they are merged.

Figure 4.6: Partially processed (blurred) image examples.

$$\hat{z}_{1i} = \frac{sim_{1i}}{\Gamma_{1i}} \quad (4.8)$$

In the second stage \mathcal{S}_2 , low-level segmentation divides the nominated proposal \tilde{p}_1 into J smaller segments, forming \mathcal{P}_2 . The same processing, captioning, and evaluation steps are applied. However, the similarity score \hat{z}_{2j} is the cosine similarity without scaling, as the proposal sizes are more uniform. The proposal \tilde{p}_2 with the highest similarity to \hat{y}_w is selected as the final explanation \tilde{x} (Equation 4.9).

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{PIC}} = \mathcal{S}_2(\mathcal{S}_1(\cdot)) = \tilde{p}_2 \quad (4.9)$$

iPIC-XAI

iPIC-XAI was built upon PIC-XAI (red components in Figure 4.5) to address some of its limitations. First, the similarity evaluation in \mathcal{S}_1 has a high computational cost, approximately $O(2^n)$. iPIC-XAI enhances efficiency by eliminating the captioning step and directly computing the similarity between the processed proposal image and \hat{y}_w using a CLIP similarity [145].

Second, PIC-XAI favors smaller segments in \mathcal{S}_1 regardless of the query’s linguistic role. iPIC-XAI improves this by incorporating the dependency tag τ of the query \hat{y}_w as an additional clue. For example, in the caption “*a man is swimming in a pool*”, the query “*man*” has the dependency tag nominal subject (i.e., $\tau = \text{nsubj}$), suggesting a smaller, foreground segment as explanation. While “*pool*” has the tag object of preposition (i.e., $\tau = \text{pobj}$), indicating a larger segment. Consequently, if $\tau = \text{pobj}$, iPIC-XAI skips the size scaling in Equation 4.8 to allow larger proposals to be selected.

Third, PIC-XAI’s blurring kernel size for processing proposals is manually set, which can be impractical and difficult to optimize. iPIC-XAI addresses this by an iterative pre-processing procedure: the entire image is repeatedly blurred and captioned with varying kernel sizes until the predicted caption excludes any tokens from the original caption, ensuring an appropriate blur level \mathcal{B} .

Finally, in some cases, the second stage proposal \tilde{p}_2 may be irrelevant or meaningless. This may be caused by excessively small segments from low-level segmentation or deficiencies in its input (i.e., \tilde{p}_1). To mitigate this, iPIC-XAI compares the relevance scores (sim_1 and sim_2) from both stages and selects the proposal with the highest similarity as the final explanation (Equation 4.10).

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{iPIC}} = \tilde{p}_{\arg \max_{j \in \{1,2\}}(sim_j)} \quad (4.10)$$

4.6.3 Experimental setup

Two variations of PIC-XAI and six variations of iPIC-XAI were created to analyze the effect of the following factors: (1) using CLIP similarity in the first stage, (2) setting the blurring kernel \mathcal{B} size, (3) incorporating the dependency tag τ as a cue, and (4) comparing the similarity scores from both stages (i.e., between \tilde{p}_1 and \tilde{p}_2).

Data

The same training (i.e., Mscoco [111] and Lvis [67]) and testing (i.e., Flickr8K [205]) data described in Section 4.5.3 were used. The test set was constructed by selecting 100 images from the Flickr8K dataset, generating captions using the IC model, and chunking them into queries. The final test set contained 176 image-query pairs.

Models

For image captioning, I utilized the architecture described in Section 4.5.3, and trained two models (one on Mscoco and the other on Lvis). For instance segmentation in the first stage, I used Detectron2 [198], while for the second stage (i.e., low-level segmentation) I applied the Quickshift algorithm [185]. To determine the dependency tag τ of the given query, I used the spaCy python library [76].

Parameters

Table 4.5 summarizes the configuration for each experiment variation. For iPIC-XAI, the blurring kernel size \mathcal{B} either was fixed manually (i.e., 20 or 120) or it was selected automatically (i.e., through a search over the range [20, 120] with a step size of 5). For PIC-XAI, the two extremes (20 and 120) were used as fixed kernel sizes. Quickshift was configured with: kernel size = 20, max distance = 200, and ratio = 0.2.

Table 4.5: Algorithm variations details regarding the four factors: applying CLIP similarity, the kernel size \mathcal{B} , the dependency tag τ , and the similarity comparison between \tilde{p}_1 and \tilde{p}_2 .

	CLIP	\mathcal{B}	τ	sim
PIC	✗	20	✗	✗
PIC 120	✗	120	✗	✗
iPIC_clip	✓	120	✗	✗
iPIC_pobj	✗	120	✓	✗
iPIC_sim	✗	120	✗	✓
iPIC_pobj_clip	✓	120	✓	✗
iPIC_auto_pobj_clip	✓	auto	✓	✗
iPIC	✓	auto	✓	✓

Metrics

Evaluation was conducted both manually (human assessment) and automatically using the *iXIC* metric (from Section 4.5). For human evaluation, a ternary scale was used: bad (0), sufficient (0.5), and clear (1). When reporting performance, both sufficient and clear were considered as good explanations.

4.6.4 Results

High performance with efficient execution time

The impact of individual components can be observed in Table 4.6 and Figure 4.4. Comparing PIC 120 with PIC shows that adjusting the blurring kernel size \mathcal{B} significantly affected performance. For the Mscoco model, setting \mathcal{B} to 120 improved performance, while for the Lvis model, it led to a decline, highlighting the importance of appropriately tuning \mathcal{B} and the limitations of manual selection. Incorporating the query’s dependency tag τ improved performance even when applied alone. The same was observed with the similarity comparison

Table 4.6: Human and *iXIC* acceptance (\uparrow) rate for the algorithm variations. The best results are in bold.

	Mscoco		Lvis	
	Human	<i>iXIC</i>	Human	<i>iXIC</i>
PIC	0.426	0.460	0.466	0.438
PIC 120	0.472	0.494	0.415	0.398
iPIC_clip	0.466	0.443	0.409	0.398
iPIC_pobj	0.676	0.460	0.528	0.409
iPIC_sim	0.665	0.563	0.511	0.438
iPIC_pobj_clip	0.659	0.517	0.506	0.455
iPIC_auto_pobj_clip	0.676	0.500	0.568	0.494
iPIC	0.761	0.619	0.591	0.494

Figure 4.7: Execution time w.r.t number of objects detected by instance segmentation in the first stage. It grows exponentially in both cases, but is more efficient with CLIP (in blue).

component. Using CLIP similarity alone did not enhance the performance; however, it substantially reduced execution time (Fig. 4.7). Overall, iPIC-XAI produced the most positively rated answers by human evaluators. Compared to PIC-XAI, iPIC-XAI achieved 80% and 27% of relative improvement for the Mscoco and Lvis models, respectively.

Crucial rule of the dependency tag (τ)

The dependency tag τ was introduced to mitigate the criteria of favoring smaller answers. Table 4.7 shows that when $\tau = \text{pobj}$, the average answer size ratio approximately doubled for both models compared to other dependency tags. Additionally, Figure 4.8 shows that the use of dependency tag rule generally led to larger responses. It also shows that human evaluation was influenced by the answer size; bigger answers were regarded as better explanations.

Table 4.7: Explanation size ratio ($\text{size}(\tilde{x})/\text{size}(x)$) based on query dependency tag: object of preposition (pobj) vs. other tags.

	pobj	others
Mscoco	0.523	0.205
Lvis	0.636	0.376

Figure 4.8: Average answer size ratio (%) based on human evaluation (bad and good) for (a) Mscoco and (b) Lvis.

4.7 XAI for large visual question answering

Requiring access to a model’s internal architecture to generate explanations is often impractical, mainly for large models (LMs), which are commonly accessed through APIs. In such cases, black-box explanation methods are more suitable. While limited to identifying correlations rather than causal relationships, these methods offer explainability without unnecessary technical complexity for end users. Furthermore, multi-modal tasks such as VQA have received less attention in XAI research. Effective explanations must attribute contributions from both the visual and textual inputs to the generated answer.

To address this, I proposed PEX-VQA [J3], the first local black-box explanation method designed for large VQA (LVQA) models. In addition, I adapted SHAP [119], a widely used XAI method, for VQA scenarios (referred to as SHAP-VQA). Finally, I introduced a novel automatic evaluation metric (i.e., the hallucination score H) which aligns with human judgment and provides an efficient alternative to manual evaluation.

4.7.1 Problem statement

As described in Section 3.5.1, given a text-image pair x , a VQA model M generates an answer \hat{y} of length W . The visual input \mathbf{x}_{vis} corresponds to the image, which is typically partitioned into I segments or regions, each representing a distinct part of the scene (e.g., objects or background elements). The tokens/words in the textual input \mathbf{x}_{text} can be categorized based on their relevance to the image content: (1) directly connected (e.g., nouns, adjectives), (2) partially connected (e.g., verbs, prepositions), and (3) indirectly connected (e.g., articles, punctuation, adverbs); providing grammatical or contextual structure.

In this context, the objective of a post-hoc XAI algorithm \mathcal{F}_{VQA} is to provide a human-interpretable explanation \tilde{x} for the model’s prediction \hat{y} , given x and M (Equation 4.11). The method must account for both input modalities: the image and the question. Accordingly, an explanation \tilde{x} is composed of a visual component $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}}$ and/or a textual component $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}}$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}} \subseteq \mathbf{x}_{\text{vis}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}} \subseteq \mathbf{x}_{\text{text}}$.

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{VQA}}(\hat{y}|x, M) = \tilde{x} \quad (4.11)$$

4.7.2 PEX-VQA

PEX-VQA is a post-hoc, black-box XAI method that produces three types of explanations: visual $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}}$, textual $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}}$, and combined $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{comb}}$. $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}}$ contains image regions that influence the model’s answer \hat{y} independently of the question, while $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}}$ includes words (or phrases) that influence \hat{y} independently of the image. Additionally, $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{comb}}$ contains concept pairs (i.e., one visual and one textual) that are not individually important but influence the model’s prediction together.

PEX-VQA operates in three stages: (1) input processing, (2) model probing, and (3) explanation selection (Figure 4.9). The goal is to evaluate how individual input components affect the output by perturbing the inputs and analyzing the model’s behavior.

Figure 4.9: PEX-VQA pipeline. The detailed algorithm is in Appendix A, Algorithm A.6.

Input processing stage involves two steps: automatic concept nomination and perturbed input generation. In the first step, PEX-VQA identifies relevant and interpretable concepts (such as object-based image segments and individual words) based on their semantic role⁶. This is necessary to filter out low salience concepts. In the second step, two sets of perturbed inputs are created: \mathcal{P}_{vis} and $\mathcal{P}_{\text{text}}$. Each element in \mathcal{P}_{vis} is a version of the image \mathbf{x}_{vis} with one visual concept blurred. Similarly, each element in $\mathcal{P}_{\text{text}}$ is a version of the question \mathbf{x}_{text} with one textual concept masked or replaced.

Model probing is then performed to test the influence of the concepts in \mathcal{P}_{vis} and $\mathcal{P}_{\text{text}}$ individually on the original model answer \hat{y} . Specifically, PEX-VQA queries M with each item in \mathcal{P}_{vis} with the original question \mathbf{x}_{text} to get the corresponding answers $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{vis}}$. Similarly, M is queried with each item in $\mathcal{P}_{\text{text}}$ with the input image \mathbf{x}_{vis} to obtain the set of answers $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{text}}$.

Explanation selection follows in the third stage. A concept is identified as a core explanation if its modification causes the model’s output to differ from the original answer \hat{y} . Accordingly, concepts from \mathcal{P}_{vis} and $\mathcal{P}_{\text{text}}$ that meet this criterion are added to $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}}$, respectively.

Combined concepts are then selected by evaluating the joint influence of remaining non-core concepts. $\mathcal{P}_{\text{comb}}$ is generated by pairing all the items that were not selected neither in $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}}$ nor $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}}$. Pairs that alter the model’s prediction are collected into $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{comb}}$.

SHAP-VQA

SHAP [119] has been applied to explain model predictions in tasks such as image captioning (SHAP-IC) and question answering (SHAP-QA), but no native version existed for VQA.

To adapt SHAP-IC for VQA, I extended it by including the question \mathbf{x}_{text} directly into the querying process of M , while perturbing only the image \mathbf{x}_{vis} . The method estimates the contribution of different rectangular image regions to the final answer by computing their Shapley values. These values are aggregated to produce a visual explanation (i.e., $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{visSh}}$) in the form of a heatmap. Similarly, I extended SHAP-QA to VQA by including the image \mathbf{x}_{vis} during inference, resulting in textual explanations $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{textSh}}$ in the form of importance of each token in the question \mathbf{x}_{text} .

Hallucination score H

To automatically assess the validity of an XAI output, I proposed a revised version of the hallucination score H introduced by [95]⁷. In Equation 4.12, P_{yes} and P_{no} represent the model’s

⁶Detailed example in Section A.3.5 in Appendix A.

⁷See Appendix A, Section A.3.2, for a detailed comparison and justification of the modifications.

predicted probabilities for the tokens “yes” and “no”, respectively, and ϵ is a small constant to ensure numerical stability. A minor difference between P_{yes} and P_{no} ($< \beta$) indicates low confidence and potentially a hallucinated explanation.

To compute the hallucination score, a test input consisting of a yes/no question \tilde{Q}_{test} and an image \tilde{I}_{test} is constructed and used to query the VQA model M . The formation of \tilde{Q} and \tilde{I} depends on the explanation type being evaluated. In case of a concept in $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}}$, the original image remains unchanged (i.e., $\tilde{I}_{\text{test}} = \mathbf{x}_{\text{vis}}$). \tilde{Q}_{test} is created using that concept and the answer \hat{y} (e.g., if the concept is “brown” and $\hat{y} = \text{“dog”}$, then $\tilde{Q}_{\text{test}} = \text{“is the dog brown?”}$). For a concept in $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}}$, \tilde{Q} is formulated using \mathbf{x}_{text} and \hat{y} (e.g., $\mathbf{x}_{\text{text}} = \text{“what is the brown object?”}$ and $\hat{y} = \text{“dog”}$, then $\tilde{Q}_{\text{test}} = \text{“is the brown object a dog?”}$). \tilde{I}_{test} is a version of \mathbf{x}_{vis} in which all regions are blurred except for the concept. Lastly, with a concept in $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{comb}}$, \tilde{Q}_{test} is similarly composed as in case of a textual explanation, while \tilde{I}_{test} as in case of a visual explanation.

$$H = -\log [\max(|P_{\text{yes}} - P_{\text{no}}|, \epsilon)] \quad (4.12)$$

4.7.3 Experimental setup

Data

I used two VQA datasets: VQAv2 [65] and Visual Genome (VG) [88]. From each test set, I selected approximately 229 image-question pairs, with some having one associated question and others having two.

Models

I evaluated four VQA models⁸: two variations of GIT, BLIP, and ViLT, described in Section 3.3.5. For image segmentation, I used a pre-trained DETR model [48]. For textual processing, I used Google’s Gemini⁹ [4] as the large language model (LLM).

Parameters

Two variants of PEX-VQA were tested when generating textual explanations; one used “[PAD]” token for masking (i.e., PEX-VQA^P), while the other used antonyms (i.e., PEX-VQA^A). Prompt templates used with the LLM are listed in Section A.3.6. Details of all metrics,

⁸See Table A.20 in Appendix A for accuracy details on each dataset.

⁹Gemini-1.5-flash.

including value ranges and threshold settings, are provided in Sections A.3.2 and A.3.3. To ensure fairness, I only included cases where an explanation was provided¹⁰.

Metrics

I compared the hallucination score H against other potential automatic evaluation metrics: absolute difference ($diff$), uncertainty score (u), and entropy (ent). For each, I defined specific thresholds to convert their continuous outputs into binary predictions (correct/incorrect). The comparison was performed using accuracy Acc and $F_{0.5}$ with human evaluation as a ground-truth. After validating the effectiveness of the H score, I used it alongside human evaluation to assess the performance of PEX-XAI and benchmarked it against SHAP variants (SHAP-QA and SHAP-IC).

4.7.4 Results

H is a reliable and efficient automatic evaluation

Table 4.8 shows that the hallucination score (H) consistently aligned with human (manual) judgments. This indicates that H was an efficient alternative to manual evaluation for assessing XAI methods. The detailed results are provided in Table A.22 (Appendix A, Section A.3.3).

Table 4.8: The aggregated accuracy (\uparrow) and $F_{0.5}$ (\uparrow) results across all the models for the automatic metrics. The results were aggregated across all the models.

	H		$diff$		u		ent	
	Acc	$F_{0.5}$	Acc	$F_{0.5}$	Acc	$F_{0.5}$	Acc	$F_{0.5}$
VQA _{v2}	0.635	<u>0.733</u>	0.511	0.563	0.601	0.709	0.610	0.719
VG	0.707	<u>0.798</u>	0.434	0.471	0.656	0.760	0.698	0.792

PEX-VQA is more efficient and it outperforms SHAP-VQA

The results show that PEX-VQA was better than SHAP-VQA in terms of quality and efficiency. As shown in Table 4.9, PEX-XAI generally achieved higher scores than SHAP-VQA in both automatic (H) and manual evaluations. Even in a case where SHAP-VQA outperformed PEX-VQA, it was a slight difference. Detailed results per model and dataset are available in Tables A.23 and A.24 (Appendix A, Section A.3.3).

¹⁰Table A.21 in Appendix A shows explanation coverage for each method. SHAP always returns explanations, while PEX-VQA may abstain when uncertain.

Table 4.9: The human and hallucination H evaluation score (\uparrow) for both PEX-VQA and SHAP-VQA using VQAv2 and VG datasets. The first two columns correspond to the visual explanation results, while the remaining columns are for the textual explanation. The results were aggregated across all the models.

		Visual		Textual		
		PEX-VQA	SHAP-VQA	PEX-VQA ^A	PEX-VQA ^P	SHAP-VQA
Human	VQAv2	0.598	0.430	0.851	0.877	0.621
	VG	0.514	0.566	0.761	0.803	0.713
H	VQAv2	0.944	0.914	0.952	0.958	0.869
	VG	0.977	0.949	0.942	0.952	0.915

Table 4.10: The average processing time per instance (in seconds \downarrow) for VQAv2 and VG datasets. The faster (lower) processing time between PEX-VQA and SHAP-VQA is highlighted. The results were aggregated across all the models.

	PEX-VQA	SHAP-VQA
VQAv2	11.20	41.21
VG	10.16	42.05

While SHAP-VQA provides detailed, ranked associations, its exhaustive computation comes with two main drawbacks: (1) high computational cost, and (2) redundant or ambiguous outputs. As shown in Table 4.10, PEX-VQA was significantly faster on average per instance when run on the same hardware¹¹. Full breakdowns are provided in Table A.25 (Appendix A, Section A.3.3). Also, Figure 4.10 illustrates a qualitative comparison. SHAP-VQA assigned scores to all input concepts (e.g., every token in the question and every image region), even when it lacked meaning (e.g., the “?” token). In contrast, PEX-VQA does not assign numerical scores; instead, it provides focused explanations, highlighting only relevant elements.

LVQA answer influences XAI performance

The experiments indicated that the model’s predicted answer influenced the behavior of the XAI algorithm. Correct answers were generally easier to explain than incorrect ones. This is supported by the results in Table A.26 (Appendix A, Section A.3.3), which shows a consistent relationship between prediction accuracy and the clarity of explanations.

In practice, the absence of an explanation should not always be interpreted as failure. When the model’s prediction relies solely on the question (i.e., regardless of the image) a visual explanation would be misleading. Table A.21 (Appendix A, Section A.3.3) shows

¹¹GPU: NVIDIA RTX A3000 (6GB, 32 multiprocessors, CUDA 12.5, Driver 556.12); CPU: Intel i7-11850H (8 cores).

that SHAP-VQA consistently produced explanations, even when unnecessary. In contrast, PEX-VQA could recognize such cases, thereby avoiding potentially misleading outputs.

Figure 4.10: An example from the VG dataset. The image, question, and model’s answer are shown on the left. The middle section shows PEX-VQA’s visual (highlighted segment in the image) and textual (highlighted words in the question) explanations. SHAP-VQA’s outcome is on the right. All parts of the input are highlighted w.r.t Shapley values (darker indicates higher influence).

4.8 Conclusion

This chapter addressed two critical aspects of AI models: interpretability and explainability. The first part of this chapter focused on SV models. I analyzed and interpreted several existing architectures (i.e., StoryGAN, CP-CSV, and DuCo) as white-box models to identify their strengths. Based on this analysis, I proposed Mod-StoryGAN, a modular design that outperformed existing models and achieved better local and global consistency in the generated stories.

Moreover, I studied the claim that KANs are more interpretable alternative to MLPs. I found that with high-dimensional data, the number of trainable parameters in KAN increased significantly without improving accuracy. This size expansion decreased interpretability, and the KAN’s variants suitable for such data were unstable.

Additionally, I investigated the explainability of image captioning models. To support objective evaluation, I introduced two automatic metrics (i.e., XIC and its improved version $iXIC$), which correlated well with human judgment. These metrics were used to evaluate the proposed post-hoc explanation methods PIC-XAI and iPIC-XAI. Both algorithms target black-box IC models, with iPIC-XAI enhancing correctness and efficiency through improved perturbation and explanation selection strategies.

Lastly, I addressed the explainability of large visual question answering (LVQA) models, proposing PEX-VQA, a post-hoc, local XAI algorithm. To support objective evaluation, I introduced the hallucination score H , which showed better alignment with human evaluation compared to existing metrics. Experiments demonstrated that PEX-VQA outperformed SHAP-VQA in both automatic and human evaluations, providing more direct and less ambiguous explanations.

Conclusion

This chapter presents a final interpretation of the results, summarizes the main findings, and discusses potential directions for future research.

5.1 Summary of thesis achievement

The aim of the first thesis group was to enhance the robustness of classical image classifiers and generalized category discovery (GCD) models. This includes the model’s ability to handle unseen (i.e., out-of-distribution, OOD) data effectively, while maintaining performance. For such neural networks, I showed that OOD includes both semantic and non-semantic types and can be defined in terms of the training data (i.e., in-distribution, ID). I formulated the OOD detection task mathematically and developed several single and combined post-hoc algorithms to enhance the robustness of image classifiers. I also proposed a GCD algorithm (i.e., S-GCD) that outperformed stand-alone clustering and works with domain-specific data.

The second thesis group addressed the robustness of large intent classifiers and visual question answering (LVQA) models. I argued that the traditional definition of OOD does not hold for large models (LMs); since training data (ID) cannot be explicitly defined. Consequently, OOD is mainly defined by non-semantic types that correspond to the input difficulty. Also, when the input is multi-modal (i.e., text and image), an additional source of difficulty emerges (i.e., combined difficulty/relatedness). I provided a scale to categorize these aspects to quantify the input scenario difficulty. Moreover, I proposed two post-hoc algorithms (i.e., ReaL and ReDiT) to enhance the robustness and increase the trust of LMs’ prediction confidence score after re-evaluation. Furthermore, I showed that a stand-alone

LVQA could sufficiently perform zero-shot GCD. To improve its performance, I proposed two post-hoc approaches (i.e., similarity- and prompt-driven) with the help of continual learning.

In the third thesis group, I discussed two concepts: interpretability and explainability. First, I showed how interpretability with access to the model’s architecture can be used as a tool to analyze the strengths of previous story visualization (SV) solutions. I combined these components and built a modular model (i.e., Mod-StoryGAN) that outperformed the baseline models in terms of background and theme awareness. Furthermore, I investigated a recent proposal (i.e., KAN) that is claimed to be more interpretable than MLPs. Initially, I concluded that the size of the network (i.e., number of trainable parameters) was an appropriate reference to interpretability. Then, I showed that the interpretability claim did not hold when dealing with high-dimensional data such as text and images. Explainability, on the other hand, does not necessarily require access to the model’s architecture. Aiming for more practicality, I developed post-hoc XAI algorithms to explain black-box model predictions. I developed two methods for image captioning (i.e., PIC-XAI and iPIC-XAI) and the third for VQA (i.e., PEX-VQA). Additionally, I proposed automatic metrics to measure the performance of such XAI algorithms (i.e., XIC , $iXIC$, and H).

5.2 Future work

The rapid evolution and integration of large models (LMs) into various applications necessitate a thorough investigation into their trustworthiness. While the methods developed in this thesis provide a step forward, future solutions have to be designed to dynamically adapt to the continuous evolution of LMs.

Another challenge is to maintain the robustness of LMs in case of OOD inputs and adversarial perturbations. A core aspect of model robustness is the ability to accurately express its own uncertainty. Developing more systematic methods beyond current approaches (i.e., softmax-based confidence scores and model self-evaluation) is a potential direction for future work.

Building on these challenges, Agentic AI - where several models (agents) interact and collaborate to respond to a single query - requires moving beyond evaluating individual models. This opens a path towards a ‘Behavioral AI’ study, shifting the focus from evaluating single predictions (or a model) to analyzing a system’s whole behavior.

Additionally, XAI approaches that were presented in this work are local methods that follow counterfactual black-box approaches to find causal connections between input and output.

While they are useful across different tasks, they can be further improved. Examining several input perturbations increases the computational cost; thus, a careful selection of significant features could decrease the number of inferences. Another limitation is the challenge of providing global post-hoc explanations. Systematic feature evaluation across several instances might offer model-level conclusions.

Such global insights would be particularly beneficial for critical applications, especially those with legal and ethical implications. In these contexts, explanations should not only highlight which features influenced a decision but also reveal biases or risks that might undermine fairness and trust. Providing the user with a confidence score together with multiple explanations (i.e., accounting for the Rashomon effect) could enhance trust in the XAI outcome. Moreover, robust and standardized evaluation metrics for both models and XAI methods are still lacking. Establishing such baselines that are objective (consider inherited biases) and flexible (can adapt to increasing model capabilities and newly generated data).

I close this thesis work with some questions that I find compelling and might open Pandora’s box of research possibilities. The first dilemma is whether our aim should be to build models that behave like humans, or unlike them: should we aim to create a flawed, biased, but perhaps more interpretable ‘mirror’ of human cognition, or a perfectly rational, unbiased, but potentially ‘alien’ intelligence? Is the answer a third alternative: an AI that is fundamentally rational and unbiased in its core processing, yet contains a near-perfect, predictive model of human irrationality, bias, and values? These questions must be approached in light of the findings that even more analytically accurate AI systems automate human flaws instead of eliminating them [68, 31, 22].

What if the AI outcome (can be a prediction or reasoning) is genuinely incomprehensible to human thought? Would not a ‘sycophantic AI’ (i.e., an AI that optimizes for user approval) prioritize agreement over honesty [27, 162, 190]? A recent work [208] even found that ethical alignment can actually weaken the performance of such systems. A single AI, regardless of how ‘intelligent’, may not be the answer; perhaps a crowd of AIs is. Would this crowd hold the same wisdom as in humans [191]? Aren’t these AI systems trained on human-made data that inherits our biases? Answering the first dilemma might give guidance for further developments in AI.

Additional material

A.1 Thesis group 1

A.1.1 Algorithms

Algorithm A.1 Threshold (Thr)

```
1: Obtain  $Preds, \beta$  (threshold)
2:  $\hat{y} \leftarrow ArgMax(Preds)$ 
3:  $P \leftarrow max(Preds)$  Prediction confidence
4: if  $P < \beta$  then
5:    $\hat{y} \leftarrow K + 1$  OOD
6: else
7:    $\hat{y} \leftarrow \hat{y}$  K-classifier label
```

Algorithm A.2 Discriminator (Disc)

```
1: Obtain  $Preds, Disc\_Pred$ 
2:  $\hat{y} \leftarrow ArgMax(Preds)$ 
3: if  $Disc\_Pred \leftarrow fake$  then
4:    $\hat{y} \leftarrow K + 1$  OOD
5: else
6:    $\hat{y} \leftarrow \hat{y}$  K-classifier label
```

A.1.2 Proofs and equations

Estimated $K + 1$ accuracy (\hat{A}_{K+1})

Proof 1.

1. The number of instances is denoted by N . The number of ID instances and OOD instances are $N \cdot R_{\text{ID}}$ and $N \cdot R_{\text{OOD}}$, respectively. The decision between ID and OOD leads to a binary classification task. The approximate number of correct decisions among the OOD (TPR_{OOD} or TNR) and ID instances (TPR_{ID} or TPR) is expressed by Equations A.1 and A.2, respectively.

$$TPR_{\text{OOD}} \approx N \cdot R_{\text{OOD}} \cdot A_{\text{bin}} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$TPR_{\text{ID}} \approx N \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \cdot A_{\text{bin}} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

2. The correctly classified ID instances are passed to the K -classifier. The original accuracy of the K -classifier (A_K) is not more than the original model test accuracy (in which the test set consists of ID data only). The number of the true positives in the K -classification task (i.e., TP_K) can be approximated by multiplying A_K by the all number of instances in the K -classification task (TPR_{ID}).

$$TP_K \approx N \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \cdot A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K \quad (\text{A.3})$$

3. The estimated $K + 1$ classification accuracy (\hat{A}_{K+1}) is the ratio of the correct decisions.

$$\hat{A}_{K+1} = \frac{N \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \cdot A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K + N \cdot R_{\text{OOD}} \cdot A_{\text{bin}}}{N} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

After using $R_{\text{OOD}} = 1 - R_{\text{ID}}$ and simplifying Equation A.4, Equation 2.6 is obtained.

□

Inequality

Proof 2.

1. Using proof by contradiction, it can be shown that the denominator in Equation 2.11 is always positive ($A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) > 0$).

Starting by assuming the opposite of this statement,

$$A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) \leq 0 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

- (a) if $A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) = 0$, then R_{OOD} is *undefined*, which contradicts Equation 2.10.

Thus,

$$A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) \neq 0 \quad (\text{A.6})$$

- (b) If $A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) < 0$, then

$$A_{\text{bin}} < A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$1 < A_K \quad (\text{A.8})$$

but this contradicts Equation 2.9.

Therefore,

$$A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) > 0 \quad (\text{A.9})$$

2. Using the left side of the inequality (Equation 2.10) and Equation A.9, the numerator cannot be negative ($\hat{A}_{K+1} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) \geq 0$).

$$R_{\text{OOD}} \geq 0 \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\frac{\hat{A}_{K+1} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K)}{A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K)} \geq 0 \quad (\text{A.11})$$

but $A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) > 0$, then

$$\hat{A}_{K+1} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) \geq 0 \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\hat{A}_{K+1} \geq (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) \quad (\text{A.13})$$

3. Using the right side of the inequality (Equation 2.10) with Equation 2.11

$$R_{\text{OOD}} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$\frac{\hat{A}_{K+1} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K)}{A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K)} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$\hat{A}_{K+1} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) \leq A_{\text{bin}} - (A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$\hat{A}_{K+1} \leq A_{\text{bin}} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

4. Finally, combining Equation A.13 and A.17

$$A_{\text{bin}} \cdot A_K \leq \hat{A}_{K+1} \leq A_{\text{bin}} \square$$

Exact $K + 1$ accuracy (A_{K+1})

Proof 3.

1. The number of instances is denoted by N . The exact number of correct decisions among the OOD (TP_{OOD}) and ID instances (TP_{ID}) is expressed by Equations A.18 and A.19, receptively.

$$TP_{\text{OOD}} = N \cdot R_{\text{OOD}} \cdot TPR_{\text{OOD}} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

$$TP_{\text{ID}} = N \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \cdot TPR_{\text{ID}} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

2. The accuracy of the binary classification task A_{bin} comes from the sum of correct decisions divided by all decisions (Equation A.20).

$$A_{\text{bin}} = \frac{N \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \cdot TPR_{\text{ID}} + N \cdot (1 - R_{\text{ID}}) \cdot TPR_{\text{OOD}}}{N} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

Using Equation A.20, TPR_{OOD} can be expressed by Equation A.21.

$$TPR_{\text{OOD}} = \frac{A_{\text{bin}} - R_{\text{ID}} \cdot TPR_{\text{ID}}}{(1 - R_{\text{ID}})} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

3. The diagonal entries of the confusion matrix contains the true positive instances in the K -classification task, and the sum of them gives the number of correct decisions,

which is equal to accuracy A_K multiplied with all instances in the K classification task (Equation A.22).

$$TP_K = N \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \cdot TPR_{\text{ID}} \cdot A_K \quad (\text{A.22})$$

4. The exact $K + 1$ classification accuracy (A_{K+1}) is the ratio of the correct decisions.

$$A_{K+1} = \frac{N \cdot R_{\text{ID}} \cdot TPR_{\text{ID}} \cdot A_K + N \cdot (1 - R_{\text{ID}}) \cdot TPR_{\text{OOD}}}{N} \quad (\text{A.23})$$

5. After substituting the TPR_{OOD} in Equation A.23, and simplification, Equation A.23 can be written as Equation 2.12

□

Binary true positive ratio

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (\text{A.24})$$

Classification accuracy

$$Acc = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N 1(\hat{y}_i = y_i) \quad (\text{A.25})$$

Weighted classification accuracy

$$Acc^* = \frac{1}{\sum \hat{\omega}_i} \sum_{i=1}^N \hat{\omega}_i 1(\hat{y}_i = y_i) \quad (\text{A.26})$$

Where $\hat{\omega}_i$ is the sample weight adjusted according to its true class inverse prevalence.

A.1.3 Tables

Table A.1: Truth table for combined algorithms. The first two columns show two individual methods (A and B) decisions, while the others represent their decisions combined by logical OR and AND. The method decision is either in-distribution (ID) or out-of-distribution (OOD).

individual decision		combined decision	
method A	method B	OR	AND
ID	ID	ID	ID
ID	OOD	OOD	ID
OOD	ID	OOD	ID
OOD	OOD	OOD	OOD

Table A.2: Accuracy (\uparrow) results for Salinas-A and Ind-Pines datasets ($C = 5$). The columns contain the three clustering methods in addition to the average accuracy per row (last column). The best results are in bold.

	Algorithm	k-means	spectral	semi-k-means	average
Salinas-A	clustering	0.758	0.313	0.286	0.452
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.959	0.959	0.959	0.959
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.983	0.983	0.987	0.984
Ind-Pines	clustering	0.466	0.465	0.419	0.45
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.767	0.763	0.763	0.764
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.812	0.826	0.753	0.797

Table A.3: Rand index (\uparrow) results for Salinas-A and Ind-Pines datasets ($C = 5$). The columns contain the three clustering methods in addition to the average accuracy per row (last column). The best results are in bold.

	Algorithms	k-means	spectral	semi-k-means	average
Salinas-A	clustering	0.951	0.944	0.963	0.953
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.968	0.756	0.979	0.901
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.995	0.958	0.992	0.982
Ind-Pines	clustering	0.694	0.737	0.734	0.722
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.965	0.972	0.862	0.933
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.959	0.957	0.915	0.944

Table A.4: Accuracy (\uparrow) results for Salinas-A and Ind-Pines datasets ($C = 15$). The columns contain the three clustering methods in addition to the average accuracy per row (last column). The best results are in bold.

	Algorithm	k-means	spectral	semi-k-means	average
Salinas-A	clustering	0.758	0.515	0.294	0.522
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.966	0.965	0.966	0.966
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.994	0.994	0.992	0.993
Ind-Pines	clustering	0.469	0.456	0.423	0.449
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.843	0.845	0.836	0.841
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.859	0.882	0.863	0.868

Table A.5: Rand index (\uparrow) results for Salinas-A and Ind-Pines datasets ($C = 15$). The columns contain the three clustering methods in addition to the average accuracy per row (last column). The best results are in bold.

	Algorithms	k-means	spectral	semi-k-means	average
Salinas-A	clustering	0.968	0.944	0.964	0.959
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.979	0.757	0.979	0.905
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.997	0.943	0.998	0.979
Ind-Pines	clustering	0.694	0.746	0.734	0.725
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.953	0.914	0.869	0.912
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.952	0.897	0.916	0.922

Table A.6: Accuracy (\uparrow) results for Salinas-A and Ind-Pines datasets ($C = 60$). The columns contain the three clustering methods in addition to the average accuracy per row (last column). The best results are in bold.

	Algorithm	k-means	spectral	semi-k-means	average
Salinas-A	clustering	0.583	0.647	0.286	0.505
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.973	0.965	0.966	0.968
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.998	0.997	0.992	0.996
Ind-Pines	clustering	0.426	0.468	0.553	0.482
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.862	0.850	0.850	0.854
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.891	0.908	0.901	0.900

Table A.7: Rand index (\uparrow) results for Salinas-A and Ind-Pines datasets ($C = 60$). The columns contain the three clustering methods in addition to the average accuracy per row (last column). The best results are in bold.

	Algorithms	k-means	spectral	semi-k-means	average
Salinas-A	clustering	0.951	0.944	0.963	0.953
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.968	0.756	0.979	0.901
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.995	0.958	0.992	0.982
Ind-Pines	clustering	0.773	0.773	0.735	0.760
	S-GCD (SVM)	0.865	0.959	0.917	0.914
	S-GCD (MLP)	0.815	0.953	0.922	0.897

A.2 Thesis group 2

A.2.1 Algorithms

Algorithm A.3 Stand-alone

1: Obtain Y_k, M, Prompt	<i>Fixed prompt</i>
2: $\check{Y}_u \leftarrow \emptyset$	
3: for n in N do	
4: $\hat{y}_n \leftarrow M(x_n, \text{Prompt})$	<i>Novel category</i>
5: $\check{Y}_u \leftarrow \check{Y}_u \cup \{\hat{y}_n\}$	
6: $\check{Y} \leftarrow Y_k \cup \check{Y}_u$	

Algorithm A.4 Similarity-driven

1: Obtain $Y_k, M, \text{Prompt}, \beta$ (<i>threshold</i>)	<i>Fixed prompt</i>
2: $\check{Y}_u \leftarrow \emptyset$	
3: for n in N do	
4: $\check{Y}_{n-1} \leftarrow Y_k \cup \check{Y}_u$	
5: category $\leftarrow M(x_n, \text{Prompt})$	
6: for \check{y} in \check{Y}_{n-1} do	
7: if $\text{sim}(\text{category}, \check{y}) > \beta$ then	
8: $\hat{y}_n \leftarrow \check{y}$	
9: $\check{Y}_u \leftarrow \check{Y}_u \cup \{\hat{y}_n\}$	
10: break	
11: else	
12: $\hat{y}_n \leftarrow \text{category}$	<i>Novel category</i>
13: $\check{Y}_u \leftarrow \check{Y}_u \cup \{\hat{y}_n\}$	
14: $\check{Y} \leftarrow Y_k \cup \check{Y}_u$	

Algorithm A.5 Prompt-driven

1: Obtain Y_k, M, Prompt	<i>Dynamic prompt</i>
2: $\check{Y}_u \leftarrow \emptyset$	
3: for n in N do	
4: $\check{Y}_{n-1} \leftarrow Y_k \cup \check{Y}_u$	
5: include \check{Y}_{n-1} in Prompt	
6: $\hat{y}_n \leftarrow M(x_n, \text{Prompt})$	
7: if \hat{y}_n in \check{Y}_{n-1} then	
8: $\check{Y}_u \leftarrow \check{Y}_u$	
9: else	
10: $\check{Y}_u \leftarrow \check{Y}_u \cup \{\hat{y}_n\}$	<i>Novel category</i>
11: $\check{Y} \leftarrow Y_k \cup \check{Y}_u$	

A.2.2 Proofs and equations

Global \hat{T}

Proof 1.

1. I measure the proximity of P_i values to a uniform distribution using the ratio of the largest and the smallest values. Specifically, for the n^{th} instance, I denote the maximum and the minimum values for P_i across all classes in the prediction as $P_{\max}^{(n)}$ and $P_{\min}^{(n)}$, respectively. The goal is to exceed a pre-defined threshold expressed in Inequality A.27, where $\varepsilon > 0$ is a hyper-parameter defined by the user. This requirement applies to each instance n .

$$\frac{P_{\max}^{(n)}}{P_{\min}^{(n)}} > 1 + \varepsilon ; \forall n \quad (\text{A.27})$$

By substituting the largest and the smallest logit values for each instance n , the resulting inequality is as follows

$$\frac{e^{\frac{v_{\max}^{(n)}}{T}}}{\sum_{k=0}^K e^{\frac{v_k^{(n)}}{T}}} : \frac{e^{\frac{v_{\min}^{(n)}}{T}}}{\sum_{k=0}^K e^{\frac{v_k^{(n)}}{T}}} > 1 + \varepsilon ; \forall n \quad (\text{A.28})$$

Where:

$v_k^{(n)}$: the k^{th} class logit for the n^{th} instance

$$e^{\frac{v_{\max}^{(n)}}{T}} = \max_{\forall k \in K} e^{\frac{v_k^{(n)}}{T}}$$

$$e^{\frac{v_{\min}^{(n)}}{T}} = \min_{\forall k \in K} e^{\frac{v_k^{(n)}}{T}}$$

After the simplification

$$e^{\frac{v_{\max}^{(n)} - v_{\min}^{(n)}}{T}} > 1 + \varepsilon ; \forall n \quad (\text{A.29})$$

T can be expressed as

$$T > \frac{v_{\max}^{(n)} - v_{\min}^{(n)}}{\ln 1 + \varepsilon} ; \forall n \quad (\text{A.30})$$

2. Using Inequality A.30, the smallest value of T for each instance n denoted by $\hat{T}^{(n)}$ is as follows

$$\hat{T}^{(n)} = \frac{v_{\max}^{(n)} - v_{\min}^{(n)}}{\ln 1 + \varepsilon}; \forall n \quad (\text{A.31})$$

3. To ensure that all conditions are met, the smallest $\hat{T}^{(n)}$ should be selected. This choice ensures that the P_i values are farther away from uniform distribution for each instance n . Thus, \hat{T} is determined as

$$\hat{T} = \min_{\forall n \in N} \left(\hat{T}^{(n)} \right) \quad (\text{A.32})$$

□

Local \hat{T}

Proof 2.

1. To determine the smallest feasible value for T_{\max} ; where $T_{\min} \leq T \leq T_{\max}$, I begin by examining the softmax (Equation 2.1) when T reaches its upper limit ($T = T_{\max}$), where

$$0 \leq P_i \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.33})$$

For simplicity, I denote the denominator in Equation 2.1 by E , as shown in Equation A.34. Noting that v_{wi} is the i^{th} logit in the w^{th} logit vector V_w .

$$P_i = \frac{e^{\frac{v_{li}}{T_{\max}}}}{E} \quad (\text{A.34})$$

I can establish upper and lower bound for the denominator E by considering the maximum (v_{\max}) and minimum (v_{\min}) values in the logits vector V_w .

- (a) I begin by defining valid upper and lower boundaries for the summation of any vector based on its maximum and minimum values. Consider a vector $\mathcal{Z} = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_C]$ of length C , where the sum of all the elements in it (without repetition) is denoted as S .

$$S = \sum_{t=1}^C \mathcal{Z}_t \quad (\text{A.35})$$

In this case, I can set upper and lower boundaries for the sum S as follows

$$C \cdot \min(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_C) \leq S \leq C \cdot \max(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_C) \quad (\text{A.36})$$

(b) I use Inequality A.36 to estimate E 's upper and lower bounds.

$$E_{\min} \leq E \leq E_{\max} \quad (\text{A.37})$$

The upper bound (E_{\max}) occurs when each logit v_n is equal to the maximum logit value v_{\max} .

$$E_{\max} = \sum_{k=1}^K e^{\frac{v_{\max}}{T_{\max}}} = K \cdot e^{\frac{v_{\max}}{T_{\max}}} \quad (\text{A.38})$$

Similarly, the lower bound (E_{\min}) is defined when each v_{lk} is equal to the minimum logit value v_{\min} .

$$E_{\min} = \sum_{k=1}^K e^{\frac{v_{\min}}{T_{\max}}} = K \cdot e^{\frac{v_{\min}}{T_{\max}}} \quad (\text{A.39})$$

2. To determine T_{\max} , the focus is on the maximum probability P_{\max} , which represents the softmax output corresponding to the highest logit v_{\max} (i.e. $P_{\max} = P \Big|_{v_{li}=v_{\max}}$).

$$P_{\max} = \frac{e^{\frac{v_{\max}}{T_{\max}}}}{E} \quad (\text{A.40})$$

In case of P_{\max} , Inequality A.33 can be rewritten as follows

$$0 \leq P_{\max} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.41})$$

By utilizing Equations A.38, A.39 and A.40, I extend Inequality A.41. The upper bound of P_{\max} is achieved when the denominator in Equation A.40 is minimized ($E = E_{\min}$). Similarly, the lower bound is when E attains its maximum ($E = E_{\max}$).

$$0 \leq \frac{e^{\frac{v_{\max}}{T_{\max}}}}{E_{\max}} \leq P_{\max} \leq \frac{e^{\frac{v_{\max}}{T_{\max}}}}{E_{\min}} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.42})$$

I employ the right side of Inequality A.42 to estimate T_{\max}

$$\frac{e^{\frac{v_{\max}}{T_{\max}}}}{E_{\min}} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.43})$$

To address the summation in the denominator E, I use the estimation provided in Equation A.39. Then, I proceed from the inequality in Equation A.43 to get T_{\max} .

$$\frac{e^{\frac{v_{\max}}{T_{\max}}}}{N \cdot e^{\frac{v_{\min}}{T_{\max}}}} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.44})$$

After rearranging the equation, I obtain

$$e^{\frac{v_{\max} - v_{\min}}{T_{\max}}} \leq K \quad (\text{A.45})$$

By applying the natural logarithm and rearranging the inequality, Equation A.47 is obtained

$$\frac{v_{\max} - v_{\min}}{T_{\max}} \leq \ln K \quad (\text{A.46})$$

$$\frac{v_{\max} - v_{\min}}{\ln K} \leq T_{\max} \quad (\text{A.47})$$

Thus, I can estimate the most constrained upper bound for the temperature (T_{\max}) as the ratio of the difference between the minimum and maximum logits' values to the natural logarithm of the total number of tokens K (the model's vocabulary size).

$$T_{\max} \approx \frac{v_{\max} - v_{\min}}{\ln K} \quad (\text{A.48})$$

□

Weighted F-score

$$F_{\beta} = (1 + \beta^2) \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{(\beta^2 \cdot \text{Precision}) + \text{Recall}} \quad (\text{A.49})$$

Inter-quartile range

$$IQR_c = Q_{3_c} - Q_{1_c} \quad (\text{A.50})$$

Quartile intersection ratio

$$QIR = \frac{\max(0, Q_{3_0} - Q_{1_1})}{Q_{3_1} - Q_{1_0}} \quad (\text{A.51})$$

The average confidence score ratio

$$R_\mu = \frac{\mu_0}{\mu_1} \tag{A.52}$$

Where Q_1 and Q_3 are the 1st and 3rd quartiles, and c is set to 1 denoting correct or 0 for incorrect answers.

A.2.3 Tables

Table A.8: The average input scenario difficulty D_{score} for correct and incorrect LVQA models' predictions.

Model	correct (1)	incorrect (0)
GIT-Base	0.3170	0.4396
GIT-Large	0.3023	0.4342
BLIP	0.2857	0.4498
ViLT	0.3003	0.4367
All	0.3014	0.4399

Table A.9: Using the manual difficulty score estimation: The LR coefficients' weights representing each criterion's importance. The last row shows the results for all the models combined.

Model	d_{Q_s}	d_{Q_l}	d_{Q_c}	D_R	D_I	intercept
GIT-Base	0.336	-0.904	-0.086	-1.682	-0.814	1.614
GIT-Large	0.718	-2.387	-0.824	-1.974	-0.664	1.972
BLIP	-0.029	-1.895	-1.033	-2.706	-0.055	2.412
ViLT	0.259	-2.474	-0.855	-1.835	-0.602	2.230
All	0.324	-1.795	-0.776	-2.079	-0.290	1.897

Table A.10: Using the automatic difficulty score estimation: The LR coefficients' weights representing each criterion's importance. The last row shows the results for all the models combined.

Model	d_{Q_s}	d_{Q_l}	d_{Q_c}	D_R	D_I	intercept
GIT-Base	0.754	-2.252	1.574	0.086	-0.385	0.026
GIT-Large	1.710	-3.443	0.100	-0.704	0.169	0.599
BLIP	0.526	-2.651	1.186	-0.824	-0.858	1.485
ViLT	0.699	-2.89	-0.063	-0.751	-0.922	1.912
All	0.639	-3.162	1.579	-1.668	-1.113	2.246

Table A.11: Using the manual difficulty score estimation: accuracy (Acc) \uparrow and (F_β) \uparrow scores ($\beta = 0.5$) for both types of classifiers: LR and MLP. The second column shows the used feature set. The last group of rows shows the results for all the models combined. The best results are in bold.

Model	Features	classifier			
		LR		MLP	
		Acc	$F_{0.5}$	Acc	$F_{0.5}$
GIT-Base	P	0.624	0.624	0.625	0.625
	D_{score}	0.666	0.663	0.666	0.667
	$Diff$	0.682	0.683	0.742	0.750
	P and D_{score}	0.688	0.692	0.708	0.733
	P and $Diff$	0.706	0.708	0.773	0.790
GIT-Large	P	0.652	0.655	0.650	0.653
	D_{score}	0.674	0.674	0.674	0.673
	$Diff$	0.685	0.681	0.736	0.738
	P and D_{score}	0.683	0.683	0.712	0.723
	P and $Diff$	0.713	0.710	0.774	0.783
BLIP	P	0.636	0.638	0.637	0.638
	D_{score}	0.733	0.733	0.733	0.733
	$Diff$	0.744	0.743	0.760	0.760
	P and D_{score}	0.721	0.722	0.719	0.721
	P and $Diff$	0.762	0.760	0.800	0.799
ViLT	P	0.623	0.623	0.623	0.622
	D_{score}	0.669	0.671	0.670	0.671
	$Diff$	0.742	0.741	0.770	0.772
	P and D_{score}	0.703	0.708	0.708	0.717
	P and $Diff$	0.753	0.756	0.775	0.782
All	P	0.625	0.625	0.625	0.626
	D_{score}	0.683	0.683	0.682	0.682
	$Diff$	0.701	0.700	0.737	0.741
	P and D_{score}	0.692	0.693	0.707	0.717
	P and $Diff$	0.720	0.721	0.767	0.773

Table A.12: Using the automatic difficulty score estimation: accuracy (Acc) \uparrow and (F_β) \uparrow scores ($\beta = 0.5$) for both types of classifiers; LR and MLP. The second column shows the used feature set. The last group of rows shows the results for all the models combined. The best results are in bold.

Model	Features	classifier			
		LR		MLP	
		Acc	$F_{0.5}$	Acc	$F_{0.5}$
GIT-Base	P	0.607	0.603	0.607	0.603
	D_{score}	0.500	0.502	0.501	0.472
	$Diff$	0.591	0.593	0.595	0.596
	P and D_{score}	0.606	0.601	0.606	0.601
	P and $Diff$	0.631	0.632	0.630	0.631
GIT-Large	P	0.640	0.642	0.638	0.639
	D_{score}	0.484	0.487	0.511	0.478
	$Diff$	0.603	0.604	0.626	0.625
	P and D_{score}	0.639	0.64	0.637	0.638
	P and $Diff$	0.655	0.658	0.669	0.671
BLIP	P	0.635	0.637	0.636	0.637
	D_{score}	0.559	0.560	0.545	0.539
	$Diff$	0.639	0.639	0.663	0.660
	P and D_{score}	0.636	0.637	0.635	0.636
	P and $Diff$	0.669	0.672	0.690	0.693
ViLT	P	0.625	0.625	0.627	0.627
	D_{score}	0.61	0.611	0.597	0.565
	$Diff$	0.650	0.650	0.702	0.688
	P and D_{score}	0.644	0.648	0.648	0.651
	P and $Diff$	0.676	0.674	0.702	0.697
All	P	0.627	0.627	0.627	0.627
	D_{score}	0.555	0.558	0.544	0.551
	$Diff$	0.635	0.635	0.668	0.664
	P and D_{score}	0.625	0.625	0.625	0.626
	P and $Diff$	0.655	0.657	0.669	0.670

Table A.13: The correct and incorrect predictions’ maximum and minimum logits values for the three languages. The tests were performed on *full* test sets (*short* and *long* combined). The values are in $(\mu_{\max} \pm \sigma_{\max}, \mu_{\min} \pm \sigma_{\min})$.

<i>en</i> (English)		
	correct (1)	incorrect (0)
MiniLM	$(9.51 \pm 1.08, -5.58 \pm 0.88)$	$(7.88 \pm 1.45, -5.58 \pm 0.86)$
XLM	$(12.55 \pm 1.08, -3.19 \pm 0.51)$	$(10.13 \pm 2.22, -3.42 \pm 0.58)$
XLNet	$(10.65 \pm 0.90, -2.72 \pm 0.37)$	$(9.10 \pm 1.67, -2.83 \pm 0.38)$
<i>en</i> (Esperanto)		
	correct (1)	incorrect (0)
MiniLM	$(8.94 \pm 1.42, -5.52 \pm 0.89)$	$(7.17 \pm 1.56, -5.48 \pm 0.93)$
XLM	$(11.26 \pm 1.97, -3.28 \pm 0.52)$	$(8.63 \pm 2.47, -3.36 \pm 0.53)$
XLNet	$(9.54 \pm 1.82, -2.75 \pm 0.47)$	$(8.29 \pm 2.40, -3.03 \pm 0.38)$
<i>pa</i> (Punjabi)		
	correct (1)	incorrect (0)
MiniLM	$(8.73 \pm 1.52, -5.60 \pm 0.94)$	$(7.25 \pm 1.53, -5.45 \pm 0.99)$
XLM	$(11.29 \pm 2.00, -3.18 \pm 0.53)$	$(8.79 \pm 2.31, -3.31 \pm 0.52)$
XLNet	$(5.66 \pm 1.64, -2.80 \pm 0.27)$	$(5.04 \pm 0.49, -2.77 \pm 0.21)$

Table A.14: IQR (\downarrow) results of the models for both incorrect and correct predicted scenarios are in the first and second groups of columns, respectively. Each group has four columns, the first shows the original P , while the other three are for the re-evaluated score P_T , using the (1) manual, (2) automatic, and (3) semi-automatic difficulty estimation. The last row shows the results for all the models combined. The best results are in bold and the second best are underlined.

Model	IQR_0				IQR_1			
	P	P_T manual	P_T auto	P_T semi	P	P_T manual	P_T auto	P_T semi
GIT-Base	0.191	0.074	0.048	<u>0.058</u>	0.487	0.307	0.110	<u>0.235</u>
GIT-Large	0.256	0.126	0.075	<u>0.096</u>	0.502	0.371	0.142	<u>0.292</u>
BLIP	0.176	0.060	0.035	<u>0.044</u>	0.361	0.230	0.083	<u>0.174</u>
ViLT	0.260	0.059	0.026	<u>0.040</u>	0.531	0.316	0.072	<u>0.185</u>
All	0.225	0.071	0.040	<u>0.054</u>	0.474	0.302	0.106	<u>0.222</u>

Table A.15: QIR (\downarrow) and R_μ (\downarrow) are in the first and second groups of columns, respectively. Each group has four columns, the first shows the original P , while the other three are for the re-evaluated score P_T , using the (1) manual, (2) automatic and (3) semi-automatic difficulty estimation. The last row shows the results for all the models combined. The best results are in bold and the second best are underlined.

Model	QIR				R_μ			
	P	P_T manual	P_T auto	P_T semi	P	P_T manual	P_T auto	P_T semi
GIT-Base	0.242	0.171	0.345	<u>0.200</u>	0.507	0.360	0.568	<u>0.378</u>
GIT-Large	0.277	0.222	0.520	<u>0.266</u>	0.564	0.423	0.658	<u>0.441</u>
BLIP	0.268	<u>0.104</u>	0.271	0.099	0.563	0.359	0.546	<u>0.371</u>
ViLT	0.263	<u>0.072</u>	0.132	0.056	0.579	<u>0.292</u>	0.448	0.290
All	0.286	0.124	0.247	<u>0.130</u>	0.562	0.345	0.528	<u>0.353</u>

Table A.16: The models’ thresholds were selected (based on Youden’s index) separately for the original P and the re-evaluated P_T (for manual, automatic, and semi-automatic estimated difficulty).

Model	P	P_T	P_T	P_T
		manual	auto	semi
GIT-Base	0.197	0.114	0.058	0.087
GIT-Large	0.297	0.235	0.092	0.194
BLIP	0.290	0.098	0.058	0.096
ViLT	0.210	0.084	0.040	0.062

Table A.17: The accuracy Acc (\uparrow) and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve AUC_{ROC} (\uparrow) between the original P and the re-evaluated P_T scores. The re-evaluation was performed based on the manual, semi-automatic and automatic difficulty estimation. The best score is in bold, while the second best is underlined.

Model	Acc				AUC_{ROC}			
	P	P_T	P_T	P_T	P	P_T	P_T	P_T
		manual	auto	semi		manual	auto	semi
GIT-Base	0.645	0.711	0.634	<u>0.694</u>	0.683	0.694	0.642	<u>0.684</u>
GIT-Large	0.649	<u>0.722</u>	0.617	0.726	0.670	0.684	0.599	<u>0.671</u>
BLIP	0.704	<u>0.740</u>	0.686	0.769	0.679	0.744	0.667	<u>0.737</u>
ViLT	0.554	0.717	<u>0.667</u>	0.717	0.683	<u>0.759</u>	0.722	0.762
All	0.694	<u>0.706</u>	0.678	0.736	0.671	0.721	0.659	<u>0.710</u>

Table A.18: Prompts

Type	Cifar-10	iNat
fixed	<p><i>what is the object in the image? answer with one word.</i></p>	<p><i>What <u>biological class</u> does the object in the image belong to? Answer with one word, <u>the latin term.</u></i></p>
dynamic	<p><i>What is depicted on the image, choose from this list: $\{\hat{y}^{(1)}\}$, a $\{\hat{y}^{(2)}\}$, ..., or a $\{\hat{y}^{(n-1)}\}$. If none fits, add a new category. Avoid plurals, conjugations, synonyms and answer with a single word.</i></p>	<p><i>What <u>biological class</u> does the object in the image belong to, choose from this list: $\{\hat{y}^{(1)}\}$, a $\{\hat{y}^{(2)}\}$, ..., or a $\{\hat{y}^{(n-1)}\}$. If none fits, <u>provide its biological class</u> <u>with its latin term.</u> <u>Avoid kingdoms, divisions,</u> <u>and other ranks,</u> <u>always give a class.</u> <u>Answer strictly</u> <u>with one word.</u></i></p>

A.2.4 Figures

Figure A.1: Instance count distribution for the manually evaluated D -score in 3U-VQA dataset. Manual scoring produces discrete values within a relatively wide range (0 to 0.75).

Figure A.2: Instance count distribution for the automatically estimated D -score in 3U-VQA dataset. Automatic results in continuous values within a narrower range (0.44 to 0.84).

Figure A.3: The count of question-image instances per (manually evaluated) difficulty criteria in the 3U-VQA dataset. The first three groups of bars from the left are for the major criteria, the others are for the minor ones. Image-related difficulty D_I and *used language* d_{Qu} criteria are unbalanced; score 1 for both represents very rare scenarios, and more instances would bias the results.

Figure A.4: The count of question-image instances per automatically estimated difficulty criteria in the 3U-VQA dataset. Instead of scores, due to the continuous values ranges are shown. The first three groups of bars from the left are for major criteria, the others for minor. The criteria are unbalanced, which indicates a deviation from manual evaluation.

Figure A.5: The used models' (correct and wrong) predictions confidence score average. The predictions are for Esperanto *full* test set. The top row is when the softmax score was calculated using $T = 1$, and the bottom row is when $T = \hat{T}$ (recalculated confidence). Each subfigure is for a separate model. The red line and square on the boxplot show the median and the mean, respectively.

Figure A.6: The used models' (correct and wrong) predictions confidence score average. The predictions are for Punjabi *full* test set. The top row is when the softmax score was calculated using $T = 1$, and the bottom row is when $T = \hat{T}$ (recalculated confidence). Each subfigure is for a separate model. The red line and square on the boxplot show the median and the mean, respectively.

A.3 Thesis group 3

A.3.1 Algorithms

Algorithm A.6 PEX-VQA

Require: $\mathbf{x}_{\text{vis}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{text}}, \hat{y}, M$

1:	$\mathcal{P}_{\text{vis}} \leftarrow \text{Process}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{vis}})$	<i>Visual</i>
2:	Initialize $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}} \leftarrow \emptyset$	
3:	for vis in \mathcal{P}_{vis} do	
4:	$\tilde{y}_{\text{vis}} \leftarrow M(\text{vis}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{text}})$	
5:	if $\tilde{y}_{\text{vis}} \neq \hat{y}$ then	
6:	$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}} \leftarrow \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}} \cup \{\text{vis}\}$	
7:	$\mathcal{P}_{\text{text}} \leftarrow \text{Process}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{text}})$	<i>Textual</i>
8:	Initialize $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}} \leftarrow \emptyset$	
9:	for txt in $\mathcal{P}_{\text{text}}$ do	
10:	$\tilde{y}_{\text{text}} \leftarrow M(\mathbf{x}_{\text{vis}}, \text{txt})$	
11:	if $\tilde{y}_{\text{text}} \neq \hat{y}$ then	
12:	$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}} \leftarrow \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}} \cup \{\text{txt}\}$	
13:	$\mathcal{P}_{\text{comb}} \leftarrow \{(\text{vis}, \text{txt}) \mid \text{vis} \in (\mathcal{P}_{\text{vis}} \setminus \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}}) \text{ and } \text{txt} \in (\mathcal{P}_{\text{text}} \setminus \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}})\}$	<i>Combined</i>
14:	Initialize $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{comb}} \leftarrow \emptyset$	
15:	for (vis, txt) in $\mathcal{P}_{\text{comb}}$ do	
16:	$\tilde{y}_{\text{comb}} \leftarrow M(\text{vis}, \text{txt})$	
17:	if $\tilde{y}_{\text{comb}} \neq \hat{y}$ then	
18:	$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{comb}} \leftarrow \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{comb}} \cup \{(\text{vis}, \text{txt})\}$	
19:	return $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{vis}}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{text}}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{comb}}$	

A.3.2 Proofs and equations

Training objective function (Mod-StoryGAN)

The input textual story is denoted as \mathbf{x} , the corresponding generated set of images as $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, and the ground-truth set of images as \mathbf{y} . Hence, \hat{y}_s denotes the generated image sampled from the distribution $\mathbb{P}_{\hat{y}_s}$ during the s^{th} stage of generation.

The first term \mathcal{L}_{KL} in the objective function (Equation 4.3) is for the story encoder (Equation A.53). This term uses Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence between the learned distribution from \mathbf{x} and the standard Gaussian distribution. \mathbf{x} is passed to $\mu(\cdot)$ and $\sigma(\cdot)$ to get the mean and the standard deviation of the distribution, respectively, and $\sigma^2(\mathbf{x})$ is restricted as a diagonal matrix by $\text{diag}(\cdot)$.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}} = \text{KL} \left[\mathcal{N} \left(\mu(\mathbf{x}), \text{diag}(\sigma^2(\mathbf{x})) \right) \parallel \mathcal{N}(0, 1) \right] \quad (\text{A.53})$$

The generator conditional loss function (Equation A.54) consists of two terms for the conditional loss of the image and the story discriminator, respectively.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}} = -\frac{1}{2} E_{\hat{y}_s \sim \mathbb{P}_{\hat{y}_s}} \left[\log \left(\mathcal{D}_{\text{img}}(\hat{y}_s, x_s) \right) \right] - \frac{1}{2} E_{\hat{\mathbf{y}} \sim \mathbb{P}_{\hat{\mathbf{y}}}} \left[\log \left(\mathcal{D}_{\text{story}}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}, \mathbf{x}) \right) \right] \quad (\text{A.54})$$

The losses for the image, figure-ground, story discriminators, and the dual learning component are represented by Equations A.55, A.56, A.57 and A.58.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{D}_{\text{img}}} = -\frac{1}{2} E_{y_s \sim \mathbb{P}_{y_s}} \left[\log \left(\mathcal{D}_{\text{img}}(y_s, x_s) \right) \right] - \frac{1}{2} E_{\hat{y}_s \sim \mathbb{P}_{\hat{y}_s}} \left[\log \left(1 - \mathcal{D}_{\text{img}}(\hat{y}_s, x_s) \right) \right] \quad (\text{A.55})$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{D}_{\text{fg}}} = -\frac{1}{2} E_{y_s \sim \mathbb{P}_{y_s}} \left[\log \left(\mathcal{D}_{\text{fg}}(y_s, x_s) \right) \right] - \frac{1}{2} E_{\hat{y}_s \sim \mathbb{P}_{\hat{y}_s}} \left[\log \left(1 - \mathcal{D}_{\text{fg}}(\hat{y}_s, x_s) \right) \right] \quad (\text{A.56})$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{D}_{\text{story}}} = -\frac{1}{2} E_{\mathbf{y} \sim \mathbb{P}_{\mathbf{y}}} \left[\log \left(\mathcal{D}_{\text{story}}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}) \right) \right] - \frac{1}{2} E_{\hat{\mathbf{y}} \sim \mathbb{P}_{\hat{\mathbf{y}}}} \left[\log \left(1 - \mathcal{D}_{\text{story}}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}, \mathbf{x}) \right) \right] \quad (\text{A.57})$$

\mathcal{L}_{dual} is the loss term for the dual learning component (Equation A.58). It is a cross-entropy loss on the predicted vocabulary probability distribution (\mathbb{P}_ζ) over its vocabulary (ζ) of length K . As mentioned earlier, the model was trained after freezing the pre-trained parameters of the dual learning component.

$$\mathcal{L}_{dual} = \sum_{w=1}^W \sum_{k=1}^K \log\left(\mathbb{P}_{\zeta_{w,k}}(\zeta_{w,k})\right) \quad (\text{A.58})$$

Hallucination score H

The authors of [95] proposed a method to enhance the factual accuracy of captions by decomposing each caption into core units (e.g., atomic propositions). Each unit is then converted into a True/False question, and its accuracy is assessed using the hallucination score $H(u)$ (Equation A.59).

$$H(u) = -\log(\min(p(T|x, Q(u)) - p(F|x, Q(u)), \epsilon)) \quad (\text{A.59})$$

Where u is the core unit (e.g., atomic proposition), $Q(\cdot)$ is the function that converts the unit into a True/False question, x is the input image, ϵ is a small constant near zero, and $p(T)$ and $p(F)$ are the probability scores of the “True” and “False” tokens, respectively. A unit u is considered correct if $H(u)$ is less than or equal to a threshold. In other words, a larger difference between $p(T)$ and $p(F)$ (i.e., a smaller $\log(\cdot)$) indicates higher model confidence in the correctness of u .

Although the logic behind this formula appears valid, I argued that it lacks mathematical stability. Therefore, I proposed a modified version (Equation 4.12). Below, I provide a detailed explanation of each component of the formula:

- I retained the negative sign in Equation 4.12, as in Equation A.59, since $\log(\cdot)$ always yields a negative value (the probability difference is less than 1).
- The use of \min in Equation A.59 makes ϵ an upper bound, given that ϵ is a small constant near zero. Consequently, $H(u)$ tends to capture ϵ rather than the actual probability difference, which is the primary focus of this score. Consequently, I substituted \min (in Equation A.59) by \max (in Equation 4.12).
- I retained ϵ in Equation 4.12 to ensure mathematical stability when the probability difference approaches zero (i.e., smaller than ϵ).

- I incorporated the absolute probability difference in Equation 4.12 because my goal was to assess the model’s confidence in its prediction — larger differences indicate higher confidence, while smaller differences indicate uncertainty. The actual model response (whether “*yes*” or “*no*”) is irrelevant in such application. Moreover, taking the absolute difference enhances mathematical stability, as negative values would lead to invalid $\log(\cdot)$ computations.

Absolute difference

$$diff = |P_{\text{yes}} - P_{\text{no}}| \quad (\text{A.60})$$

Uncertainty score

$$u = 1 - \frac{diff}{P_{\text{yes}} + P_{\text{no}}} \quad (\text{A.61})$$

Entropy

$$ent = - \left[P_{\text{yes}} \cdot \left(\log \left[\frac{P_{\text{yes}}}{P_{\text{yes}} + P_{\text{no}}} \right] \right) + P_{\text{no}} \cdot \left(\log \left[\frac{P_{\text{no}}}{P_{\text{yes}} + P_{\text{no}}} \right] \right) \right] \quad (\text{A.62})$$

Weighted F-score

$$F_{\beta} = (1 + \beta^2) \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{(\beta^2 \cdot \text{Precision}) + \text{Recall}} \quad (\text{A.63})$$

A.3.3 Tables

Table A.19: Approximate range and threshold β for the hallucination score (H range is (0,4); $-\log(0.0001) = 4$ at $\epsilon = 0.0001$), absolute difference ($diff$), uncertainty score (u), and entropy (ent reaches its upper bound, when $P_{yes} = P_{no}$). An upward arrow (\uparrow) denotes correctness for scores above β ; a downward arrow (\downarrow) denotes correctness for scores below β .

	$H \downarrow$	$diff \uparrow$	$u \downarrow$	$ent \downarrow$
range	$(0, -\log(\epsilon))$	$[0, 1]$	$[0, 1]$	$(0, 0.3)$
β	2.1	0.2	0.9	0.2

Table A.20: LVQA models’ response accuracy score for each used dataset.

	GIT-Base	GIT-Large	BLIP	ViLT
VQAv2	0.830	0.843	0.865	0.790
VG	0.834	0.873	0.948	0.868

Table A.21: The percentage (%) of instances when the explanation was provided w.r.t the total number (229) using the VQAv2 dataset and VG dataset. The first two columns correspond to the visual explanation results, while the remaining columns are for the textual explanation.

		Visual		Textual		
		PEX-VQA	SHAP-VQA	PEX-VQA ^A	PEX-VQA ^P	SHAP-VQA
VQAv2	GIT-Base	76.42	100.00	68.56	65.07	100.00
	GIT-Large	69.00	100.00	68.56	61.14	100.00
	BLIP	62.45	100.00	77.73	69.43	100.00
	ViLT	65.07	100.00	75.55	75.11	100.00
	All	68.23	100.00	72.60	67.69	100.00
VG	GIT-Base	73.80	100.00	76.42	64.63	100.00
	GIT-Large	72.05	100.00	74.64	68.12	100.00
	BLIP	57.21	100.00	79.48	72.93	100.00
	ViLT	56.77	100.00	72.93	68.56	100.00
	All	64.96	100.00	75.87	68.56	100.00

Table A.22: Alignment between all automatic metrics and human evaluation is indicated by accuracy (\uparrow) and $F_{0.5}$ (\uparrow) using the VQAv2 dataset and VG dataset. The highest accuracy is in bold, the best $F_{0.5}$ is underlined for each model (each row). The last row of each group contains the results across all the models combined.

		<i>H</i>		<i>diff</i>		<i>u</i>		<i>ent</i>	
		<i>Acc</i>	<i>F</i> _{0.5}	<i>Acc</i>	<i>F</i> _{0.5}	<i>Acc</i>	<i>F</i> _{0.5}	<i>Acc</i>	<i>F</i> _{0.5}
VQAv2	GIT-Base	0.649	<u>0.747</u>	0.418	0.374	0.605	0.713	0.637	0.745
	GIT-Large	0.674	<u>0.769</u>	0.484	0.560	0.624	0.733	0.648	0.752
	BLIP	0.554	<u>0.655</u>	0.501	0.430	0.529	0.632	0.537	0.654
	ViLT	0.768	0.747	0.764	0.738	0.768	<u>0.749</u>	0.750	0.721
	All	0.635	<u>0.733</u>	0.511	0.563	0.601	0.709	0.610	0.719
VG	GIT-Base	0.685	0.780	0.384	0.342	0.624	0.732	0.698	<u>0.790</u>
	GIT-Large	0.730	<u>0.815</u>	0.523	0.625	0.697	0.792	0.722	0.810
	BLIP	0.748	0.836	0.375	0.419	0.713	0.813	0.783	<u>0.857</u>
	ViLT	0.659	<u>0.751</u>	0.456	0.430	0.582	0.684	0.575	0.685
	All	0.707	<u>0.798</u>	0.434	0.471	0.656	0.760	0.698	0.792

Table A.23: Manual evaluation (\uparrow) for both PEX-VQA and SHAP-VQA using the VQAv2 dataset and VG dataset. The first two columns correspond to the visual explanations, while the remaining columns correspond to the textual explanation. The highest score for each model in **bold**. The last row aggregates the results across all models.

		Visual		Textual		
		PEX-VQA	SHAP-VQA	PEX-VQA ^A	PEX-VQA ^P	SHAP-VQA
VQAv2	GIT-Base	0.589	0.480	0.847	0.867	0.690
	GIT-Large	0.576	0.576	0.815	0.850	0.804
	BLIP	0.636	0.223	0.865	0.887	0.384
	ViLT	0.597	0.441	0.872	0.901	0.607
	All	0.598	0.430	0.851	0.877	0.621
VG	GIT-Base	0.403	0.524	0.674	0.716	0.655
	GIT-Large	0.442	0.576	0.749	0.746	0.782
	BLIP	0.687	0.629	0.808	0.874	0.856
	ViLT	0.577	0.532	0.814	0.866	0.559
	All	0.514	0.566	0.761	0.803	0.713

Table A.24: The hallucination H (automatic) evaluation score (\uparrow) for both PEX-VQA and SHAP-VQA using the VQAv2 dataset (the first group) and VG dataset (the second group). The first two columns correspond to the visual explanation results, while the remaining columns are for the textual explanation. The highest score for each model is highlighted in **bold**. The last row aggregates the results across all models, providing an overall comparison between the two approaches.

		Visual		Textual		
		PEX-VQA	SHAP-VQA	PEX-VQA ^A	PEX-VQA ^P	SHAP-VQA
VQAv2	GIT-Base	0.954	0.904	0.943	0.973	0.812
	GIT-Large	0.975	0.952	0.943	0.964	0.856
	BLIP	0.853	0.878	0.972	0.969	0.939
	ViLT	0.987	0.921	0.948	0.930	0.960
	All	0.944	0.914	0.952	0.958	0.867
VG	GIT-Base	0.977	0.974	0.920	0.953	0.887
	GIT-Large	0.994	0.978	0.947	0.981	0.913
	BLIP	0.970	0.948	0.945	0.940	0.939
	ViLT	0.962	0.895	0.958	0.936	0.921
	All	0.977	0.949	0.942	0.952	0.915

Table A.25: The average processing time per instance (in seconds \downarrow) for both datasets. The first group (from the left) of columns corresponds to the VQAv2 dataset, while the second group corresponds to the VG dataset. Within each group, the faster (lower) processing time between PEX-VQA and SHAP-VQA is highlighted.

		VQAv2		VG	
		PEX-VQA	SHAP-VQA	PEX-VQA	SHAP-VQA
	GIT-Base	10.32	45.63	10.63	45.17
	GIT-Large	19.55	68.17	15.88	72.58
	BLIP	08.09	26.84	07.57	26.05
	ViLT	06.85	24.20	06.55	24.41
	All	11.20	41.21	10.16	42.05

Table A.26: The human (manual) and hallucination H (automatic) evaluation scores (\uparrow) for explanations provided in correctly and incorrectly answered scenarios. The evaluation was conducted for both PEX-VQA and SHAP-VQA across all models using the VQAv2 dataset (the first group) and VG dataset (the second group). The highest score for each case is highlighted in **bold**.

			Human		H	
			correct	incorrect	correct	incorrect
VQAv2	Visual	PEX-VQA	0.668	0.283	0.941	0.956
		SHAP-VQA	0.467	0.247	0.915	0.909
	Textual	PEX-VQA ^A	0.873	0.756	0.961	0.911
		PEX-VQA ^P	0.899	0.794	0.968	0.9216
		SHAP-VQA	0.642	0.520	0.890	0.753
VG	Visual	PEX-VQA	0.591	0.069	0.976	0.977
		SHAP-VQA	0.630	0.091	0.949	0.946
	Textual	PEX-VQA ^A	0.840	0.242	0.942	0.945
		PEX-VQA ^P	0.902	0.250	0.953	0.948
		SHAP-VQA	0.799	0.073	0.921	0.872

Table A.27: The overall consensus (\uparrow) between human evaluation and metric score for the two test sets.

	XIC	$iXIC$
Mscoco	0.587	0.542
Lvis	0.558	0.464

A.3.4 Figures

Figure A.7: The relative frequency of PororoSV's characters' appearance.

Figure A.8: The relative frequency of PororoSV's themes.

A.3.5 Examples

PEX-VQA process example

Considering the example in Table A.28. The LVQA model M responds to the original question Q : “*What color is the microwave?*” with the answer A : “*black*”. Some parts of the question (e.g., “*is*”) can be entirely removed or replaced without affecting the model’s answer. Altering other parts (e.g., “*color*”) might (or might not) result in a change in A , while modifying certain elements (e.g., “*microwave*”) immediately influences the model’s response.

Table A.28: An LVQA model M responses (in the 3rd column) for nine different questions (in the 2nd column) and the image (in the 4th column). The original (non-modified) question and answer appear in the first row. The remaining questions are modified by either removing (i.e., questions 2, 4, and 7) or replacing (i.e., questions 3, 5, 6, 8, and 9) a word each time. Modified words in the questions are underlined. Deviations in the model’s responses (compared to the original answer in the 1st row) are underlined.

	Question	Answer	Image
1	what color is the microwave?	black	
2	<u>[PAD]</u> color is the microwave?	black	
3	what color <u>was</u> the microwave?	black	
4	what <u>[PAD]</u> is the microwave?	<u>0</u>	
5	what <u>shade</u> was the microwave?	black	
6	what <u>dimension</u> was the microwave?	<u>0</u>	
7	what color is the <u>[PAD]</u> ?	<u>white</u>	
8	what color is the <u>cooker</u> ?	<u>white</u>	
9	what color is the <u>dog</u> ?	<u>no dog</u>	

In this example, let’s say that there are 4 main segments ($I = 4$): the microwave, the stove, the knives, and the tables. Regarding the textual component, it can be tokenized, where each token is considered a textual concept. However, a refined set of textual concepts can be formed by excluding ‘irrelevant’ tokens. For instance, question articles, punctuation, or adverbs have little meaning on their own, and using them as explanations for the prediction is not useful. Instead, PEX-VQA employs a large language model (LLM) to identify the most relevant tokens. For example, given the question “*What color is the microwave?*”, tokenizing

the question results in eight tokens: “*what*”, “*color*”, “*is*”, “*the*”, “*micro*”, “*wave*”, and “*?*”. Most of these tokens are irrelevant for the explanation, excluding them results in two textual concepts: “*color*” and “*microwave*”.

To generate the perturbed input, PEX-XAI modifies the selected concepts and creates a set of perturbed images (\hat{I}) and questions (\hat{Q}). Thus, \hat{I} has four images, where one segment out of the four (i.e., microwave, stove, knives, and tables) is blurred each time. Similarly, \hat{Q} consists of two items: each is a modified question (e.g., “*color*” is modified in one and “*microwave*” in the other). The modification is either done by masking (e.g., “[PAD]”) or replacement (e.g., “*color*” becomes “*dimension*”).

The next step is the model probing. The model needs to answer six scenarios: four in which each item in \hat{I} is passed with the original question Q , and two for each item in \hat{Q} with the original image I .

To judge if the *microwave* segment influences the model’s prediction, PEX-VQA passes the image where the *microwave* segment is blurred (along with the original question Q). If the response is different than “*black*”, then the *microwave* segment constitutes a visual explanation. Similarly, if with the question: “*What color is the [PAD]?*” (along with the original image Q), if the answer is “*white*”, then, “*microwave*” is a textual core concept. Until this point, there are two sets of explanations: (1) visual concepts/explanations \tilde{x}_{vis} (e.g. {*microwave* segment}) and (2) textual concepts/explanations \tilde{x}_{text} (e.g. {“*microwave*”}). Lastly, the same process is performed on the remaining concepts (that were not selected individually). after combining them in pairs (e.g., the word “*color*” paired with the *stove*, *knives*, and *tables* segments) to form the set of the combined explanations E_{comb} .

To evaluate the textual explanation using the hallucination score H (with the answer $A = \text{“black”}$ and the textual explanation set $\tilde{x}_{\text{text}} = \{\text{“microwave”}\}$), \tilde{Q} becomes “*is the microwave black?*” and \tilde{I} is the original image I . For the visual explanations, both the question and the image are modified. For instance, $\tilde{Q} = \text{“is the color of the microwave black?”}$, and \tilde{I} is generated by blurring all regions of I except for the *microwave* segment. For combined explanations, $\tilde{Q} = \text{“is the color black?”}$, and \tilde{I} is a blurred version of I where only the *stove* segment remains visible.

A.3.6 Prompts

Extracting relevant concepts prompt

“how many nouns and adjectives in the question: {Question} ? answer only with a list in the following format: noun1#noun2#noun3#....”

Masking concepts prompt

“Substitute ‘_____’ in the question: {Question} by {Masking type} the word: {Concept}. The new question should have the same length and structure. Do not add any additional characters to the new words.”

Creating question from concepts

“Return the answer only.

concepts: brown, object

concepts: brown, object

answer: dog

question: is the brown object dog?

concepts: object, brown

answer: dog

question: is the brown object dog?

concepts: big, co##, lor##, ful##, pretty

answer: glass

question: is the colorful big pretty object a glass?

concepts: tall

answer: building

question: is the building tall?

concepts: boy, dog

answer: 7

new question: does the boy have 7 dogs?

concepts: text, tail

answer: WizzAir

question: is the text on the tail WizzAir?

concepts: vehicle, side, big

answer: van

question: is the big vehicle on the side van?

concepts: {Concepts}

answer: {Answer}

question: ’

Creating question from question and answer

“Return the answer only.

question: what is the brown object?

answer: dog

new question: is the brown object dog?

question: how old is the boy

answer: 2

new question: is the boy 2 year old?

question: what is behind the tree

answer: building

new question: is the building behind the tree?

question: why is she holding a bottle of water?

answer: because it is hot

new question: is she holding a cup of water because it is hot?

question: what is the big vehicle on the side of the street?

answer: van

question: is the big vehicle on the side of the street van?

question: {Question}

answer: {Answer}

new question.”

Abbreviations

Table B.1: List of abbreviations

1 General abbreviations	
Acc	Accuracy
AE	Auto-Encoder
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AUC	Area Under the Curve
Avg	Average
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
BLEU	Bilingual Evaluation Understudy score
BLIP	Bootstrapping Language-Image Pre-training
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CIAN	Conditional Invariant Adversarial Networks
Cifar	Canadian Institute For Advanced Research (image dataset)
CL	Continual Learning
CLIP	Contrastive Language-Image Pre-Training
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CP-CSV	Character-Preserving Coherent Story Visualization
CPU	Central Processing Unit

Table B.1: List of abbreviations (Continued)

CV	Computer Vision
DANN	Domain-Adversarial Neural Networks
DBScan	Density-Based Spatial clustering of applications with noise
DCCL	Dynamic Conceptual Contrastive Learning
DETR	DEtection TRansformer
DL	Deep Learning
DPN	Decoupled Prototypical Network
DuCo	Dual Copy story GAN
EU AI Act	European Union’s Artificial Intelligence Act
FC	Fully Connected
FID	Frechet Inception Distance score
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
GCCD	Generalized Continual Category Discovery
GCD	Generalized Category Discovery
GenAI	Generative Artificial Intelligence
GIT	Generative Image-to-text Transformer
GPT	Generative Pretrained Transformer
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
HSI	Hyper-Spectral Imaging
IC	Image Captioning
ICL	In-Context Learning
ID	In-Distribution
ID-OOS	In-Distribution and Out-Of-Scope
iNat	iNaturalist dataset
IQR	Inter-Quartile Range

Table B.1: List of abbreviations (Continued)

KAN	Kolmogorov-Arnold Network
KAT	Kolmogorov-Arnold representation Theorem
LAN	Learnable Activation Network
LLM	Large Language Model
LM	Large Model
LR	Logistic Regression
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
Lvis	Large Vocabulary Instance Segmentation dataset
LVQA	LM-based Visual Question Answering
MART	Memory-Augmented Recurrent Transformer
Massive	Multilingual Amazon Slu resource package (SLURP) for Slot-filling, Intent classification, and Virtual assistant Evaluation dataset
Mini-LM	Mini Language Model
MI	Mesterséges Intelligencia (AI in Hungarian)
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
Mnist	Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology (handwritten digits dataset)
Mscoco	Microsoft Common Objects in Context dataset
NCD	Novel Category Discovery
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NN	Neural Network
OOD	Out-Of-Distribution
OOD-OOS	Out-Of-Distribution and Out-Of-Scope
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
QA	Question Answering
QIR	Quartile Intersection Ratio

Table B.1: List of abbreviations (Continued)

RL	Reinforcement Learning
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
RoBERTa	Robustly optimized BERT pretraining approach
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic curve
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Descent
SHAP	Shapley Additive exPlanations
SHAP-IC	SHAP for Image Captioning
SHAP-QA	SHAP for Question Answering
SV	Story Visualization
SVM	Support vector machine
T2I	Text to Image
T2V	Text to Video
TN	True Negative
TPR	True Positive Ratio
TP	True Positive
Transformer-XL	Transformer-eXtra Long network
UAT	Universal Approximation Theorem
UNO	UNified Objective function
VG	Visual Genome dataset
ViLT	Vision-and-Language Transformer
VQA	Visual Question Answering
VQA _{v2}	Visual Question Answering (iteration 2.0) dataset
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
XLM	cross-lingual Language Model
XLM-R	cross-lingual Language Model trained with RoBERTa approach
XLNet	eXtra Long network
X-VLM	multi-grained Vision Language pre-training Method

Table B.1: List of abbreviations (Continued)

2 Special abbreviations	
Chapter 2 (Thesis I)	
Disc	Discriminator-based algorithm
Dpm	Double Probability Model
S-GCD	Spectral Generalized Category Discovery
Thr	Threshold-based algorithm
Chapter 3 (Thesis II)	
3U-VQA	Usual, Unusual, and Unknown object scenarios for LVQA models with difficulty scoring dataset
NS-OOD	Non-Semantic Out-Of-Distribution dataset
ReaL	Reassessing softmax score by Logits distillation for foundation model based intent classification
ReDiT	Re-evaluating large visual question answering model confidence by defining input scenario Difficulty and applying Temperature mapping
Chapter 4 (Thesis III)	
Mod-StoryGAN	Modular StoryGAN
iPIC-XAI	improving PIC-XAI for enhanced image captioning explanation
iXIC	improved eXplainable AI scoring for Image Captioning
PEX-VQA	Post-hoc Explanations for large Visual Question Answering models
PIC-XAI	Post-hoc Image Captioning Explanation using segmentation
SHAP-VQA	SHAP adapted for Visual Question Answering
XIC	eXplainable AI scoring for Image Captioning

Notations

Table C.1: Used notations

Notation	Description
\mathbb{P}	The set of all probability distributions, and denotes a specific probability distribution if it is subscripted
\mathbb{P}_{ID}	Training (i.e., in-distribution, ID) probability distribution ($\mathbb{P}_{\text{ID}} \subseteq \mathbb{P}$)
\mathbb{P}_{OOD}	Out-of-distribution (OOD) probability distribution ($\mathbb{P}_{\text{OOD}} \subseteq \mathbb{P}$)
P	A prediction's probability score
\mathbb{D}	Dataset
\mathbb{D}_{ID}	Training (i.e., in-distribution, ID) dataset
\mathbb{D}_{OOD}	Out-of-distribution (OOD) dataset
\mathbb{D}_{k}	Labeled dataset
\mathbb{D}_{u}	Unlabeled dataset
X	The set of instances in \mathbb{D}
X_{k}	The set of instances with known labels
X_{u}	The set of instances with unknown labels
Y	The set of the ground-truth labels correspond to X
Y_{k}	The set of known labels
Y_{u}	The set of unknown labels

Table C.1: Used notations (Continued)

Notation	Description
Y_d	The set of dummy labels for all the instances, and Y'_d is the set of dummy labels for the instances with unknown labels
Y'	The new set of assigned labels (i.e., $Y' = Y_k \cup Y'_d$)
\check{Y}_u	The set of discovered labels
\check{Y}	The set of all labels (i.e., $\check{Y} = Y_k \cup \check{Y}_u$)
C	The number of principle components in PCA
M	AI model
K	The number of ID classes
U	The number of unknown categories
N	The number of instances
x_n	The n^{th} instance, or x in short, also denoted as \mathbf{x}_n (or \mathbf{x}) if it is a set
y_n	The n^{th} instance ground-truth label, or y in short, also denoted as \mathbf{y}_n (or \mathbf{y}) if it is a set
V	The final-layer logits for a single prediction, also denoted as \mathbf{V} if it is a set (e.g., for VQA and IC)
W	The length of the prediction of a single instance (for VQA and IC)
S	The length of the story of a single instance (for SV)
\hat{y}_n	The n^{th} instance predicted label, or \hat{y} in short, also denoted as $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_n$ (or $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$) if it is a set
β	Threshold
μ	Mean
σ	Standard deviation
A_K	The original model (K -classifier) accuracy
\hat{A}_{K+1}	The estimated $K + 1$ classification accuracy
A_{K+1}	The exact $K + 1$ classification accuracy
A_{bin}	Binary classification accuracy

Table C.1: Used notations (Continued)

Notation	Description
R_{ID}	ID ratio
R_{OOD}	OOD ratio
ε	A user defined parameter
\hat{T}	The estimated temperature parameters
D	A difficulty score, and d is used if it is for a single criterion/aspect
Q	Quartile
\mathcal{L}	Loss (in an objective function)
θ	Trainable parameters
\mathcal{N}	Gaussian distribution
\mathcal{G}	Generator
\mathcal{D}	Discriminator
ζ	Vocabulary set
\mathbb{R}	The set of real numbers
ω	Learnable weight of an MLP
L	The number of layers
r	Number of the trainable parameters in a layer
Φ	A univariant function, also denoted as $\mathbf{\Phi}$ if it is a set
\mathcal{F}	An XAI algorithm
\tilde{x}	The output of \mathcal{F} (i.e., part of the input), also denoted as $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ if it is a set
\tilde{I}_{test}	The test image for an XAI evaluation method also denoted as $\tilde{\mathbf{I}}_{\text{test}}$ if it is a set
\tilde{Q}_{test}	The test question for an XAI evaluation method, also denoted as $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_{\text{test}}$ if it is a set
ρ	Pearson’s correlation coefficient
I	Number of instances/segments in an image
J	Number of objects/segments in an image

Table C.1: Used notations (Continued)

Notation	Description
\mathcal{S}_j	The j^{th} stage in an (XAI) algorithm
\mathcal{P}	A set of proposed explanations
\hat{z}_{ji}	The similarity score for the i^{th} proposal in the j^{th} stage
Γ	The size ratio of a proposed region (batch of pixels) to the full image
\tilde{p}_i	The i^{th} stage selected proposal
\mathcal{B}	Blurring kernel size
τ	The dependency tag of a word (query) in a sentence (caption)
H	Hallucination score

Appendix **D**

List of algorithms

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- [J1] **Modafar Al-Shouha** and Gábor Szűcs. Single and Combined Algorithms for Open Set Classification on Image Datasets. *Acta Cybernetica*, 2024, 26. Volume, Issue 3, Pages 297-322. (Scopus, Q4).
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